
EXPORT BARRIERS OF THE GARMENTS INDUSTRY IN BANGLADESH

A Doctorate Thesis submitted to the in Partial Fulfilment for the Award of Doctorate in Business Administration.

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Declaration

I declare that the entire thesis is my original work and where I have used information from other researcher's work or information I have stated it clearly with appropriate referencing. I also confirm that this work has not been submitted to any other institution or university.

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Signature:

Personal details withheld.

Acknowledgement

I am thankful to all those individuals who have helped me to complete this thesis research. I want to show my gratitude towards all my teachers who have helped me to complete this project. I have been able to develop my skills about the subject matter related to AN ANALYSIS OF BARRIERS TO THE EXPORT OF GARMENTS: a CASE STUDY FROM BANGLADESH. I would also like to thank all those respondents and managers who have been interviewed to conduct the research. They have given their precious time and valuable information, which has helped me to construct the project. Finally, I would like to thank all my friends and members of my family who have supported me to complete this project.

Abstract

This case study is on the 'barriers to the export of garments goods in Bangladesh'. This dissertation aims to identify the barriers that the garments' industry faces to conduct their daily operations and export goods overseas. The focus of this research is to concentrate on techniques and concepts of the export garment industry in respect of the business scenario in Bangladesh. In this entire research, the researcher has tried to analyse the current position of the garment industry in Bangladesh and the challenges that are faced by the respective owners. In addition to this, the researcher has reviewed existing literature presented by other scholars relating to this topic to underpin theories and concepts which would help analyse the theory and draw a concurrent conclusion. Therefore, the researcher has used various theoretical tools and models to help gain a clear insight into this topic to substantiate the thesis.

Garments industry is under tremendous pressure and therefore this research aids in providing clear and essential recommendations to tackle and mitigate the issues at hand to be able to sustain in today's competitive environment. To be able to carry out an effective research work the researcher has used positivism research philosophy, the inductive approach of research and descriptive research design for this case study. The researcher has carried out the primary investigation by taking the sample size of thirty garment owners among a selection of various organisations of Bangladesh.

Four managers were selected and interviewed for qualitative research purposes based on their experience and knowledge in the industry to ensure that the data have been compiled from learned individuals of the industry. During the interview process, the gestures and postures of the interviewees were considered to deduce and analyse the qualitative data effectively. The quantitative data has been represented in the graphical format along with details explanations of each figure.

The researcher observed that in the present scenario the condition of the export of garments has plateaued due to the several barriers pointed out in this research. These barriers need to be mitigated to rise above the competition and sustain to be able to attract customers. Therefore, the learner has recommended certain strategies so that all the challenges can be mitigated for economic development and sustainability.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.0 Introduction

The research is based on the garment industry in Bangladesh. The readymade garment industry of Bangladesh is facing several challenges nowadays for the competition level and majorly due to the Globalisation. There are several barriers for which the garment industry of Bangladesh is facing several challenges and it is affecting the whole apparel industry of Bangladesh. It can be said that readymade garments that are majorly exported to other countries have become important for the economic development of the country. The garment industry affects GDP and it enhances to create jobs for the people over the last 3 decades in Bangladesh. When garment products are exported to other countries, it boosts the economic development of the country and in addition to this, it helps to provide more jobs to the people of Bangladesh.

Recently, it has been seen that there was a tremendous success in the export of readymade garments from Bangladesh and since the last 2 decades, this industry is creating optimistic optimization for economic development. In the current scenario, the garment export sector has been considered as the multi-billion-dollar export and manufacturing industry within Bangladesh. The entire impact of readymade garment export can be considered as most significant to have economic and social developments in Bangladesh. There is huge influx of women workers and those are employed for the production of clothes that are used for the exports. Therefore, it can be said that the garment export industry has huge implications on the economy and society of the country.

According to Mia & Akter (2019) in the recent world, the garment industry has employed approximately 4 million people among which 40% people are employed in the manufacturing department and hence, it can be said that those are directly employed and few people are employed

indirectly and those are approximately 10 million. Furthermore, Bangladesh considers the garment industry as a goose that gives golden eggs and it is going for 15 years till now. Due to this, it has been seen that the garment export industry is dominating the modern economy of Bangladesh regarding revenue from exports, employment generation and secondary impact. Certain events have been considered from the year 1998 because those have highlighted vulnerability in this industry, and it has given both external and internal shocks for supply and demand side. In today's world, this dominating feature and vulnerability have become a concerning matter for policymakers of Bangladesh. From the report of the garment industry in Bangladesh, it has been noticed that this sector has a huge contribution to the country because its export earnings have been estimated approximately 83% of the entire export (Ministry Of Finance, 2020) This has happened because of backward linkages to garments and the development has become slow. As there is a vulnerability in the garment industry, therefore, the policymakers of Bangladesh need to make some policies so that dependency can be reduced hugely so that export of products of other industries can be developed effectively.

However, it is a fact that the garment industry of Bangladesh is having a huge success and support that are given to this industry must not be reduced at any cost because if there is no development in the garment industry, then that will affect the society and economy of the country. However, it can be said that vulnerability can be reduced in Bangladesh by diversifying market mix and products of the garment industry.

Furthermore, it has been observed that knit products in the garment industry are gaining market shares rapidly in comparison to the entire garment export of Bangladesh. This happens because knit products are majorly sold in the quota-free markets and due to this reason; the power of producers of Bangladesh has been reflected on competitive markets of the apparel industry. The

garment industry is export-oriented and hence, it is insulated from the domestic shocks of demand and it continues to be vulnerable in the context of domestic shocks of supply. According to (Ministry Of Finance, 2020), for the export of clothes, Bangladesh heavily relies on the European Union and the US as these 2 regions imports approximately 95% of readymade garments from Bangladesh's textile industry. Percentages of the export to the US and EU can fluctuate highly, however, it has been seen that the share of the US in regards to the garment industry has decreased whereas the share of EU has increased.

1.1 General background of the study

Since, last 3 decades, it has been seen that garment industry greatly contributes to the economic development of Bangladesh because this sector has been considered as the main source of income for the country and that helps in economic development, women empowerment and increasing foreign reserve. This industry has given several opportunities to open the door for employment and thus, job opportunities have increased for the garment export industry. As the garment industry is increasing, marketers have to face several challenges and barriers to get success in the garment industry. As mentioned by Mostafa & Klepper, (2018), the journey of the garment industry had commenced in the late 70s and the beginning of early 80s. In the recent scenario, it has been seen that the garment industry has become the most popular industry in Bangladesh and in addition to this; it has contributed a huge amount to the economic development of the country. To export a product, roads and infrastructure must be improved. This research focuses on analysing the barriers of garment export industry.

According to Ahmed et al., (2014) road links in Bangladesh are monitored regularly so that exporting of the garments does not face any type of obstacles, as this will disrupt the business. It has been seen that there was a huge problem when the roads of Bangladesh were submerged in

water/flooded and due to this there were problems in exporting of garments. For instance, an order of US\$15,000 could not be delivered on time because of a flood, almost three hundred thousand labours were affected (Rakib & Adnan, 2015). Due to the flood link/connection between Dhaka and Chittagong was completely blocked. It was a serious threat for the garment exporters. At that time, it has been seen that the garment industry has responded and called the Bangladesh navy so that trawlers can be arranged to remedy the situation.

The exporting of the garments to other countries have been done after renting an aeroplane from Thailand and this has been used so that garment consignments can be sent from airport of Dhaka to airport of Chittagong many times within a day. Hence, it can be said that road linking is the main barrier for the garment export industry. According to Haque & Azmat (2015), RMG contributes a huge amount for the economic development of the country and if there is any type of barrier, then that would cause harm to the development of the economic and social industry. Therefore, the research is highly necessary to identify what effect the barriers of garment export industry are giving on the development of Bangladesh.

Furthermore, it has been seen that export earnings for RMG had increased by 8 times and for this, there was exceptional growth of 17% per annum (BGMEA, 2020). However, there is one major advantage for this RMG industry in Bangladesh and the advantage is that the labour force is cheap and this can provide a competitive edge for competitors of Bangladesh. RMG industry has taken a unique position in the economy of Bangladesh for the last 20 years. In this research, it has been seen that trade liberalisation has been one of the important issues that are faced by the garment industry. This trade liberalisation reduce barrier by eliminating quotas, tariffs, and subsidies but will also competition. It can be said that this trade liberalisation can provide both opportunities and challenges for the RMG sector. In the regime of liberalised trade, it has been seen that

competition among clothing and textiles exporting countries are highly intense. The main aim of this study is to analyse the barriers related to the garment export industry. To analyse, present scenario needs to be analysed through different policies and options that are available so that those barriers can be mitigated to a certain level. Exports that are made by the garment industries in Bangladesh are continuously improving and it needs to be improved more by mitigating certain barriers. It has been found that strike, the shutdown of the company, economic problems, political problems, inflation and many more are the main barriers and it has been considered as the main reason for the decrease in export in the garment and apparel sector of Bangladesh. As mentioned by Hasan & Noh (2017), in regards to exporting of the product, export to the USA is not at all satisfactory, however, at some point in time, it has been noticed that situation has been made better by considering certain essential laws, furthermore, business need to be removed to make the position of Bangladesh much better than before.

1.2 Significance of the Research

This research is very crucial because the garment industry is the main source for income in Bangladesh and it helps in the economic development of Bangladesh. In Bangladesh revenue from exports is a source of significant national earnings and demand and supply of the garments is in the high position in Bangladesh. The apparel industry or garment industry is considered as 100% export-oriented and due to this, the sustainability of the garment industry is highly important for the development of the country. For sustainability, effective linkage among important factors is highly required and such linkage is needed in the context of transportation, banking and others. For the exporting of garment products, road linkages must be effective. There must be good linkages between the roads of Dhaka and Chittagong. Through the port of Dhaka and Chittagong, finished product and raw materials need to be shipped in and shipped out. It has been seen that

even if there is a huge dependence on the air transportation, trucks have been considered as the major transportation medium in Bangladesh to transport finished products and raw materials related to garment industry of Bangladesh. There can be a flood and similar natural calamities and due to this reason, the usual flow of the traffic often gets disrupted.

At some point of time, the road problem becomes severe to a huge extent when maximum portions of the road go underwater and the exporting of the goods become highly problematic. If there are no linkages within the road connection, then it can be taken as the major threat for garment exporters. As the garment industry is rapidly growing in Bangladesh, therefore, it is creating optimal expectations for better development of Bangladesh. Therefore, mitigating such incident is crucial for the development of Bangladesh economy.

In addition to this, trade liberalisation can create both opportunities and challenges for the RMG sector of Bangladesh, as there are certain trade policies such as quotas, tariffs, and subsidies. These trade policies can hamper the RMG sector and it has already become a huge barrier in many cases for the garment industry in Bangladesh. As the garment industry is very important, therefore, the barriers need to be mitigated so that the garment industry can run smoothly. As a result of this, the economic development of Bangladesh is happening to a great extent. Furthermore, it has been seen that there are other causes for which, the export industry gets hampered and those are economic and political problems, strike, the shutdown of company and layout. Therefore, it is highly needed to mitigate these problems and for this purpose, it is highly required to identify the major problems that the garment industry faces and in addition to this, it also needs to be analysed of how these barriers are affecting the development of Bangladesh. This paper addresses these issues and thus contribute to fill the current research gap.

1.3 Problem Statement

Ready-Made garments industry is the main source of export revenue of our country. It has been a stable source of income and over the years it has contributed not only to the economic development of our economy but also to the empowerment of Bangladeshi woman. 85 % of the garment workers are women and push female labour force participation rate up to 36.4 percent. According to Better Work (2019), garments industry consists of 83% of the overall export sector of our country. For sustainable growth of our country, it is imperative a systematic research oriented theoretical framework formed on evidence-based research must exist so that any problem or barrier hampering our garments sector is addressed immediately.

But unfortunately, there has been no aggregate framework which encapsulate the major problems faced by our industry. Evidence looks at the issues independently without any attempt to arrange them in a framework. Research work did not address these issues properly. The Millenium Garment Ltd. is one of the leading companies in Bangladesh, which exports its goods mainly to the European market. According to Rashid & Rashid (2015), as this company exports its garment to various countries, therefore barriers must be mitigated so that exports can be done efficiently. Another company, Rahan Garments Private Ltd. has started its exporting business from the year 1995 and it majorly deals with woven and knit garments, under garments and sportswear. This company does not face any type of transport barriers as its office and plants are located in central portions within the city. Therefore, it can be said that convenience and security for transporting goods must be provided and therefore, supports must be given to facilitate finance and daily production. However, even after providing support, the companies face several problems in the context of the RMG industry.

Unfortunately, the existing researches did not attempt to get a broad overview and tied all this separate links to a whole. This is essential because if we can develop a broad overview and develop an integrated framework, then an effective policy to address these barriers can be designed and implemented. This research paper will try to address this research gap through critical literature review and primary research with individual industry people. This will hopefully contribute toward developing an integrated framework which will address the current research gap and associated industry problem.

1.4 Research Rationale

There is a long history of the apparel industry of Bangladesh and it has been traced from 1965 to 1966 because at that time a company named Mercury Shirts first started exporting the garments to Europe. However, the export of the garments of Bangladesh started growing rapidly in the middle of the 80s. It has been seen that in the years 2015 and 2016, the amount of export had become approximately US\$ 28 billion and therefore, the garment industry has contributed approximately 82% of the entire national export (Ministry Of Finance, 2020). Therefore, it can be said that from these data that the export of Bangladesh and economy of Bangladesh is highly dependent on the RMG sector. As mentioned by Karmaker & Saha (2016), the growth of the garment industry does ensure a higher GNI, it also helps the country to rule against unemployment and poverty. Therefore, it can be said that barriers faced by the garment export industry are a major issue for Bangladesh as it is affecting the development of the country and its economy as a whole. The garment industry has been considered as the main source of foreign exchange in Bangladesh. According to Ritzel et al., (2017), for 25 years, the garment industry is the main division for export. It has been noticed from the report of Bangladesh that factories of Garments employ approximately 40% of overall industrial workers in Bangladesh. Therefore, it is a fact that only the garment

industry has been considered as the best source for employment within Bangladesh. However, apart from all these positive sides, there are challenges that the garment industry of Bangladesh has to face. As in Bangladesh, there are no proper laws, therefore, workers in the industry often lack general labor rights and due to this reason, conflicts have arisen within the industry. These issues often lead to workers strike, negative image of our industry in the global media. If unchecked, these issues may lead to prohibition of export or losing of special benefits. Hence, it is crucial to identify the challenges that Bangladesh has to face while exporting the garments to other countries. Even if Bangladesh is not so developed in other fields, the garment industry is only enriched one among all other industries. As commented by Islam & Jantan, (2017), the garment sector dominates the modern economy regarding export earnings, employment generation, and secondary impact. It has been seen that barriers have been created while exporting the garments to other countries because of raw materials, unskilled workers, the improper environment of working, inadequate managerial knowledge, gender discrimination, wages, insufficient loan, labour cost, poor accommodation facilities, health and safety problems at the factories, price competitiveness, political crisis and finally lead time. These are major barriers in the garment export industry and this is affecting the economic development of the country.

This is a crucial issue because, in the last few years, this prospective sector of Bangladesh is having issues that are emerging from international and local incidents. As mentioned by Huq et al., (2014) in 2013 RMG industry of Bangladesh was shaken to the core when one of the factories, named Tazreen Fashion was destroyed because of fire and due to the collapse of the factory, approximately 1200 workers have died. Therefore, it can be said that due to improper safety measures, nowadays the garment industry is facing huge problems. Therefore, it can be said that in this sector, safety issues are highly neglected and due to this reason, the garments sector of

Bangladesh is lagging behind from maintaining the global standards on fire, workplace safety, environmental implications, hygiene and many more. In this context, the garment industry is facing huge competition from other countries which is a matter of great concern for the future. Bangladesh exports approximately 35 different kinds of garment products and it exports these products to around 31 countries across the world. Due to this reason, the garment industry has been considered as an industry that is 100% export-oriented. In today's scenario, Bangladesh has been considered as an economic competitor in the context of manufacturing of international garment by all other developing countries. But Bangladesh market depends on foreign nations both on supply and demand side. In the opinion of (Islam, et al., 2013) as Bangladesh is depending on foreign suppliers, therefore, it is hampering on development of the garment industry because it often happens that foreign supplier supply those materials which are of low quality and hence, low-quality products are being produced that is directly affecting the exporting of garments to other countries from Bangladesh. In addition to this, knowledge is another big issue nowadays for which exporting of garment industry is being affected. This problem is considered to be a major problem that is linked to the sector. It involves a lack of marketing tactics and in any industry, if marketing tactics are lacking, then it hampers the whole industry. Therefore, it can be said that this has created a negative impact on the Garment export industry. Furthermore, manufacturing methods are small in number, and for this reason; the exporting of the Bangladeshi Garment industry is being hampered. These are all connected with managerial knowledge. According to Riasi (2015), as there is lack of adequate managerial knowledge, the garment export industry is facing issues at the time of loading or unloading of goods and along with this, entry or exit of the product becomes complicated. Process units of garments and textiles are very few and for this, it has become a

barrier for the garment export industry. Therefore, it can be said that as these barriers are affecting the export of garments, these issues need to be identified to some extent.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Astarloa et al, 2015. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 1.1: RMG sector dominates the Bangladesh export

(Source: Astarloa *et al.* 2015)

This has become an issue now and it has been considered as the most important issue because Bangladesh is facing severe challenges in recent times. Export of the garment products of Bangladesh to the EU and the continent of North America that includes the USA had become sluggish in the fiscal year 2017-2018. However, this has happened because of Brexit and National elections. Due to these reasons, the demand for apparel items had declined in the US market. Therefore, it has been found that there was negligible growth in exporting the garment items and that growth will have higher impact on the overall earning in higher rate as this sector comprise of the 83% of the total export earnings (Ministry Of Finance, 2020) and this is highly frustrating. But we had not seen prudent action to address these issues. It stems from lack of appropriate policy

which is further aggravated by lack of research in this field. But this need to be mitigated. We have a very unstable economical, technological, and political situation. It has been seen that the performance of the garment industry was poor for the year 2016-2017 and hence, it needs prudent actions. As mentioned by Hossai et al., (2016), because of the political crisis, the garment industry is facing huge problems and that is also affecting the economic development of the country. In the current scenario, it has been seen that the global market has removed the advantage of quota on the export of garments from Bangladesh from December 2005. Later it faced more barriers. Majorly when the twin tower got destroyed, it has seriously affected the garment export industry of Bangladesh. Bangladesh needs to enjoy the competitive advantage to a great extent so that country can be economically developed. As commented by Mottaleb & Sonobe (2011), other competitors to Bangladesh have applied the policies of sharp price-cutting to export garments to other countries. However, there are still now some companies that lack the knowledge to tackle such competition and overall knowledge regarding the industry, it is creating a barrier for exporting. China and the US have applied these policies for the betterment of the garment export industry. As this is a major issue, therefore, Bangladesh must respond to these policies so that it can enjoy a competitive advantage by having a quota-free market globally. Another important issue for which this industry faces various challenges is the lead time. Lead time is majorly considered to be the time of delivery. This implies the delivery of the ordered garment after the export order is received. However, in this context, the RMG industry of Bangladesh has shown some improvements, but compared to other market competitors, this cannot be held to some commendable improvement. It has been seen for the delivery of woven garments; the lead time is approximately 90 days to 120 days. However, in other countries, like China, the lead time is normally 40 days to 60 days. (Nuruzzaman & Haque, 2009) Therefore, it is a major issue and

therefore, Bangladesh needs to improve its lead time so that these barriers can be removed and it can compete with the international market. As mentioned by Habib (2016), China has shifted its product mix so that high value can be added and that leads to an increasing rate of market shares and it can provide benefit to the producers of RMG like Bangladesh. It can be said that Bangladesh must know certain good measures that can give a better advantage and the opportunity to make profits. It will help in mitigating the current barriers that this industry of garment is facing.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Habib, 2016. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 1.2: Benchmark in the Garment Sector

(Source: Habib, 2016)

This research thus sheds light on the barriers that the garment industry of Bangladesh is facing while exporting the products. The researcher has identified those barriers and has provided probable solutions so that those barriers can be mitigated. In this study, graphical representation has been done and along with those opinions of the proprietors have been taken. This study evaluates the problem that Bangladesh is facing when the products have been exported to other countries. The issues have been analysed properly so that proper solutions can be given.

1.5 Research Aim

The main aim of the study is identifying the barriers and challenges that are faced by readymade garment exporters within Bangladesh. It has been found that barriers are emerging due to the knowledge gap and other trade policies. The knowledge gap rises due to lack of holistic view which can be generated from research focusing to garner broad overview. If those barriers can be identified properly, then feasible solutions can be given. Therefore, it is required to find a feasible solution for Bangladesh so that the barriers can be mitigated.

1.6 Research Objectives

- To critically identify the knowledge barriers while exporting the textiles and RMG products for the producers of Bangladesh
- To assess how these knowledge barriers are preventing the growth of Ready-Made garments sector growth and probable future of the whole export industry.
- To examine the ways that we can address this research gap.
- To integrate theoretical and practical knowledge so that a rigorous and problem-solving methodical framework can be developed.
- To recommend certain knowledge framework so that it can be used for decreasing exporting barriers and hence, the export structure can be improved

1.7 Research Questions

- What kind of knowledge barriers is there that are faced by garment export industry of Bangladesh?
- What strategies can be recommended in the knowledge framework so that exporting barriers can be minimised and streamline for the export process?

1.8 Structure of the Dissertation

Figure 1.3 Structure of the Dissertation

(Source: Created by author)

1.9 Summary

This introduction chapter is related to the entire structure of the dissertation. This chapter has provided the subject matter of research because it is crucial to know the exact topic of the research. The problem statement of the research has been given on various problems that the industry is facing because accordingly solutions can be given to proprietors or marketers of the garment industry of Bangladesh by addressing the existing research gap. Research rationale has been mentioned because firstly, the issues need to be identified so that what type of barriers the country is facing can be identified. It has been seen that Bangladesh is having lots of problems and majorly they are facing problems for knowledge lacking. Due to this reason, they are unable to apply those policies that have been applied by other competing countries. Bangladesh is still not improved in

the garment sector and hence, more improvement is needed in this context as the garment industry of Bangladesh is a major source of income. This helps in the economic development of the country. In addition to this, the reason for these barriers has been mentioned and the researcher needs to concentrate on these reasons for providing certain solutions. RMG industry takes a unique position in the economy of Bangladesh. As it is a major exporting industry within Bangladesh, it has experienced phenomenal growth for 25 years. The workforce of Bangladesh is highly dedicated to the business of garments in Bangladesh and in addition to this; there are entrepreneurial initiatives for making the garment industry of Bangladesh more established than before. As there are several barriers, Bangladesh had to take some relevant measures so that these barriers can be removed and challenges can be converted into opportunities. Importance and significance of this research study have been mentioned here and research aim, objectives and questions have been given to identify the barriers and on that, possible solutions have been given in this study. These aim, objectives and questions have been set because based on these objectives, the research can be conducted effectively. Hence, the researcher needs to concentrate on these objectives and take the research further. Therefore, this helps in identifying barriers and giving possible solutions to marketers of Bangladesh. In the second chapter, that is, in the literature review chapter, all the concepts and underpinning theories are discussed so that the entire research can be carried out effectively.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.0 Introduction

In the second chapter, the researcher needs to critically analyse all the points that are related to the topic. In the first chapter, the aims and objectives have been discussed and based on that the entire literature review needs to be conducted to identify the current barriers in the garment industry. The main aim of this study is to analyse the barriers that the garment industry of Bangladesh is facing and for which the economic development of Bangladesh is being affected. Several concepts are related to the topic and these need to be analysed effectively so that proper measures can be taken. The concepts have been discussed in this chapter clearly to identify the export pattern in Bangladesh. Various underpinning theories have been discussed here that are related to the topic and that needs to be critically analysed. This is crucial so that a comprehensive perspective can be developed aggregating all important variables upon which a theoretical knowledge-based framework can be based. This will help in addressing the problems arising in practice in a consistent, comprehensive and immediate fashion.

2.1 Conceptual framework

A conceptual framework effectively demonstrates the underlying aspect of research. As far as particular research is concerned conceptual framework helps to extract what a reader expects to find as underlying fundamental aspect and aggregate them in a consistent way to address the research issues. The conceptual framework essentially defines the pertinent variables for the study and maps out how they might relate to each other. It is useful to construct a conceptual framework before the beginning of collecting data. This is the general paradigm in managerial research especially in case of an exploratory one. (Saunders et al. 2009) Critical literature review is important in order to establish an overall framework through inductive approach. Based on that, hypothesis

can be developed to test various assumptions. As we find a lack of qualitative research and theoretical framework to address the research gap existing, this approach seemed suitable for the current research. Lastly, it is often symbolized in a graphic or visual layout.

In this research paper, a conceptual framework is created to analyse the export barriers of Bangladesh Garments Industry which are shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework

(Source: Created by author)

2.2 Concept of the export

The term export means the products that have been produced by a country; those products have been purchased by other countries. Exports have been considered as the function of the international trade where goods are produced within one country and those goods are shipped into another country for future trade or sale. These sales of goods add values in GDP as domestic market prices are lower for exported goods. Thus, international trade helps exporting industry to generate

more economic value than otherwise in absence of trade. (Krugmen et al., 2018) Products or services are not a matter of concern and in addition to this, the shipping process is also not a matter of concern when trade is allowed to do. According to Choudhury & Rahman (2017), the products can be shipped or can be carried in the personal luggage. Exports affect the economy to a great extent. There are several countries which want to increase the exports so that the economic development of the country can be achieved. Therefore, for the economic development of a country and for developing the company, all the companies want to sell their products on huge quantity. If the export is more, then the country can enjoy a competitive advantage more than before. As mentioned by Islam et al. (2017), the exports are done more because through the export expertise can be gained by producing products and services. In addition to this, the companies can get knowledge on how the products can be sold to foreign markets.

It has been seen that a country that is having large reserves of currencies, use those reserves in managing value of the currency of their own country. According to Shimu & Islam (2016), countries that have enough foreign reserve due to export income can manage balance of payments and currency exchange ratio easily. Countries can use those currencies to manage liquidity. This implies that inflation can be controlled in a better manner. To control inflation, reserve foreign currency is used for purchasing their local currency. Therefore, this decreases the supply of money and makes local currency worthy. Businesses can only export the products and services where they found a good competitive advantage. This means those companies are better than other companies to provide a particular product.

As mentioned by Ahammad et al. (2017), there are several companies which export the products to reflect the comparative advantage of the country. Countries are having a comparative advantage on those commodities in which they found that they will have natural ability for producing at a

cheaper cost. This perspective was developed in western economic theory based on comparative advantage. (Krugman et. al, 2018)

The world economy was based on mercantile economic theory before advent of the idea of international trade in 19th century. International trade was viewed as a zero-sum game and absolute advantage over every goods and services was deemed to be the way of economic development. But David Ricardo had developed the theory of competitive advantage showing how trading countries can win mutually by trading. At the same time, it has been shown that countries do not need to have absolute advantage but rather comparative advantage to export. The global trading economy is based on country base comparative advantage factors.

Different countries have a different comparative advantage and based on those advantages; the companies take initiatives to export products to other countries. For example, India and China are having enough advantage in manufacturing because of low living standard. Therefore, it can be said exports of some products can be done based on these factors. In addition to this, countries adopt several measures so that export can be increase because if exports are increasing then it leads to the socio-economic development of the countries.

Firstly, it has been seen that countries are using trade protectionism so that proper advantages can be given to the industries. Majorly trade protectionism comprises of the tariffs which help in increasing prices of the imports. In addition to this, trade protectionism provides subsidies so that prices can be lower. It has been seen that when one country starts applying this process, other countries also start applying this process. It has been noticed that as time passes, trading of goods becomes lower for all other countries. Hence, it is considered as a major cause for the Great Depression. These policies are taken in order to protect the interest of particular industry and in the name of public welfare. But often time, this results in loss of welfare for economy as a whole.

For that reason, such policies are not suitable in the long run and often discarded. According to Paul-Majumder & Begum (2016), once subsidies and tariffs help in lowering the trade, countries start doing trade agreement as it helps greater exports through the reduction of trade protectionism. WTO has tried in negotiating an agreement among all nations in the world. However, it has been seen that the United States and European Union have denied eliminating farm subsidies. But trade seem to have develop without barriers between regional parties through agreement like NAFTA which these countries are often unwilling to do with other countries around the globe. In other words, it can be said that all countries need to rely on regional agreements. Moreover, countries need to lower the currency value. If that can be done, then it helps in increasing the export and exports can be increased if prices can be made lower. But low price means low interest rate and currency devaluation often result in higher interest rates. This is problematic for economic growth in the long run. Countries that want to compete through lowering currency; those are accused of currency wars. Balancing these factors are both art and science for which policy makers must strive.

Common methods for exporting goods are direct selling and indirect selling. In the method of indirect selling, export intermediary assumes responsibility to find overseas buyers, products shipping and then getting paid. In the process of direct selling, the producer directly deals with foreign buyers. The decisions regarding exporting and importing of goods can be devoted to the global marketing effort. As opined by Prentice & De Neve (2017), there are certainly major factors on which the indirect or direct marketing depends and those are firm size, nature of products, previous experience of exports and expertise and finally business conditions in a specific market at overseas.

Indirect exporting: There are certain major advantages in regards to indirect marketing and it happens especially in the smaller company. Indirect exporting provides certain ways to penetrate the foreign market without any complexities or risks that take place in case of direct exporting. It has been seen that there are several intermediary firms which offer various export services. It has been seen that each firm type can have individual advantages for a company.

Direct exporting: There are certain advantages of direct exporting and that includes control over the process of exports, potentially higher profits and closer relationships with marketplace and buyer at overseas. As mentioned by Fukunishi & Yamagata (2014), these advantages cannot be achieved easily because organisations need more time, corporate resources and personnel and these are not much needed in the indirect exporting. It can be said when an organisation wants to export products directly in the foreign markets, then internal organisation wants to change more so that complex functions can be supported effectively. For this reason, the direct exporter needs to choose the best channels so that distributions can be done effectively. In addition to this, there must be connections in foreign business so that enough products can be sold. Exporting needs to be done in an organised manner and that must be done in regards to the domestic sales. According to Belal (2016), there are also advantages if the international business can be separated from domestic business. This includes centralisation of the specialised skills and that needs to be dealt with the international markets. This can be a benefit if marketing effort can be focussed properly. As argued by Ahammad *et al.* (2017), there are also disadvantages for this separation. The main disadvantage in this context is the corporate resources are used less and this takes place because of segmentation. Therefore, it can be said that separation must be done on separate levels so that no difficulties can be found. Therefore, it can be said that export needs to be done properly so that barriers can be mitigated effectively. As there are two types of exporting, they are highly linked with the drivers

of export. Their relationship with government is crucial which is related to both the direct and indirect exporting of goods. The government policies are made on the indirect export policies as well as the direct export policies that affect the overall economy of all trading countries.

Figure 2.2 Types of Exporting

(Source: Created by author)

2.3 Drivers of the export

Government is the main driver of export for any country and it helps in boosting the exports more in comparison to the imports because surplus comes more in international trade. Government takes more initiatives; implement export friendly policies, direct monetary policies to boost the exports. Indirect and direct exporting depends upon the government policies and therefore drivers of the export need to consider these before exporting the goods to other countries. According to Akhter et al. (2017), local authorities of every country focus on the new policies to boost the export of garment products. The government of several countries are working on the policies. The Government is adopting Vision 21 strategy to boost the export because proper boosting can be

done, then that leads to good economic development. The government allows exporting of products without any payment of the IGST (integrate Goods and Service Tax) because this matters a lot in case of exporting of goods.

Local Currency Weaker: This is considered as the main reason which can boost export in several countries and that can take place with the help of Government. If the local currency is weaker, that helps in the depreciation of the foreign exchange rate. This implies that exporter can receive more money and hence that boosts the export. Exporter always has the aim to receive more money and if the exchange rate becomes lower, then that helps to do more export in other countries. Therefore, the policymakers must balance currency valuation because the weak local currency can lead to cost-push inflation and due to this reason, import becomes highly expensive. According to Carlson & Bitsch (2018), it is the best time to export for the international business when the local currency becomes weak. This can be considered to start smart and start small. It will be best for the companies to make the provision based on currency conversions and exchange rates. There are political implications when there is a lower currency as this leads to export growth. If the currency is weak, then export of the country can obtain good market share because it is better to obtain goods at a cheaper rate than goods obtained at a higher price with the stronger currency. This results in the increasing rate of sales and that boosts jobs and economic growth. In addition to this, it helps in increasing of corporate profits of those companies that deal with the foreign markets.

But this policy has adverse impact on economy at the long run. The presence of foreign capital often leads to devaluation policy that led to contractionary policy that reduce GDP and GNP in the long run.

In Bangladesh, there are several reasons to worry. First, for any underdeveloped country, inflation can severely affect welfare of poor people as food price can increase dramatically and this impact

seems to be higher in case of countries where food grains are mainly imported from other countries. At the same time, countries which buy capital good from other countries may face severe issues regarding capital growth as capital instrument price will be higher. Inflation thus complicates the outcome of devaluation policy.

When goods are imported from other countries, there are tendencies in climbing inflation because it uses more weak currencies for buying certain goods that price with a stronger currency. In the present world, it has been seen that when economic growth becomes lower, that results in the deflation, falling prices and that leads to bigger risks. As opined by Liu *et al.* (2017), this has created a deflationary mindset within the consumers, and they expect price declines regularly and that has affected on the imports of goods. Therefore, it can be said that this boosts the export of goods to other countries. If the local currency becomes weaker, then that also affects the competitiveness of the garment industry within the country. If it is seen that local currency is weaker, then that leads to boosting of the export to several countries effectively and that is done by the Government.

Competitiveness: Export level can be determined by competitiveness level of the industry and in addition to this, it can be determined by those countries which are having different labour costs, inflation, productivity, raw material price and infrastructure. These factors play a major role in boosting the export of products to other countries. Different countries have different labour costs and based on those exports of goods are done. If the cost is higher, several countries have the tendencies not to do business with that country. This can be majorly affected by the local currency because it helps in the economic development of the country by boosting the exporting of products. It is a fact that if competitiveness can be strengthened, then it can boost exports in an effective manner and because of this, economic development can take place. According to Islam *et al.*

(2018), if the quality of the commodity exports is improved, then that leads to the boosting of the export of products to other countries. With the help of value addition, the quality of the products can be improved and if the product quality gets improved that increases the competitiveness level of the garment industry. In addition to this, price competitiveness is another factor which attracts the countries in exporting of the goods. If there is a drop in the price level, then that helps in exporting of goods. This is done only with the help of making the local currency weaker. Therefore, it can be said that price competitiveness is the major driver of exports. Furthermore, rising inflation is the major driver in the exporting of goods to other countries. An economic survey has been conducted and from the survey, it has been found that open account of capital and exchange rate helps in the boosting of exports.

As mentioned by Brooks (2016), if there is a rise in the exchange rates of rupees, then export competitiveness can erode and for this reason, there is an absence of special package that helps in boosting exports to other countries. In this context, it can be said that policymakers need to grip international trilemma with the help of the capital account. Therefore, it can be said that competitiveness in rupee and capital account is highly crucial to boost exports.

Value-added and quality of exports: It is a fact that products of low price are not only a major driver of the exports. Quality products are needed to boost the exports and it is mainly for garments, pharmaceutical products and food products. The demand for quality products is high in all these products. Therefore, it can be said that change in the price is not so important, rather value-added and quality product is important to export goods to other countries. As commented by Weber, Musiolek & Maher (2015), ministers of several countries are focussing on various areas so that exports can be promoted as it helps in economic development of the country. Majorly, ministers are working on improving the quality of the products. As there are new products and new markets

launching, hence, quality needs to be improved in huge manner. Value addition and export quality are considered as the major drivers for the boosting of export of goods to other countries because that helps in the economic development of the country. Competitiveness depends on every factor that are mentioned here such as local currency, export quality and value addition. This must be considered by the drivers of exporting of goods.

In addition to all these drivers, it has been seen that Ministers of different countries have mentioned that 300 GIs (Geographical Indications) needs to get registered soon because that plays a major role in the boosting to exports. Reputation or qualities of goods are main criteria that every company seeks and hence, it is crucial that in every geographical locations, reputation or qualities of goods needs to be maintained. Therefore, assurance must be given on distinctiveness and quality of the goods and that must be attributable to origin.

Economic Growth: Economic development of the country can be done with the help of all the factors that have been mentioned above and if those factors are not present then that affect the development to a huge extent. Growth in the exports leads to economic growth of the importing countries. Therefore, it can be said that if there is a change in the economy, then that reflects on the export of the goods. If the economy of the country is stagnant or if there is recession, then that damages the export drastically. According to White, Nielsen & Valentini (2017), if economic growth is high, it affects in boosting of exports of good to other countries.

There are some ways of increasing the export level. Firstly, weaker currency needs to be pursued, that means devaluation of the exchange rate. If the value of currency is low, then that makes the export cheaper. This helps in boosting competitiveness. But it has resulted in increase in the inflation rate. Furthermore, if proprietors of the company have trust on the depreciation, exporters can enjoy less incentives for the purpose of cost cutting and hence, long-term productivity can be

improved. Secondly, policies of supply side can be adopted for improving the competitiveness. These policies can be of two types: one is interventionist policies and other one is market-oriented policies. Interventionist policies can be like training and education and on other hand, market-oriented policies are reducing trade unions power and government regulations. Therefore, this helps in increasing productivity by non-interruption as a result of which, export to other countries can be increased. Thirdly, innovations in private sector are crucial. Government of various countries takes several measures in order to promote productivity in the private sector. According to Khan & Ullah (2017), competitiveness depends on the advanced and new technologies and also on management techniques. These are done through government policies. Fourthly, if tariff barriers can be reduced, then that helps in boosting exports. Lower barriers of tariffs help in increasing rate of trade, however, when general barriers of tariffs are reduced, there can be loss out of domestic industries. This happens because they do not have that much capability to compete. As argued by Mondal *et al.* (2017), theory of the comparative advantage has implied that economic welfare can increase and in addition to this, there can be shift within economy. Additionally, reduction in the non-tariff barriers plays a major role in boosting exports. Non-tariff barriers have become an obstacle for trade. If non-tariff barriers have been removed, therefore trade can be made frictionless and thus helps in improving exports.

Figure 2.3 Drivers of Export

(Source: Created by author)

2.4 Challenges of export

If the factors that are mentioned above are not present in an appropriate manner, then that causes challenges in regards to exporting of goods to other countries. Even if exporting has various positive attributes for the company or for countries, however, it poses several challenges in comparison to the local sales. In the domestic sales, the manufacturing unit sell to the wholesalers as well as they do direct selling to the retailers. It has been seen that exporters sell products to importers who in return sell products to wholesalers or retailers. Therefore, exporting of goods within the distribution chain helps in reducing profit margins and thus foreign customers does not feel attractive enough in order to export the goods.

While trading of goods, it is obvious that there will be certain trade barriers. However, in spite of the trade barriers, there are also internal barriers such as lack of proper knowledge on the foreign

market, policies for governing international export, poor understanding on the products standard, negotiating capabilities and many more. Therefore, all these factors create trade barriers in regards to export.

For the purpose of simulating the exports or for protecting domestic products, foreign competition needs to be protected. Government has introduced policies, laws, and regulations which are considered as major source for the trade barriers. Barriers are of different types such as Strategic barriers, tariff barriers, Subsidies, and gaps in knowledge. All these factors highly affect the export of goods to other countries and therefore, economic development of the country is being hampered. It has been seen that in every country, there are certain industries which is the leading industry which contributes a huge investment for development of the country. If the marketer does not have any proper knowledge on the tariff barriers or about laws and regulations, then, they often fail to respond in the appropriate manner. That affects the export of garments to US and EU countries. Therefore, all marketers must have relevant knowledge on every aspect while exporting the goods. In spite of several advantages in exporting of goods, there are several challenges that exporters find while exporting the goods to other countries. Extra cost is required on the purpose of doing exports; extra markets need to be developed. In addition to this, periods for the pay back are longer and there is a requirement of up-front costs so that unique promotional material can be developed. In this context, it can be said that there is a problem in the business strategies for which barriers have been created while exporting and hence, it can be said that there is an exporting challenge. According to Blumer (2015), Personnel need to be allocated more for travelling purpose. Furthermore, other costs for administration are required which are linked with market. At the same time, export product can demand more financial resources which is often difficult for small companies to fulfil.

Product modification is another challenge for the exporting of goods. At the time of exporting, sometimes organisation need to do product modification so that security and safety codes of the foreign country are met and in addition to this, there are also import restrictions for which export of goods get hampered. At some point of time, the modifications are needed at minimum level because these modifications are required in order to satisfy the other countries. The product modification is required for the packaging requirements along with the labelling of the country. Therefore, it can be said that strategies for product modifications need to be applied in such a manner so that barriers can be mitigated.

Figure 2.4: Lifeline of Bangladesh

(Source: Syduzzaman *et al.*, 2016)

For the financial risks, more knowledge is required as if there are any type of financial risks found then it affects every company that belongs to the garment industry because financial risks are considered as the major challenge for every garment industry at the time of exporting the goods. Payment collection methods need to be considered and therefore marketers must have proper knowledge on methods of payment collection. The methods for collection are pre-payment, open-

account, letter of credit, and documentary collection. All these methods are more time-consuming than the domestic sales and moreover, it is highly complicated. Therefore, it becomes difficult for the exporter to export goods such as garments to other countries.

At the same time, legal consequence in times of unforeseen situation must be understood. During Corona pandemic, many international buyers has cancelled orders in undue process which has adversely affected the garments industry. Therefore, legal consequence of contract and payment procedures must be taken in to account

Export documentation and licenses can be another factor to raise barriers while exporting goods to another country. Trends in exporting require less licensing of the exports. It is a fact that every company needs to have export license in order to export the products and help those countries to be more competitive. There are several instances where it can be seen that documentation is mandatory in order to export products to other countries, however, it is not mandatory for the domestic sales. In Bangladesh, it has been seen that there are no such proper laws for the export of goods and therefore, there are no such policies for the export documentation and licensing.

Proper market information is required for proper exporting of goods. It has been seen that due to the knowledge gap, the exporters find it very difficult to export goods to those countries from where enough profit can be obtained. For this, market information is highly crucial. According to Anguelov (2015), finding information related to foreign markets is important, however, it is highly difficult and in addition to this, it is time-consuming to find relevant and appropriate information. Moreover, domestic markets need to be analysed properly so that proper knowledge on the market can be obtained enough that helps in exporting of goods. It has been seen that the countries, which are less developed, does not have enough information about the foreign markets and this information are on the business practices, characteristics of market and cultural barriers. All these

helps in proper exporting of goods and therefore, the companies must not have knowledge gap in regards to information collection.

In order to enter into the export business, careful planning is required. As stated by Syduzzaman et al., (2016), certain amount of capital, accessibility to the quality product, market know-how, and strategy of competitive pricing, realisation of opportunities and challenges and management commitment is crucial for entering into the export business. Without all these factors, success cannot be achieved in export business. It has been seen that there are no such rules which can help all companies for decision-making related to the export or to obtain success in the business. Therefore, it can be said that all benefits and challenges need to be known by the companies for smooth running of business or to enter into a new market. This helps in realising profit eventually (Dspace.ewubd.edu, 2018).

Economic, political and technological changes are creating integrated, new, highly competitive and rapidly changing international environment. Therefore, as per the environmental concerns, it can be said that adaptable skills are required so that environmental problems related to garment industry can be handled in an effective manner.

Environmental Concerns: Environmental concerns are related to the economic, technological and political changes and it has been done by analysing the market environment of the garment industry. As environmental practices have become irresponsible, therefore strict regulation has been imposed as sustainable solutions. According to Ahmed (2014), environmental issues are highly affecting the export business. When a company is entering into a market, managers need to be sure not only about products, they must have knowledge on the corporate practices. In addition to this, they must conform to the regulations of local environment. In the case of mergers and acquisitions, managers need to ensure that there are no such environmental liabilities that are

hidden because that can rise when deal has been created. In order to position the company, managers need to focus on those aspects of exports which are sustainable and friendly. These are considered as the sensitive issues which can create challenges in export business (Orca.cf.ac.uk, 2018).

Business ethics: As global economy is emerging rapidly; certain standard code of conducts is being emphasised and those business ethics is creating barriers for the export business in different countries. As mentioned by Khosla (2014), practices in most of the countries do not abide by international rules and regulations. These international rules and regulations have been considered as way of running the businesses. It has been seen that exporters need to pay bribe for exporting the goods to other countries. Government is becoming more vigilant to monitor all exports and imports of several countries. In addition to this as there are technological changes taking place that are affecting the garment industry, therefore Government needs to monitor the all the changes minutely so that it does not create any huge risks for garment industry. At the same time, industry practice in one country can vary greatly and can be a matter of ethical concern for others. For example, child labours are often used in underdeveloped countries but seen as a severe crime from western importing countries perspective. Therefore, export industries must have ideas about acceptable business norms and conducts from importing countries perspective.

Resource Costs: For the purpose of entering into overseas market, financial investment and manpower increasing rate is highly important. In addition to this, timescales are considered as an issue and these timescales have pay-back that is of short term in nature, however, these are not necessarily guaranteed. Therefore, it has become a challenge or barriers for exporting goods to other countries. In order to mitigate these issues, knowledge on the financial position of the opposite country needs to be acquired in an appropriate manner. In this context, it can be said that

exporting itself is a challenge; however, it provides huge potential rewards. As mentioned by Ali et al., (2017), if two different countries are going into a relationship through export business, they both can obtain good returns on the investments.

Intellectual property, legal and regulatory issues: There are several barriers that exporters have to face, however, sometimes, intellectual property, legal and regulatory issues help to mitigate those issues instead of creating barriers. Due to regulatory and legal policies, it has been seen that exporters find difficult to export business to other countries. As argued by Paul *et al.* (2017), intellectual properties sometimes help in these issues and it is very helpful to overcome

Difficulty to find and understand overseas customers: It has been noticed that over 35% of the non-exporters have claimed that it is difficult to find potential customers in overseas market and even if they are found, it is not possible to understand them because different countries have different cultures that needs to be understand in order to obtain success in the export of goods to other countries. As stated by Rahman et al. (2018), exporters are facing problems and they are having great fears when it comes to proper documentations of export. If this cannot be understood properly, then that hampers the export business. Language is another problem in different countries because the exporters cannot have the knowledge about the languages of all countries. Hence, because of the knowledge barriers, it has been found that it becomes difficult for the exporters to find appropriate and potential companies and customers in other countries because of the proper understanding of their languages as well as their demands.

International credit risk: International credit risk has been considered to be an important barrier for the export business. According to Hoque & Boateng (2017), the major concern of the company aims at credit worthiness for exporting the goods to abroad. When a company goes into partnership with other company in other country, the major concern is whether that company in abroad is credit

worthy. Based on that fact, the companies look forward to export well to other companies in abroad. Therefore, it can be said that credit worthiness is also a major factor for running business smoothly in the world of globalisation. In Bangladesh, there has been recent scandal when a Norwegian buyer has complained through their embassy after a local company swindled their money after taking contact. This has adverse impact in terms of new foreign investment and subsequent trade.

Red Tape: It has been seen from a report that approximately 25% of the exporters have cited that red tape is considered as key barrier for export. Whether it is international or domestic, it can be said that due to red tape regulation, companies are facing uncertainty and therefore, it is affecting export and productivity of goods. If this becomes the scenario, then the companies are not able to understand whether to export goods in the abroad or not. Therefore, it becomes a tough situation for the exporters to run their business smoothly in abroad. At the same time, bureaucracy may create issues in the intermediary or any stage of the trade which has potential of huge loss which create uncertainties and hamper trade development.

Around 80% of the garments owners has confirmed that they face huge export barriers in the RMG industry. This has been further confirmed in the data analysis from the questionnaire and interview.

Figure 2.5: Challenges of export

(Source: Created by author)

2.5 Apparel industry of Bangladesh

Apparel industry can run in an effective manner only if the exporters and garment owners have proper knowledge about the condition of garment industry of different countries. In addition to this, tariff barrier knowledge is highly important because based on that exporting of goods is done. In Bangladesh, garment industry is considered as backbone of the economy and major source of the income. At some point of time, like India, Bangladesh was also dependent on agriculture. The government of Bangladesh has attempted to reduce poverty through the highest productivity and that comes majorly form Bangladesh apparel sector. Bangladesh is accelerating and changing her

exports at certain intervals of time. After all these actions, apparel industry has become the major export-oriented sector. As mentioned by Tahiduzzaman *et al.* (2018), due to the continuous flood, prices of jute fibres are falling and due to this reason, world demand for jute industry is declining, which was previously main exporting goods of our country. Therefore, function of jute sector has deteriorated which is affecting the economy of Bangladesh. As this took place, therefore, the focus is shifted to role of the production sector and that is majorly on garment industry. In the current scenario, Bangladesh has generated approximately \$5 billion and that generates from cost of the products per year through exporting the garments. Moreover, it has been seen that garment industry of Bangladesh has provided employment to approximately 3 million people within whom 90% are women. In garment industry of Bangladesh, there are 2 non-market elements and these elements perform major function in order to achieve continual success in Garment Industry. These two elements are: (a) there are quotas in market of North America under the Multi-Fibre Arrangement (MFA) and (b) special entry in the European markets. Therefore, it can be said that the entire process is linked with trend of the relocation of the production (Ccsenet.org, 2018).

It has been seen that global economy has been controlled with the help of transfer of the production in the developing world, while the companies, located in the developed countries focus more to develop the core design and technology. A new presentation has been structured and it has been centred on the core-periphery production system. The garment industry of Bangladesh has been controlled by transfer of the production. It has been seen that globalisation of production of garment has started earlier and in current scenario, it is expanding more. The companies in Bangladesh are taking the initiatives to transfer production activities that are of blue collar from developed countries that Bangladesh can provide in less cost. This helps in the cost reduction process and global industrialization. Networking and communication system plays a major role

for development of such economic structure, maintenance and growth in apparently different countries in terms of industrial infrastructure. Once properly developed, such regionally dispersed industrialization seems to be beneficial for all involving parties. It has been seen that export-oriented manufacturing can give good returns.

There were concerns in the past that as an industry, garments sector is not complying with safety standards. Garment's owner did not pay heed to such complaints. But the scenario changed after the Rana Plaza collapse incident. In that collapse, approximately 1130 people died outside the Dhaka, Bangladesh. Bangladesh has become the global spotlight in order to shun garment industry. According to Khan et al. (2017), the country is making cheap clothes in each year. In order to do that, it is violating basic worker rights and workplace procedures. There are several disasters found in the garment industry of Bangladesh, however, garment companies are trying to take some measures so that disasters can be mitigated to a certain extent. As garment industry is trying to mitigate the issues, therefore, workers' life can be improved to a certain extent. It has been seen that in Bangladesh, lives of workers are entirely depended on garment business. In addition to this, the employees who are being involved in these disasters, majority of them are women. It is affecting social and economic life of Bangladesh. For 40 years from the independence, poverty rate has decreased from 80% to 30% or even less in the current scenario. In this scenario, it has been seen that average growth of GDP has become more than 8% and, in this context, garment industry plays a major role.

Industrial revolution of Bangladesh is majorly supported by the manufacturing of garment. According to Jacobs *et al.* (2016), societal changes can be done through the garment industry as well. In addition to this, it is essential to acknowledge safety regulations of the sectors so that garment workers feel protected while working within the garment industry. This has a spill over

effect in terms of workplace safety standard and workers right in other industries where changes are slow and can be only made through implementation of law that cover all industries but initiated with a focus to modify Garment sector. Garment sector of Bangladesh is huge and thus sometimes it becomes dangerous and as a result of this, it becomes difficult in fixing certain issues. Bangladesh industry is growing rapidly because it provided cheaper range of clothes. In the year 2013, it has been noticed that Bangladesh has exported approximately \$31 billion products and it is two times more than what it was 4 year before in year 2009. From the data of International Trade Centre, it has been seen that 90% value, that is approximately \$28 billion, had come from selling the clothes. Therefore, Bangladesh is considered as second-largest apparel exporter of the world and thus it is growing rapidly. As stated by Rahman & Sayeda (2016), cheap clothes in Bangladesh enhance the export growth of Bangladesh.

Figure 2.6: Bangladesh export

(Source: Seddiq & Basak, 2014)

Moreover, it can be said that the garment industry of Bangladesh is much cheaper than China. Bangladesh has risen at a position to a large extent because regulation is lacking and low wages are given to the garment workers and most of the workers are women. Minimum wage of Bangladesh is considered to be the lowest wage across the world. As the fashion brands are looking for cost cutting, therefore, they are moving from China as wages are continuously rising in China. Due to this reason, Bangladesh is becoming an attractive place increasingly for the making of clothes in cheap price. In year 2014, a study has been conducted on fashion industry in collaboration with fashion industry of United States. 60% of the respondents have claimed that Bangladesh is much cheaper than China or than other countries.

It has been noticed that Lax regulations in Bangladesh is the major cause for collapse of Rana Plaza and due to this economic development of the country has been affected to a huge extent. The Government of Bangladesh has pitched very nicely for the garment industry for the purpose of attracting the investment. But their effort was inhibited by this incident. Moreover, it has been seen from year 2001 to year 2011, garment workers of Bangladesh were noticing that incomes are decreasing in regard to the power of purchasing. As argued by Farhana et al. (2015), wages of China have been doubled than that of Bangladesh in regard to same terms. The report has been analysed and that has been noticed that wages in Bangladesh garment sector provides the basic sustenance to the worker's family to a large extent even though the wage is hardly above the living wage. Therefore, as sustenance of workers is dependent on the performance of the apparel industry of Bangladesh, therefore, it can be said that it is only possible to continue the welfare of our workers if the market barriers are removed effectively.

Green revolution in apparel industry: It has been noticed that green factories of RMG in highly environment-friendly and therefore it is rising rapidly within Bangladesh. Due to this reason,

apparel industry of Bangladesh is revolutionising. In addition to this, downward reputation is slowly uplifting across the world. Since, the year 2011, all over 67 RMG factories of Bangladesh has obtained LEED certification. Hence, it can be said that apparel industry of Bangladesh has successfully achieved green revolution for the success of garment industry of Bangladesh. Among 67 factories, 13 factories were rated as platinum, 20 factories of garments were rated as gold and five factories were rated as silver. As mentioned by Seddiqe & Basak (2014), approximately 222 factories are registered with USGBC for LEED certification. Industry insiders of Bangladesh have mentioned that green factories are increasing to a large extent because nowadays global retailers always look for eco-friendly manufacturers of garments. This has happened because in present scenario, consumers are highly concerned with the process of producing the clothes as that affect the environment. Bangladesh has been successfully established due to the improvement of global image regarding RMG industry of Bangladesh. More improvement in RMG sector of Bangladesh is required because safety of the workers within the factories is highly required because this led to the fatal incidents. According to Adnan, et al., (2015), Bangladesh garment industry has helped in establishing eco-friendly factories which are rebuilding our reputation and thus, attention has been drawn from the popular global brands. Green revolution is only required to make the industry eco-friendlier. The aim of making green factories is to reduce the carbon emissions and hence, green technology in the apparel industry has been adopted to a large extent. It has been noticed that green factories are using 40% of the less energy, 41% of less water and carbon is emitting 35% less in comparison to the regular RMG factory.

Green manufacturers may find challenges when it goes to compete with regular manufacturers in regard to the price range. However, global buyers need to pay more amounts for the green products because green manufacturers always care for both environment and workers. As commented by

Taplin (2014), Bangladesh Government is offering green finance to the RMG sector in order to encourage all other companies so that they build eco-friendly factories. For establishing apparel industry, it has been found that Government is offering loans with interest of 9% and this has been offered majorly to RMG Sector. As per Bangladesh Bank, in the fiscal year 2015-2016, banks are disbursing TK46, 590 crores for loans. Of this entire amount, TK 39695 crore are contributed to the green factories and majorly it is in RMG sector. Sources in RMG sector have mentioned that government need to do more formulation of the industry-friendly policies and that involves import that are of duty-free regarding raw materials. As argued by Rahman & Haque (2016), government must provide incentives so that eco-friendly factories can be established.

According to the Textile Today (2020), that has been released by WTO last month, Bangladesh has been considered as 3rd largest manufacturer of clothing because the growth of this sector is of approximately 4.60%. EU and China have been considered as the biggest manufacturers because its market shares are of 26.2% and 38.6% respectively. On the other hand, there are other leading manufactures and those are India and Vietnam. Market shares are increasing with growth rates of approximately 14% (Wrbpapers.com, 2018). In present world, it has been seen that apparel industry is looking for huge change for which the industry dynamics needs to be redefined. Factors such as financial policies, low rates of interest, and exchange rates in US and Europe are affecting apparel sector. It has been seen that even if the inflation rate is low, prices of the products will increase. Therefore, it has been expected that consumer market will shift in the future. In addition to this, fast fashion is enhancing apparel players so that they think about new strategies that can help to develop garment industry of Bangladesh. Furthermore, it can be said that though labour costs are considered as a key driver; however foreign exchange rates are the biggest issues in the minds of apparel players today.

In the recent years it has been seen that Africa is receiving huge attention this it is expecting to rise as a source of cheap labour so that it becomes top country of sourcing in upcoming years. However, till now, China has become a first choice of destination. In terms of export, top 3 sourcing countries besides China are India, Vietnam and Bangladesh. Scenario is changing slowly and therefore; it can be said that Bangladesh has been considered as leading country in regards to garment industry. As opined by Khan & Ullah (2017), China majorly focuses to cater middle-class people and the garment manufacturers are majorly focusing on the open facilities of Vietnam, Myanmar and Cambodia. However, for international CPOs, Bangladesh has become the top sourcing destinations for the future. Even if Bangladesh is not expected to flourish like the nearest competitors, Bangladesh is great for the garment industry as it helps in the development of economy in Bangladesh.

For Bangladesh, CPO is the most favourite and therefore, it is growing more than the other countries. Due to this reason, Bangladesh is facing several challenges for which potential needs to be checked and hurdles must be driven down. The major issues occur because of the political instability within the country. Due to the political instability, lead time is increasing when raw material is procured and in addition to this, they face difficulties in order to transport the products when the production gets completed. Fast fashion is considered to be area which needs to be treated gently but fast during production and transportation. The garment manufacturers of Bangladesh are getting large orders because demand for garments of Bangladesh is huge. Despite of it, slowdown of the growth had been noticed and that from approximately 13% in the year 2013 to 4.60% in the year 2014. Therefore, based on this situation, future of Bangladesh is the huge matter of concern. Better future of Bangladesh fully depends on the efforts of suppliers and in addition to this; it depends on Government of Bangladesh. Suppliers need to focus on certain weaknesses such

as establishments of the clear standards for the labours and also on the environmental compliance. According to (Syduzzaman, et al., 2016) the staffs must need to improve their management skills and training must be given to the workers so that organisational goals can be achieved in an efficient manner. The workers must be provided with training so that they can have a great knowledge on production process. Government must take initiatives for the purpose of stabilising political situation along with infrastructural development of RMG sector. This helps in reducing costs, lead time and transportation.

Bangladeshi RMG manufacturers has been considered as radar of RMG buyers because they are strong player and they cannot be replaced because it is considered as valuable destination for sourcing. However, competition among sourcing countries can surely increase in near future. The challenges that are found in garment industry needs to be mitigated to a certain extent and that can be done through value addition in the production process. If that can be done, only then RMG sector of Bangladesh can grow more rapidly than before. As commented by Akter & Uddin (2017), RMG sector of Bangladesh is the catalyst to develop Bangladesh. Made in Bangladesh is the tag that brings glory to the country and Bangladesh become prestigious for the garment industry across the globe. The country has limited resources and for this average growth rate of GDP needs to be maintained at 8% and that helps in remarkable human and social development.

Garment industry has made crucial contribution for rebuilding country and it is a fact that economic development can only take place because of the garment industry. It has been seen that garment industry of Bangladesh has started the journey from year 1980. Rights of workers need to have great progress so that they can contribute good things for the betterment of the organisation. Moreover, it has been seen that RMG workers minimum wages have increased by approximately

219% in 5 year. Moreover, labour law needs to be amended again so that workers welfare and rights can be improved.

2.6 Situation of export at other countries

International trade barriers are considered as the reason for most of the political issues among various countries, domestically and also among governments. When a company buys some products that have been produced by other countries at cheaper rate, standard of living rises in both the countries. Trade among different countries is highly important because comparative advantage can be enjoyed, and absolute costs cannot be enjoyed at all. It is a fact that country can enjoy comparative advantage rather than absolute advantage. Due to the comparative advantage, it can be said that standard of living can rise to a great extent in both the countries and this give good news to both countries in regard to the economic development. Even when a developing country does not have the absolute advantage, it can have comparative advantage always so that business can be traded profitably with the advanced economies. Comparative advantage can be different because of the several reasons and due to this reason, situation of the export in other countries are different.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Cheng et al, 2018. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 2.7: Buyers of Bangladesh in other countries

(Source: Cheng et al., 2018)

Trade contributes to the global efficiency. When one country wants to trade, labour and capital have the tendencies to shift towards the trading industries because in those industries these two are mostly used and efficiently used. This shift or movement helps in providing economic welfare of high level to the society. Exporting becomes different for different countries because trade sometimes bring dislocation to the different component of the same product of same companies which are involved in both export and import business. It has been noticed that quotas and tariffs are the major barriers in order to export and import products. As mentioned by Hasan *et al.* (2016), situation of export is different in different countries. In India, the export is growing at fastest pace within 5 years and it has increased by 4.7% that is \$274.65 billion approximately. However, it has been seen that because of the demonetisation in financial year of 2016-2017, it has slowed down the domestic and economic activity from November. However, even if there is demonetisation,

exports are rising from 27.6% to approximately \$29.32 billion. Therefore, it can be said that situation of export in India is quite better than that of other countries. As commented by Cheng et al., (2018), exports are growing faster in India, however, for 4 years, shipments are low and it is not increasing at rapid pace. Therefore, in India, economic development takes place in moderate pace right now which was previously quite high. In addition to this, it has been noticed that imports are growing faster than exports and it has been seen that trade deficit has been widened up to \$10.44 billion approximately. Therefore, in India both imports and exports are in good situation till now. Exports must be good so that it highly affects the economic development.

Export from the China has increased approximately by 12.9% and it is increasing year after year. It has increased to US\$ 200.49 billion in the April 2018. From the market forecasts it has been noticed that export of China has improved from the previous years. China has gained 6.3% growth because the country has been supported by the global solid demand. As mentioned by Islam et al., (2016), the country has experienced trade boom and this has majorly happened since last 2 decades. It has been noticed that Chinese exports are growing rapidly. In 1984, China's export was US\$25 billion and in year 2003, it has been noticed that it had become US\$383 billion. This implies that the position has jumped from approximately 1.5% to approximately 5.8% in the share of world exports. Export activities of China have been considered as highly diversified and dynamic. It has been seen that in year 1987, approximately quarter of the export of China has been classified into the products that are having huge demand worldwide. Within the year 2002, it has been seen that the export has risen to approximately 60%. This implies that same proportion has been recorded by exports of US. As commented by Shahinuzzaman et al., (2017), China is taking initiatives to shift from the simple goods to sophisticated products. In 1980s, it has been seen that approximately 90% of the Chinese exports were consisted of the manufactured items or primary products. These

products were majorly dependent on the natural resources and have used that technology which is low. In year 2002, this figure had dropped down to approximately 50%. On other hand, it has been seen that those exports which are of high-tech had risen, however, that is, lower than 5%. Economic reforms of China are highly impressive; however, it is facing issues regarding structural reform, therefore it is facing new challenges and problems in medium time period. Proportion of the global exports of China had risen to approximately 14% in the last year and in year 2014, it was approximately 12.3%. Due to this reason, it has been seen that Chinese labour cost had risen, however, in last decade, it has been seen that China is losing the market share to the cheaper competitors. As opined by Akter *et al.* (2017), it is not possible to replace China because of lower lead time of China, and in export, delivery times is crucial than price. Due to this reason, export situation at China is at good position because if the Chinese companies promised that they will deliver the product within 45 days, then they mean it. Therefore, export situation in China is highly attractive. Export structure of China is not so much sophisticated in regard to high-income economies; however, its export structure consists of educated labour and therefore, investment is increasing in China to a great extent. Critics have mentioned that, China has ability to move up value chain and this is done because of pressure on the foreign firms for purpose of transferring the technology. Therefore, considering all these it can be said that export situation is well enough. Apart from all these countries, there are export crisis in several countries because of the economic problems and that has been experienced in year 2008. It has been noticed that there are certain fundamental differences due to which there were economic crisis in regard to export. According to Rashid & Taibb (2016), there are major 10 victims which are facing export crisis.

China: With the economy, made on the manufactured exports, China is facing the challenges because of the decreasing demands. Along with this, China is facing several consequences because

cost of production is increasing rapidly. Due to this reason, China is struggling with the export crisis. The government of China is struggling in order to find out certain ways so that financial consequences can be managed in an effective manner. Moreover, it has been noticed that as new source of growth is decreasing, growth is declining in some sectors. Therefore, Chinese Government is now suspecting that there are several individuals who are involved in the corruption and due to this reason, stringent dictatorship needs to be imposed so that unrest and dissent can be controlled in an effective manner.

Russia: Economy of the Russia has been built on export of the raw materials, majorly energy. The national budget of Russia is only funded with the help of exports. There is a pressure on the Russia to export the products in an effective manner, however, they are facing export crisis. In order to mitigate this export crisis, government has taken the initiative to compensate the decline. This can be done through the creation of alliance with Politico-military power in abroad.

Saudi Arabia: Saudi Arabia plays a major role for production of the Arab Oil and this production has made this country a major player in oil industry and within the region. The Saudis had nationalised major company of the oil. It has been seen that Saudi Aramco is the major company of oil and it is facing several problems while exporting their products. Due to this reason, regime needs good cash so that export crisis can be mitigated to a certain level. One of the detriments is the volatile nature of the oil demand. For example, during pandemic, we had seen historical fall of oil price and now we see historical price rise of oil. This uncertainty regarding demand in future has created uncertainty about export income in different period for Saudi Arabia oil industry.

South Korea: South Korea is the major exporter in regard to manufacturing of goods. This ranges from manufacturing of cars to manufacturing of electronics. As mentioned by Rahman & Haque (2016), in South Korea, most of export product is the cause of GDP growth. It has been seen that

growth rate of exports in South Korea has become 3.3% from 3.1%. In addition to this, it has been seen that Bank of Korea has forecasted 4% growth rate, however, growth rate has not yet reached that level. Exports of South Korea have been taken away by China and that includes a significant amount. Due to this reason, the export has declined to a great extent.

Australia: Australia is considered as modern industrial country. Australia is famous for exporting industrial minerals. It has been seen that Australia is facing export crisis due to the decline of demand of the commodities and manufactured goods, however, particularly the minerals. It is one country which is majorly based on the exporting of goods and the exporting is approximately 21% of the GDP. As per the custom agency of China, drop in the Chinese demand have resulted in the declination of approximately \$15 billion in the revenue. Therefore, it can be said that Australia is facing major export crisis and that needs to mitigate as soon as possible.

Zambia: Zambia is famous in the production of the industrial metals of a significant amount. It has been seen that 41% of the GDP comes from the exports and furthermore, it has been seen that copper only make 75% of the GDP. It has been seen that in Zambia, the total exports have declined, and it has been declined by approximately 27%. As commented by Halder *et al.* (2018), Zambia is closing the mines and because of this, currency of the country is performing worst globally. Therefore, it can be said that Zambia is facing huge amount of export crisis.

Angola: Angola is considered as famous oil producer country and this country used to receive approximately 95% of the foreign currency by selling oils to other countries. In year 2014, it has been seen that China majorly had purchased exports of Angola, in 2016, the price of oil in Angola had become very low and due to this reason, this country had to face export crisis to a huge level. As the foreign currency is lacking, therefore, that limits the food amount, construction material

and manufactured goods. It can be said that it is not at all clear that if the export platform gets weak, what consequences will the country need to face in the future.

Nigeria: Nigeria has a powerhouse which produces oil and therefore, Nigeria has taken an initiative of considering disproportionate hit. Exports in terms of GDP have dropped down to 18% in the year 2013. Most of the export in Nigeria is oil and as there were exchange shortage and political instability, the country had to face export crisis. Due to this reason, the country has become unrest and majorly this is happening due to instability.

South Africa: In South Africa, exports have accounted for approximately 31% of the GDP and of this amount, approximately 40% comes from fuels and metals, particularly coal. As mentioned by Khan & Rodrigues (2015), approximately 9.6% of the exports have been obtained by China. In this context, it can be said China needs to be considered as leading importer in regard to some commodities.

Mongolia: In Mongolia, export is approximately 54% of the GDP and if there is a crisis in that export, therefore, it hampers the economic development of the country. This country majorly depends on the Chinese appetite for mineral exports. But export demand is of the volatile. Therefore, the country is facing the export crisis in this context.

Environmental analysis has been done on these countries so that both the domestic and national competitiveness can be identified appropriately because based on the competitiveness level, the garment industry can have the chance to get flourished furthermore.

Saudi Arabia	Angola	Nigeria	South Africa	Mongolia
South Korea	Australia	Zambia	Russia	China

Figure 2.8: Countries faced an export crisis

(Source: Created by author)

2.7 Domestic and National Competitiveness

Domestic and National competitiveness is a major matter of concern because, in the world of globalisation, competitive factors need to be considered while exporting goods to other countries and that has been measured based on the above-mentioned countries. As stated by Ali & Moudud-UI-Huq (2016), globalisation is important in order to broaden and deepen the process and this helps in deepening inter-relationships through international trade, portfolio flows and foreign investment. Due to this reason, the global marketplace for the products can be created. The contemporary era in the global economies majorly has six central characteristics and those are: Firstly, global competition is intensified, and new centres of the production area are emerging all the time. Secondly, the technological environment is exceptionally innovative. Thirdly, transnational corporations have been restructured and spread. Fourthly, the global system of finance is diverse in nature. Fifthly, the role of the state in national and domestic economic affairs is changing rapidly and sixthly, export-oriented industrialisation is becoming more sophisticated and diversified than before. Therefore, it can be said that due to all these characteristics,

competition at domestic and international level is huge. Capital flows and international trade is considered as the important channels to achieve global integration.

The current standard in the globalisation has the widespread interest because this helps in upgrading the national competitiveness to a certain level. National competitiveness and globalisation have considered as the famous issues. Certain economic theories have mentioned that globalisation helps in the greater convergence for economic performance. Competitiveness needs to be highlighted so that exports can be made in an effective manner. Substantial attention has been drawn from the business communities and government for 25 years. Concept of the international competitiveness of the nations is applicable in the context of national economy. To export, nations have adopted trade policies and economic policies because that affect the ability of the organisation and in addition to this, industries involve in the investment and international trade. Competitiveness is highly required for both export and import because competitiveness is the degree under which a country produces certain products and services, and those products are exported to other countries. Competitiveness of the nations is majorly determined by strength of certain factor endowments, demand conditions, competitiveness of the firm strategies, rivalries and structures. Competitiveness cannot be considered as an end; however, it can be considered as a way through which end can be obtained. Both domestic and national competitiveness helps in improving the standard of living; however, there must be fair and free market conditions. This implies that all the country must have the ability for creating, producing, distributing and servicing the products so that international trade can be done in an effective manner.

The major aim that national government has is establishment of such an environment that improves the standard of living. For this reason, we not only need to increase export through higher productivity of garments but also need to increase the quality of workplace as it is part of quality

of living which is required by exporting countries. For this reason, safety, health, and environmental laws need to be abided for avoiding the compliance barriers. The goals need to be achieved in an appropriate manner. The goals need to be achieved through resource allocation and effective management. Hence, it can be said that government of all the countries is coordinating for the purpose of investment and trade and hence, it can be said that this is competition oriented. All the countries take the initiatives to attract FDI. In addition to this, it has been seen that China attracts approximately 49% of its economy only through exports. There can be several competitiveness indexes, and these are done by the international and private organisations. In regard to competitiveness measure, it can be said that there are few factors in the competitiveness which needs to be considered while exporting the goods to other countries.

Domestic economy: If there is huge level of competition in domestic economy, there will be more competitive and productive domestic firms. When firms meet national demand and reach a certain level of productive capacity, they want to export or expand abroad in order to increase profit. As a result of this, there are country prosperity and value-added productivity.

Internationalisation: Economic activities are open internationally and this results in improving the economic performance. Export-led competitiveness must be associated with the growth orientation of the domestic economy. In the opinion of Hasan (2017), higher integration is required with the international economy and that led to obtaining productive and good resource allocation. Moreover, this helps in improving the living standards of the people.

Government: Direct interventions of the state within the business activities have been minimised. Government policies are majorly focused on the creation of the competitive environment for an organisation regarding export goods to other countries. In addition to this, it enhances providing the social and macro-economic conditions which are highly predictable, and this helps in

minimising external risks in the context of economic activities. Therefore, it can be said that effective Government policies are required for both domestic and national competitiveness.

Finance: Finance sector plays a major role in international competitiveness because it supports international competitiveness. The efficiency of the finance sector is required so that the export business of all countries, be it domestically or nationally, can be made successful. Financial integrity and efficiency are essential as business growth require reliable money flow to most efficient and profitable sector time to time. Reliability of the money flow often ensure business operation even at uncertain times.

As mentioned by Farha et al., (2015), international competitiveness is considered as macro sense as it is highly related to the comparative advantage which can be only achieved through exporting the goods to other countries. A country can be considered as competitive if few industries have the capability in producing at the average level. In other words, it can be said that this helps in identifying whether the country can use the resources and therefore, productivity can be measured efficiently. The parameters of the competitiveness are determined at the national level and both macro-level and micro-level are determined. To compete globally, certain ideological and political policies need to be adopted. According to Hossain & Rashid (2015), international competitiveness is defined from two perspectives: one is a micro perspective (firm) and the other one is a macro perspective (nation). The micro perspective of the competitiveness implies about the major competition among the different organisations and it is required to measure the competition within the nation because this affects the international market. As argued by Ullah *et al.* (2017), macro perspectives are concerned with competition among different nations. Competitiveness is the international perspectives and domestic perspectives, based on which the export business is

conducted effectively. If the export business is done, economic performance can be improved. Due to this, both domestic and national competitiveness can be understood properly. As export business helps in the economic development of the organisation, therefore, domestic and international competitiveness must be maintained and in an appropriate manner.

Figure 2.9: Domestic and National Competitiveness

(Source: Created by author)

Export and domestic demand have a negative relationship and the reason for this negative relationship is majorly linked with the demand side. As opined by Sikhdar et al., (2014), at the time of the growth of the domestic demand, related inflationary pressures lead to the declining of price competitiveness regarding export business. As argued by Naved *et al.* (2018), there is a problem with the supply side to have an export business properly. Within the business cycle, resources that are available for export sector sometimes get affected and that affect the performance of the export business. Development of the foreign and domestic markets helps in making the market more dynamic. The analysis must be done at the firm level and that helps in identifying the major factors which help to create a relationship between export and domestic

demand and these relationships will be made at the macroeconomic level. According to Heath & Mobarak (2015), in the domestic market, firms are not at all price takers and thus it allows in providing economic reasoning for negative relationship. These negative relationships need to be mitigated appropriately. Sometimes, export sales may become less profitable or it can also happen that greater effort is required. In this case, capacity production can be limited. In the short run, firms prefer selling in the domestic market if it is noticed that domestic demand is increasing, and it affects export sales. In the domestic market, a short-run firm which concentrates to maximise the profits must face that demand curve that is negatively sloped and due to this reason, foreign markets and domestic markets are being affected. International trades are having several variations for which the marginal costs become constant and this affects the export business in both foreign and domestic markets. If there is demand uncertainty, that gives a shock to the markets which in result affect the export market of different countries.

2.8 Factors affecting the garment industry of Bangladesh

As has been discussed above about the national and domestic competitiveness, therefore it can be said that these factors can contribute to the garment industry of Bangladesh. It has been seen that Bangladesh possesses high potential for the growth of readymade garments. There can be several factors that can affect the garment industry of Bangladesh and majorly it affects the export of the garments to other countries. As mentioned by Paudel & Burke (2015), contented workers, cheap labour and aspiring businessmen contribute effectively for the better development of the organisation. But though these drivers are important for growth, they are often difficult to find simultaneously. For example, cheap labour and content workers are often two different kinds factors that may not coexist. But the level of expectation plays a role here. For example, if a worker has low wage expectation and firms fulfil that, then the workers will be content and firms will also

have cheap labour. It has been seen that the garment industry of Bangladesh is highly strong and it has happened because of the RMG industry of Bangladesh. There are several policies for which the industry has been strengthened. In addition to this, this is a fact that the manufacturing portion of Bangladesh is highly competitive.

In garment industry of Bangladesh, it has been seen that women actively participate and due to this reason, export performance of Bangladesh has become vibrant. As this section of the population was previously not part of the labour force in most cases, they provided huge labour flow to our economy. Due to the RMG sector, real GDP of the Bangladesh is increasing. Due to this RMG industry, it has been seen that living standard of the country has improved and it has improved from low-income status to the middle-income status. According to Hansen (2016), several groups and stakeholders are responsible for the effectiveness and to make Bangladesh more competitive than before. Apart from this, there are more factors for which the Garment industry has become more improved and competitive in Bangladesh. Those factors are garment delivery time, quality and price. These are the factors for which all leading companies in other countries and customers looks and this is highly required for the better economic development of the country. From MFA, it has been seen that Bangladesh is considered as the strongest competitor because the garment industry of Bangladesh uses those raw materials which are expensive in nature and that involves fine machinery and fine fabric to finish ready-made garments. As mentioned by Trần (2017), Bangladesh knows how to take the advantage of different situations so that the garment industry can be developed effectively. The exporters of Bangladesh need to monitor several quotas. However, the economy of Bangladesh is considered as versatile and dispersed in multiple sectors. As there are several competing countries in regards to export, therefore, the garment industry of Bangladesh must not lose any opportunities for its development. Due to this reason, it has been

seen that the business of this industry is running flexibly and quickly. Due to this reason, GDP has increased in this country to a certain extent. As argued by Ofreneo (2017), the RMG sector of Bangladesh sometimes involved itself in violating the working condition. However, this sector is majorly responsible for the creation of the opportunities for the employment as well as it helps in creating the source of the foreign exchange. If there is absence in the labour union, therefore, we see wage discrimination, long working hours. So, it can be said that Bangladesh economy is having poor practices and therefore, it is affecting the RMG sector of Bangladesh. Lack of standard equipment, training, working condition often results in low productivity and at the same time, it also means lack of lucrative contacts from major buyers who are very concerned about the possible reputation damage in case of association with workers unfriendly factories. Due to this reason, it has huge impact on economy of Bangladesh. Therefore, it can be said that even if there are so many problems, all the problems related to labour need to abide by the ILO standard. There are several income group and demographic part who are entirely dependent on the garment industry of Bangladesh and from the report, it has been seen that approximately 3 million women are depending directly on the RMG sector of Bangladesh. Therefore, it can be said if the RMG sector of Bangladesh get affected, then huge number of workers from Bangladesh become highly affected. As argued by Knutsen (2017), even if Bangladesh is running effectively the garment industry, Bangladesh has to face several challenges because in regard to export, they are having huge competition with Vietnam, India and China in the current scenario. Therefore, it can be said that Bangladesh must use certain apex body so that they can overcome present challenges. At the same time, the main detriments of growth are lack of R&D investment and high lead time which require substantial change in the current structure. It will pave up new way of development in an already important and flourished industry. As RMG sector contribute approximately 78% of the

total exports and due to this reason, the economy of this country can be developed in an effective manner by ensuring its growth.

There are several macro-environmental factors that affect the garment industry, and this lies outside the small companies. Business owners do not have much control over the external factors and therefore, its impact is minimal while changing the factors. As mentioned by Crinis (2017), small companies of several countries need to adapt certain macro-environmental factors and that includes technology, consumer characteristics, government influence, economy, and technology. The process that several small companies adopt helps in running the garment industry successfully. There are some factors that have been discussed below:

Consumer factors: Consumer factors include norms, culture, lifestyle, change of population and demographics. All these consumer factors highly affect the garment industry in several ways. It can be said that garment companies need to make the clothes for the purpose of creating styles based on different cultures. When the clothes are exported to several countries, it is important to consider their cultures and lifestyles and accordingly the garments need to be manufactured. According to Mallick & Marques (2016), if a particular culture forms a large group, then clothing manufacturers need to consider these factors to a large extent. Clothing retailers, wholesalers and manufacturers always avoid creating too much of the clothing items that goes beyond the rules and regulations of society. In addition to this, it has been noticed that clothes are created on styles that were worn approximately 100 years before. It can be said that there are aging population in different countries where there is a large demand for pants sizes and jeans, and this include loose-fitting or relaxed jeans. Moreover, it has been seen that in several countries, there is a tendency of expanding the waistlines of some consumers and therefore, while exporting the garment industry, these factors need to be considered. In addition to this, there are some places where baby clothes

are high in demand. Based on the lifestyles, these baby clothes need to manufacture. But as Bangladesh basically manufacture these products rather than design and sell on the markets through own brands, the impact is basically from capacity side. We need to have enough industrial capacity to fulfil the diverse demand rather than worry about designing appropriate products as we are mere sourcing production of foreign brands. At the same time, in case of consumer, we may deem them to be foreign firms rather than foreign consumers of cloths. Appropriate business norms with these people need to be maintained and focus must be given in that.

Technological factors: Technological factors highly affect the garment industry that includes demand, production, and resources. If there are scarcity of the certain materials, then that affect the garment industry to a large extent. For example, if leather is scarce, then that affects the wholesale and retail company because if there is scarcity, then they cannot deliver the leather products within the stipulated time to the customers of different countries. As mentioned by Feng et al., (2017), when the clothing companies considers that there are certain shortages of raw materials, then, the companies have tendencies to increase the price of clothes. It has been noticed that whenever new clothes are being introduced in the market, the demand is shifting from older clothes to new clothes. Therefore, small manufacturers of clothing must discontinue the clothing lines and therefore new clothes are produced so that customers' demands of different countries can be fulfilled. Exporting the garments depends on the choices of the customers and if that is not met properly, then that affect the entire garment industry of a particular countries from which the export of the goods has been made. Therefore, we need to develop proper research function to make deals with parties whose order will less likely to be withdrawn due to shift in consumer choice. But this will mean to deliver product in a short period as product life cycle is often short-term. This will need to develop process and facilities in such a way that Lead time can be reduced. In addition to

this, garment companies can add some equipment within their plants that are more advanced and that can be Robots. However, if that is done, some companies can fire certain workers.

Political and legal factors: These factors are the most crucial factors for affecting the garment industry. It has been seen that clothing industries are repeatedly being affected by certain issues and those issues can be workers' rights as well as laws on the child labour. As stated by Esposito *et al.* (2015), union workers in the manufacturing plants of clothing can picket some employees and it happens majorly when medical benefits or wages becomes less than other workers within same industry. If this takes place for long time, then that affect the production of clothing and due to this, it affects the garment industry to a large extent. Due to this reason, the delivery of fall fashions or spring fashions to retailers get delayed and therefore, it is not delivered within time. In addition to this, often the companies employ little children in their company so that they can run their business smoothly and products can be delivered on time. But in recent ages, even if such incidence is rare, there is a perception that it is happening everywhere. In this context, it can be said that there is a widespread rumour of violating the laws of child labour. Hence, this is considered as negative publicity and therefore, this issue have huge impact on the retailers' profits and sales.

Economic factors: Economic factors have both negative and positive impacts on garment industry. During the period of economic booms, individuals have disposable income more. Therefore, due to this scenario, people have the tendencies to purchase more clothes and thus, it leads to increasing the sales for the clothing manufacturers, retailers and wholesalers. As argued by Esposito *et al.* (2015), recessions always have opposite effect and due to this reason, sales in several clothing entities becomes significantly lower. It has been seen that, sometimes retailer get stuck with the larger amounts of the inventory because they do not get much opportunity to sell

the goods. In this situation, the retailers can sell the garment products at the reduced prices. Clothing retailers and manufacturers sometimes need to sell the lower-priced garment brands for the purpose of competing with other generic brands. As opined by Wahid (2017), consumers often purchase cheaper brands when they are having less disposable income.

Figure 2.10: Factors affecting garment industry

(Source: Created by author)

Therefore, it can be said that all these factors are highly crucial because this helps in the increasing sales of garments as well as it helps in exporting business of garments to other countries. According to Khan & Abasyn (2017), once a garment is being manufactured, it must be sold in market. Therefore, it is highly needed to fulfil the demands of the customers of several countries. In other words, it can be said that customers are the major factors on which, garment industry is depending

and therefore, segmentation is required so that consumers choices can be segmented accordingly. It can be said that the market for the garment industry can be same in which the garments are manufactured. In the current scenario, due to the price competitiveness, it has been seen that nowadays, garments are being manufactured in some parts of world and those are sold in other parts of world. Therefore, it can be said that after the clothes are being manufactured within a company, several costs get involved before the products are sold to final customers. According to Simpson *et al.* (2016), pricing of garment has been done with the help of manufacturing cost and that cost are added to estimated profit percentage. Pricing of the garments is the major factor on which the success of the garment industry depends. Therefore, there are certain major factors that affect the pricing or costing of garments. As pricing can have huge impact directly on the profitability. Therefore, these factors are decided very carefully after the consideration of several factors. If product is first and new in market, the company can get the opportunity for achieving first-mover advantage. In addition to this, companies also get opportunity to set higher retail price and these are opposed when the products have been made generic. At this situation, the companies have to reduce prices and that gets represented in the costing sheet. In this context, it can be said that there are certain major key factors that has huge effect on pricing of garments. But as a manufacturer, Bangladeshi garments will need to develop ways to produce all types of products and even master the complex products production style. Only then, it can have some sellers power over exporters. But as it just source orders, it's natural competitiveness by differentiation is quite low and we see that our competitiveness with other export nations lies on cheap labour only, no product or technological superiority.

Brand recognition: Pricing of the garments depends on the recognition of the brands. According to Ghosh *et al.*, (2016), popular brands are majorly sold at the higher price because of brand

acknowledgement as well as for brand popularity. Whenever, a customer opts for branded product, they have to pay lump sum amount in order to purchase garment products. Associating with major brands will ensure BD garments manufacturers reliable and large order.

Garment Nature: Garment nature is another important factor for which, the prices can be increased as well as it can be lowered. Therefore, it can be said that quality of merchandise decides the mark-downs and price of the products. If the quality of the products is good, then its price is also higher and nowadays, it has been seen that tendencies of consumers is to buy quality products even if the price is higher. Due to lack of R&D investment, there is a constraint in innovative production method capable of producing complex design efficiently in the garments sector in our country.

Garment Size: Again, size specifications have been considered as important factor the pricing of garments. Therefore, it can be said that after garment merchandiser receives the order, they must confirm about right size specifications that has been given by the customers while giving the order. Therefore, it can be said that in garment industry, garment size is the major factor for increasing or decreasing the price.

Market pressure: Market pressure comes from the competition. Competition is the major factor within a market that enhances decision-making in regards to price. As mentioned by Carlson & Bitsch (2018), if two companies within the same market or same industry need to set same price. If one of those two companies set higher price, then that company will be fired from the market. In Bangladesh, export industry is suffering from lower price issues as garment manufacturers often violently compete against each other for order by declining price offer. It has negative impact on overall industry profit. Setting up a producer cartel or government intervention may help but may lead to issues like monopoly and competitive pressure from other low labour cost countries.

Demand and Supply: Pricing of garment products depend on the demand of the products as well as supply of products. If the demand is low and supply is high, therefore, prices are made low and vice versa. When supply is low and demand is high, prices increases and customers opts for those garment products which are having huge supply.

Other costs: There are other costs based on which pricing of the garments are done. These costs include Inventory control, pilferage costs, and storage costs, alteration cost, handling cost, delivering costs, alteration costs and many more. All these costs are considered as an input in order to decide final price of the merchandise.

Figure 2.11: Factors affecting the pricing of garments

(Source: Created by author)

Productivity is another factor that has major effect on the textile industry or garment industry. Therefore, there are some factors that affect the productivity of textile industry. According to

Ahmed, Ahmad & Joarder (2016), productivity implies about the physical relation between quality produced and resource quantity in production course. For exporting the goods to different countries, productivity is highly required as productivity is considered as economics term that refers to ratio of product and the materials that are required in the textile industry. There are several factors that influence the productivity in the textile industry. There are both negative and positive factors for the success of the garment industry and moreover, it can have adverse effect on production and therefore, that affect export business. There are controllable factors which are internal factors and uncontrollable factors which are external factors.

Product factor is the crucial factor that influences productivity. As mentioned by Islam, Rakib & Adnan (2016), output requirements of the products are judged by the usefulness of the products. Benefit factor of cost has been enhanced if benefit can be increased at same cost and other way out is by reducing same benefits. Equipment and plant play a major role in order to enhance productivity. Productivity increases by increasing the availability of plant and that can be done by proper maintenance as well as by reducing idle time. As mentioned by Dhiman & Sharma (2016), through proper attention in utilisation, modernisation, age, investments and cost, productivity can increase. Latest and innovative technology can improve productivity to huge extent. Information technology and automation helps in achieving the improvements for material handling, communication system, Quality control and storage. All these are majorly required for the production of garments. Energy and material consumption must be reduced because that creates the major barrier in the exporting of the garments to other countries as many countries do not seek much interest to compensate with higher price in this respect. Moreover, for improving productivity of the garment sector, human factors are the crucial factor because productivity is possible only if skill and human competence is good. The employees or the staffs need to give

their efforts effectively and that can be only governed through training, experience, education and many more of the employees. Hence, it can be said that motivation of the employees can influence productivity. Therefore, human factors are highly important for productivity.

External factors that influence the productivity are important for success of garment industry. Structural adjustments are needed and that includes both social and economic changes. Economic changes highly influence productivity and those changes include import of the technology, industrial competitiveness and shift in the employment. But this technological improvement is not mere upgrading existing technology only, but also adopting dynamic mindset and management practices. Often it requires administrative overhaul of existing organization. This also require proactive engagement toward change rather than sluggish mere import of new tech. If it can be done, then productivity can grow to a completely new level. Garment industry and its export business is highly influenced by this factor. As commented by Venkatesh, Paluri & Bhattacharya (2016), social changes like participation of women, cultural values, attitudes and education are the important factors on order to improve the productivity. Another major factor that influences the productivity of garment products to greater extent are infrastructure and government. There must be government programs and policies that are important for productivity practices.

2.9 Performance of Apparel sector in Bangladesh

Factors that have been discussed above have the effect on the performance of apparel industry and that must be examined properly in order to identify the status of garment sector of Bangladesh. For garment industry, there were MFA and that has been made on 31st December, 2004. It has been anticipated that if the MFA can be removed, then that leads to the drop in the export business from Bangladesh. However, it has been seen that such adverse impact did not materialized. It has been seen that since 2008, there are several companies which have lost export steam and that is

due to the global recession. But overall, our garment sector seems to be out of this trend. Bangladesh not only maintains the past gains, but also improves the performance in recession and post-MFA periods. It has been seen that apparel and textiles are the major issues for the trade relations among several countries. Due to this reason, several agreements, bilateral and multilateral, were signed between developing and developed countries so that textile quantities can be restricted. In Bangladesh, it has been seen that total export to the apparel export had rose from 0.5% to 76% in year 2005 and 2006.

Development and emergence of RMG industry of Bangladesh has been considered as a by-product of quota based restricted trade that are done globally. After the phase out of MFA, actual performance of the export business of garments has been identified. At some point of time there were potential threats and negative anticipations when MFA phase out was running. However, it has been seen that Bangladesh has a huge ability in achieving the success and it has become idol for several analysts. According to (Ministry Of Finance, 2020), export receipt from the garment industry was approximately \$7.6 billion within fiscal year 2003-2004. In year 2005-2006, the growth record has been recorded as approximately 23.5% and this has been received from the apparel exports. Therefore, it can be said that the performance of the export in Bangladesh is quite better and hence, if there are barriers in export business, that can have huge impact on the economic development of country. From the report of post MFA phase out, it has been understood that export in other countries is increasing between 2001 & 2013. In those years, there were enormous shift in regards to export business in India and Bangladesh. Moreover, it has been noticed that export business from Bangladesh has risen by 200 percent; however, in Turkey and India, exports have increased by 72% and 127% respectively. In year 2009 after phase out, volume of export has reduced in every country. This is because of counter and common effects of the recession.

However, the volumes are increasing from the year 2010. In all the countries, except Hong Kong-China and Korea, successive growth has been achieved in garment industry post phase out of MFA. However, in Bangladesh, exports are flourishing simply. According to the data, export has reached to \$235 billion in the year 2013 and before phase out, it was \$63 billion. In that year, Bangladesh had recorded massive growth of approximately 270% after phase out.

There are certain factors behind the growth of Apparel industry for which Bangladesh has achieved massive success in garment sector.

Restrictions on the export from the China: When the MFA quota had been removed in year 2005, USA and EU have imposed the restriction on export categories from the China. It had continued from 2005 to 2008. Due to this reason, the export business of Bangladesh has achieved a successful growth in the garment industry. As the restrictions have been imposed on China, therefore, it has opened a window for several Asian countries and that include Bangladesh in garment industry. It has been noticed that at initial time of phase out of MFA, export business of Bangladesh to EU had fallen to approximately 3.7 billion euro from 4 billion and that has implied that there was negative growth in apparel industry. It has been seen that after the phase out of the quota, Bangladesh got opportunity for enlarging export of the knit wear items and woven garments to markets of EU and US.

Depreciation of Value of the Bangladeshi currency: Bangladesh currency, that is, taka had depreciated at some point of time and it has been considered as the major factor to attain positive growth so that there can be improvement in the export performance of Bangladesh. According to Lopez-Acevedo & Robertson (2016), in 2004-2007, taka had huge depreciation against US dollar and at that time, it has been seen that Chinese Yuan and Indian Rupees have appreciated at that time. Therefore, in those circumstances, depreciation of taka and phase out of MFA had a great

combination to enhance the growth of garment sector of Bangladesh. However, continuous depreciation to enhance exports cannot be considered as the sustainable way for preserving growth in apparel industry. Therefore, it can be said that if this is continuing repeatedly, therefore, it will be the serious crisis and hence competitiveness cannot be achieved in apparel sector. The depreciation in the value is the serious issue for which export business can develop accordingly or it can fall also for this depreciation. It has been seen in several countries that continuous depreciation is not good for any business. Competitiveness in the apparel sector cannot be measured if there is continuous depreciation in the currency of Bangladesh. The real competitive power lies on the underlying factors upon which business is situated like productive capacity, technological know-how, infrastructure, management and work culture, R&D etc. If artificial drivers like currency devaluation is used without any focus on developing real capacity, the end result can be extremely damaging for the overall industry.

Provides lowest price for product: The major reason behind the success of Bangladesh for garment industry is the price competitiveness and the trend has been estimated for apparel business in the world and that has revealed that those countries which are having low wage rates, get a priority to become major suppliers of apparel initially because garment industry is considered as labour intensive. Therefore, in the industry where labour is intensive, wage rate is considered as important determinant in terms of production cost. According to Uddin & Rahman (2015), in Bangladesh, cost of labour is low because this country always has surplus labour. Therefore, Bangladesh enjoys **for** its capability to keep the wage rates relatively low along with production cost.

Enhancement of the labour productivity: Due to enhancement of labour productivity, performance of the garment sector had improved in an effective manner. It has been seen that

labour productivity within Bangladesh is low in comparison to other countries like Cambodia, China, India, Sri Lanka and Indonesia. Moreover, it is a fact that labour productivity is related with the wages. It implies that if one unit of wage rises, then it is expected that labour productivity will increase by approximately 1.3 units. As over the time, our industry remains in the same productivity level based on the idea of using cheap labour, we did not see any huge productivity gain. But over the years, when apparel makers have started to produce complex products like lingerie, the required workers skill was high and their wage has increased too for specific skill. Therefore, developing a set of sophisticated products is a way to increase productivity, wage rate and overall competitiveness and welfare of our workers. Furthermore, certain other elements are required so that productivity can be developed and those elements are appropriate training, improvement of the compliance situation, entertainment facility, and good behaviour for workers and performance incentives. Therefore, in this context, it can be said labour productivity is crucial.

Figure 2.12: Factors behind the growth of Apparel industry

(Source: Created by author)

2.10 Impact of RMG sector on economy in regard to exporting

RMG sector has the huge impact on the economic development of the country and this can be monitored from several aspects. Majorly it depends on the competitiveness factor and knowledge about the current scenario. Export earnings of Bangladesh are determined by export of the readymade garments to the European countries and North American countries. It has been seen that approximately 75% of earnings from the total exports are coming from the garment sector. The economic crisis can take place if the exports are not done in proper manner. As mentioned by Akter & Ahammed (2018), clothing sector becomes weak because of the global crisis and sometimes this had been taken place due to the entrepreneurs. It has been seen that in year 2007-2008, growth of export of the RMG was approximately 17% and that has increased to approximately 24% in the current fiscal year. All this has happened due to the export of the garments to other countries.

Readymade garments have been considered as the major export industry in Bangladesh and after certain analysis, it has been seen that majority of the earnings come from export and it is growing at satisfactory rate. It has been seen that there is no such strong indication for any type of negative impacts due to economic crisis, future will continue as unpredictable. As prices of the imported commodities are declining, therefore, government can increase the subsidies for agricultural inputs and there are fiscal difficulties. Due to this reason, BOP gets improved and that enables the government for implementing the bail-out package as well as long-term plan for purpose of increasing efficiency and competitiveness of export sector.

RMG sector has huge impact on the economy in regards to export of goods to other countries. Export of RMG contributes towards GDP, retention of local currency and export earnings. In addition to this; it contributes in earnings through foreign exchange. RMG sector of Bangladesh

comprises of knit and woven sub-contents and hence, it has become the export-oriented sector. This sector consists of approximately 95% of woven and 90% of knit exports; these have been directed to the foreign markets. According to Rakib & Adnan (2015), export earnings of the RMG industry of Bangladesh is approximately 5 billion US dollars. In the current scenario, it has been seen that local value is considered as addition for the RMG sector and that is estimated at approximately 45%.

Knitted garments are highly necessary for the growth of the economics of Bangladesh. Knit-RMG is emerging in the recent years and that have been considered as the second phase. Due to this reason, the share is growing rapidly and constantly.

Diversification: In the garment industry, it has been that Bangladesh can accomplish the product diversification. Its product line is extending from Pyjamas, T-shirts, and shirts to the shirts that are having complicated designs. In addition to this, certain branded items have also been developed and that has added values to the retention of local values and export earnings. Complicated items are often high value products and ensure more profit per unit and local brands provide substantial source of sustained revenue in times of uncertainties regarding export for garment manufacturers.

Incremental (grow) contribution: According to Alam, Azim & Alias (2017), as the garment sector is becoming important, therefore, Bangladesh can bring some money out of this sector for incremental growth of export. Growth in garment sector will provide long run economic sustainability and will compensate loss of export revenue from previous major source like jute products.

Addition of value in manufacturing sector: RMG sector of Bangladesh highly contributes to value addition of manufacturing sector. If there is a contribution towards the manufacturing sector, this helps in the economic development of the country. More ever, industrial growth will also result

in job expansion in technical sector which will raise opportunities for higher educated portion of our country.

Wage bill and employment creation: Due to the RMG sector of Bangladesh, it has been seen that wage bill and employment creation can be benefitted effectively. On other words, it can be said that garment sector of Bangladesh is considered as major employers in economy. It has been seen that, in the current scenario, total employment is approximately 20 lakhs out of which 80% of them are women. As mentioned by Rahman & Siddiqui (2015), in year 1990, majority of labour force that were existing in manufacturing sector, were taken by RMG sector. In this context, it has been seen that workers of RMG have received US\$ 316 million. Hence, this has implied that purchasing power of the individuals has grown and we see more contribution due to this growth to savings and expenditures.

Figure 2.13: Impact of RMG sector on economy

(Source: Created by author)

Moreover, there are certain sectoral contributions, and these contributions are done by the RMG sector. In this context both the forward and backward linkages are considered to understand the entire contributions by the RMG sector of the country. Growth of garment sector has linkage industries and thus it has facilitated activities expansion of the service sector. RMG sector of several countries not only helps in growth of weaving, spinning, dyeing and many more activities, however, it has also contributed to other economic activities like insurance, banking, real estate, tourism and hotels, and packaging, transportation and many more. As commented by Sarker & Saadat (2015), RMG sector of Bangladesh has backward linkages with the textile sectors that provide yarn, fabric as well as other ancillaries. Moreover, it has backward linkages with the utilities that involves gas, electricity, spare parts and machinery supplying sectors. Besides this, garment sector of Bangladesh can have forward linkages with communication, transport, trade services and insurance. Considerable subcontracting is there in RMG sector. Therefore, it has been noticed that garment sector Bangladesh has undergone with several changes and those changes have taken place with the addition of the values. From the data of Bangladesh, it has been seen that value addition by the garment sector is approximately 25%. Bangladesh had a base of cotton textile sector in garment industry before the emergence of the export-oriented sector of RMG and it has been identified that relationship with global market is insignificant. To satisfy the need of growth of RMG sector, government of Bangladesh took certain initiatives for declaring textile sector to be thrust sector. The policies of textile came into the picture in year 1995 and that has made a remarkable growth in countries. In Bangladesh, certain incentives have been given by Government and ready market has been provided by RMG industry. Due to this reason, private sector has invested in the industries related to backward linkages.

In RMG sector of Bangladesh, approximately US\$ 0.5 billion investment has come. According to Mozumder & Islam (2018), there are several mills that have come for the operations. Along with this, some new mills are going to set up and this helps in economic development of the country. There are approximately 524 members in BTMA and in addition to this, there are 159 spinning mills approximately. There is installed capacity along to fulfil the domestic and export requirement for the fabric and yarn. Capacity of the actual production in regard to weaving has increased and this is highly required for economic development of country. As production capacity has expanded, capacity utilisation has shown a remarkable improvement which has affected positively on the economic development of country. There are several sectors that are linked with garment industry and hence, those sectors are being affected with the improvement in RMG sector of Bangladesh. According to Chowdhury (2016), as RMG sector is flourishing, captive yarn fabrics are emerging to a great extent and at present it is of 3 million. Therefore, this provides ample opportunity in order to grow the industries of backward linkages. Therefore, this helps in more development of economy of Bangladesh. RMG sector of Bangladesh has contributed towards several sectors such as Insurance and Banking, Logistics and Shipping, Transport Communication, Contribution to the Government Exchequer, Professional services, engineering sector, Utility services, Information Technology, Real Estate, Tourism and Hotel, Waste Recycle Industry, and Consumer market. As RMG sector contributes in these sectors, therefore, it helps in the economic development of the country.

Insurance and Banking: Growth of RMG sector and certain related activities have major contribution towards the rapid growth of finance industry in Bangladesh. As mentioned by Rahman & Al Amin (2016), in year 2012, banking sector has earned nearly about 40 million dollars by doing business of readymade garments and it has earned in terms of L/C (Issuance

Charges) and interest charges. It has been noticed that most of the assets of commercial banks are related to RMG sector within the country. In some of the years commercial banks have borrowed Taka 4500 crore to RMG sector. On the other hand, commercial banks have borrowed approximately Taka 813 crore to woven-RMG sector. Therefore, it can be said that export business of financing is highly dependent on RMG and textile sectors. RMG sector has received Taka 2200 crore in terms of export-finance. A survey of World Bank has provided a report that most of the companies, that is, 98% of the companies are customers of commercial banks and that is because of the working capital and equipment and machine procurement. In addition to this, RMG industry of Bangladesh has contributed a lot towards the insurance sectors of Bangladesh. On an average, premium is paid by garment sector to insurance organisations every year and the amount is approximately 7 million dollars. It has been noticed that all the companies are insured for their plants and machines. Moreover, it is required that RMG exporters always insure their export and import. Therefore, RMG sector contributes huge amount economic development of country.

Logistics and Shipping: Garment sector of Bangladesh has contributed to shipping business within Bangladesh. This helps in stimulating for setting up the container yards, expanding port facilities so that large container can be handled that carries trains, increase storage facilities and the cargo handling. Manufacturers of RMG take the initiative to use the services of the Clearing and Forwarding Agents in order to have custom clearance of inputs as well as finished goods. According to Biswas et al., (2018), usage fees of port that comes from the garment sector, is estimated around 45% of income of port authority. Therefore, the contribution of RMG sector is about US\$ 66 million towards shipping business of Bangladesh in terms of port charges, Commissions of C&F Agents, Forwarding Charges and Freight charges.

Transport Communication: Development and growth of the services of inland transport is because of the RMG sector to the considerable extent. Transport communication is related to services of railway and wheel transport. All these transports are majorly utilised by RMG sector and it is majorly required for the cargo movement and manufacturing. For the safe transportation for products of RMG, concept of the covered van has emerged in Bangladesh. In the year 2002, industry of inland transport has received approximately 28 million dollars in terms of revenue that comes from the RMG Sector.

Contribution to the Government Exchequer: RMG sector plays a major role for government exchequer because this sector contributes indirectly and directly the major amount to government exchequer. As mentioned by Mustafa et al. (2016), RMG sector pays the huge amount for postage and stamp and license renewal and many more. In addition to this, payments are also made for the visa form, GSP form, license form and there are other forms as well. It has been seen that the sector has paid approximately US\$ 3 million to government in terms of direct taxes.

Professional services: In order to run the business smoothly, garment sector majorly utilise the professional services. They receive the services from legal agencies, CA firms and business consultants. It has been seen that estimated contribution towards this service is approximately 4 million dollars.

Engineering sector: Engineering sector is developing majorly for the contributions of RMG sector. Garment sector contributes huge amount and that include payment towards maintenance and repairing, electrical engineering, service of machine tools and maintenance of transport vehicle through which the goods are being transported. Therefore, it can be said that apart from other sectors, RMG sector of Bangladesh contributes major amount towards the engineering sector. This helps in the economic development of the country and this is happening only for the contribution

by RMG. The spill over effect of technical development due to RMG sector development is a really important aspect for future economic growth. Though we have not seen increasing R&D growth in our economy, the existing body of technical knowledge has nevertheless increased than before. The skills acquired through garments manufacturing, capital equipment development, new manufacturing design are being implemented in other industries. We are also seeing development plan for new sector like leather in imitation of RMG sector which can further develop technical workforce employment opportunity. RMG sector is helping technical knowledge workers employment directly and indirectly.

Utility services: Utility services include electricity bills, telephone bills and many more. According to Ansell et al., (2015), RMG sector has contributed approximately 15 million dollars in the financial year 2012 as utility payment. Utility payment is required while paying for the gas, WASA and many more. This also helps in the economic development of the country because majority of the utility bills are paid by RMG sector of Bangladesh.

Information Technology: Garment sector plays catalytic role for growth of ICT sector of Bangladesh. As opined by Mezzadri & Srivastava (2015), RMG sector is highly responsible for generating revenue for ICT sector.

Real Estate: Demand for the development of Real estate by RMG sector is required for accommodating offices along with factories of 3400 garments. This has generated lots of activities for Construction Industry.

Tourism and Hotel: There are approximately 1000 to 1500 apparel buyers who visit Bangladesh due to business purpose each year. In addition to this, representative of those apparel buyers often visits Bangladesh for their business purpose. Due to the RMG sector, there are several tourists who visit Bangladesh and thus, it can be said that this contributes a huge amount to tourism and hotel

industry. This can be considered that tourism and hotel industry contribute largely towards the economic development of the country as RMG sector contributes to tourism and hotel industry.

Waste Recycle Industry: In Bangladesh, approximately, 0.3 million citizens are involved in the waste recycle industry. According to Al-Amin & Hoque (2015), Waste recycle industry obtain materials majorly from RMG sectors. Along with the waste materials, RMG sectors are involved in creating stuff toys, quilts, cushions, patterns and many more. Waste recycle industry is considered as that industry which is highly linked with the economic development of the country.

Consumer market: RMG sector majorly contributes to those consumer markets which are emerging recently. It has been noticed that almost 2 million employees have the demand of consumer goods. Regular earning source leads to increasing rate of basic needs of consumption that includes better healthcare, improved diet, improvements in the housing conditions and family utensils. Moreover, the garment sector is responsible in creating major demands for consuming commodities that are of low cost, cosmetic items, footwear, dresses and fast food. According to Smith et al. (2014), entire garment industry is created for servicing growing demand. Along with this, it has contributed a lot for employment opportunities for several people of local and of different countries.

Apart from all these, RMG sector has social impacts which in turn affect the economic development of the country.

Women empowerment: Due to the participation of women, income gets generated and this helps in making the living standard far better and in addition to this, women get considerable freedom. Job of women ensures that the women must get equitable access for the household resources and hence, it can be said that there is large investment on the human capital of female. RMG sector has given huge employment opportunities and due to this reason, women empowerment is increasing

each day in Bangladesh. Expansion of the employment of women has contributed majorly towards economic development because after women's employment, savings behaviour has been improved to a great extent. Income by female members helps in reducing the dependency on the male income and thus reduces vulnerability. Independent earnings give opportunity to the women to obtain greater share for making decisions for the household. Hence, garment industry helps in empowering women and status improvement.

Savings: It can be said that there must be regular earning member in the family. Regular earning helps the garment workers to have some savings and that helps in the economic development of the country. In several countries, there are schemes for family pensions and if an individual can invest in those schemes, then that helps in the creation of savings. BIDS survey has been conducted to understand that how much people try to save so that their living standard can be improved. 30% of the workers have bank accounts and after the analysis, it can be said that women are the best savers than men. But major source of saving are the owners who had gained enormous amount of profit through this industry. A large portion of it is saved through financial intermediary. And as garment sector is a lucrative business, it was also a major source where financial intermediaries can channel the savings of lenders. In that way, RMG sector has contributed micro and macro savings and efficient use of capital for higher growth and productivity.

Child labour: Child labour has become a major concern in every country of the world. Based on ILO Convention, child labour must be eliminated because it highly affects the economic development of the country. As argued by Yadav (2017), besides women's employment, if child works, then that helps in bringing a good amount of income to the family and that helps in the improvement of the living standard. However, child labour must not be there at any country.

2.11 Impact of garment sector on the women

Garment industry of Bangladesh plays a major role to uplift the vulnerable and poor women. It has been seen that many times women want to fight against their early marriage. As commented by Ahmed & Nathan (2014), women have the power to control the income and hence, that helps them to make decisions at home in an effective manner. In the current scenario, as the women have started working, they are having self-esteem and moreover they can have voice in their society. Presently, about 80% of the workers in garment industry are women. Instead of the poor women, women from north-western districts are majorly joining the garment industry. Female workers of garment industry are majorly highly vulnerable group that involves young, unskilled, poor and sometime illiterate. It has been noticed that there several single women within the society who have faced several difficulties in their life and now they are joining the garment sector.

Garment industry of Bangladesh provides best opportunity of work for women. As mentioned by Rahman & Ehasan (2017), minimum wage has been revised and that improves the harsh working conditions and the employers have also mentioned that there is disrupted production. For many years, it was noticed that garment industry is female-dominated. In the current scenario, 85% of the workers are women. From the perception of the women, development is highly related to their working conditions. All the women workers want to have decent pay and in addition to this, there must be dignified working conditions and work security. As garment industry is employing several women, it is helping the women to get out from the poverty. As argued by Kibria, Matin & Sharmin (2016), most of the garment workers expect decent wages which is far away from current standard. Women have claimed that there is huge pressure and sometimes they have to work overtime and hence, they want good amount of money for their hard work. There are several women workers who only work to fulfil the basic needs. It has been noticed that workers are working 60 to 140

hours overtime per week. Moreover, there are some employees who does not want to work due to gruelling overtime working hours. Due to this exploitation, there is a question mark regarding the true state of women empowerment by garment industry. Despite this, women are more independent that before due to their own earning capability. As commented by Baird et all, (2017), women integration for the paid work is considered as important forces for the purpose of growing equality of gender and emancipation. Social economist has emphasized on how the garment industry is allowing women within Bangladesh for gaining recognition as they are contributing economically in their family. In this context, garment workers become more conscious for their rights. But we need to understand and develop certain factors in order to truly empower woman of the industry. Firstly, it is highly important for understanding the way through which women are integrated in garment industry. Integration of women in the garment factories plays a major role so that garment factories can be established in a well-structured manner. Furthermore, it has been seen that factory owners are taking advantage of the unequal position of women in the society so that flexible, more docile and cheaper workforce can be made available. Rather it can be said that women in the garment industry have faced several challenges because most of the time, women face systematic discrimination with men. Due to this reason, women do not enjoy enough prospects for the promotion. In addition to this, there is no work security which is majorly required for women. As in Bangladesh, most of the garment workers are women, therefore, working environment must be good and as most of the poor women are working in the garment industry, therefore, it is highly required to ensure job security.

Exploitation of the women workers are done so that huge profits can be made and that is done by denying those workers whose basic rights is to produce clothes in an appropriate manner. To outsource the production, most of the organisations have the tendencies to step away from

responsibilities; however, they are having the demand of profitable deal. In face of such exploitation, women are standing up and getting vocal for their rights. Even if there are several challenges, several women are there who are getting involved into the unions and there are labour movements for the purpose of challenging the exploitation and inequalities within garment industry. As mentioned by Nathan, Tewari & Sarkar (2016), in Bangladesh, there are few workers who are defying threats, social oppression, powerful capitalist and violence so that basic rights can be defended. Struggle of women is considered as key for developing the workers, families, and entire societies. In other words, it can be said that all these have important women empowering effect. This helps the women to become stronger by moving out from the poverty. Therefore, the women employees become more independent. Citizens of the Europe play an important role through their purchasing decision and therefore support is needed for to gain their support for woman labour rights.

In every country, it has been seen that apparels are the main choice for the women workers and therefore garment industries are always having the tendencies to employ the women as male workers are less interested to work here. As there are several women working, therefore, there must be certain ethics and that must be maintained in an effective manner. As commented by Sawada, Mahmud & Kitano (2017), in Bangladesh, there are several approaches that are only made for the women to develop the garment industry. NARI is considered as a project for providing training, counselling, and placement services so that talented women can be employed in the garment factories. Therefore, vulnerable, and poor women can be supported financially by employing them in the garment factories.

We need to have an understanding how women workers are selected in garments sector. After the screening, some women are selected and there are orientation course and that are given to all

women. The women are given time for the purpose of developing support systems and social networks. It has been also seen that while giving training for garment industry batches are made and each batch has 300 girls. Those girls are given training on the sewing, quality control and cutting. In this way the female employees can learn several things related to the garment industry. There are several dormitories, and those dormitories can accommodate approximately 600 women for the transitional period and that is of 4 months in each time. Expected results have been identified and in those results, it has been identified that approximately 10800 women has achieved formal employment. Therefore, it can be said that women can achieve good opportunity if women are trained in an effective manner. Therefore, it can be said that if women learn everything related to garment sector, then it can improve the economic condition of their family.

Even if there are risks, jobs in the garment factory provide long-term benefits to Bangladeshi women. But there are also considerable risks. It has been seen that Rana Plaza collapse in April 2013 has provided a picture that is full of risks because in that incident 1100 workers have lost their lives in Bangladesh. While garment industry poses several risks to the workers and due to this reason, improvement is highly needed, new research has been found and in that new research it has been found that industry reshaped the women's lives positively in Bangladesh. As commented by Rahman & Ehasan (2017), Bangladesh women can avoid their early marriage by accessing the garment factory. In addition to this, with the help of garment factory, they can avoid childbirth. Jobs in the garment factory led to development of the women. Instead of the banning of imports, it is suggested that working environment must be improved as several women work in the garment industry. The garment industry is growing rapidly in the last 30 years. The industry is growing 17% on an average each year and now, in current scenario, 75% of the earnings in

Bangladesh comes from the export. 80% of the workers are women and among those, 15% of the women are between 16 to 30 years old.

To study the impact of garment industry on lives of women of Bangladesh, marriage, school enrolment and childbirth from 1400 households in 62 villages of Bangladesh have been examined (Insights.som.yale.edu, 2018). Outcomes for the women have been compared on the basis of exposure to the garment industry work. For this, commuting distance for garment factory has been considered. Moreover, outcomes of women have been compared with their male siblings. Due to these jobs in garment factory, childbirth and marriage has dropped down for 12-18 aged girls. The girls who stay near the garment factory, approximately 28% girls do not want to get married and approximately 29% does not want to give birth to the child. This implies that those women who live far away from factory have major tendency to get married and give birth to child. As girls stay near the garment factory, they delay their marriage because they want to stay in school for a longer time so that they can obtain a good knowledge and this will help them to get jobs in the garment factory of Bangladesh. As mentioned by Mahmud et al. (2017), young women are delaying their marriage as they want to work outside their home.

The girls who are staying near the factory, they are enjoying additional 1.5 years of education in comparison with their brothers. Young women and girls are exposed to the factory jobs when their age is between 10 to 23 years old. Hence, it can be said that rate of women's working in the garment factory has increased by 79%. Therefore, it can be said that garment factory has huge impact on the living standard of women. As these are the effects of RMG sector on Bangladeshi women, therefore, it can be said that RMG sector is considered as the first industry which has provided large scale of the employment opportunities for women within Bangladesh. After the analysis of the retrospective data, it has been found that approximately 15% women have enrolled their names

in the RMG sector. As the factories are opening up, therefore economic opportunities are increasing to a great extent. Due to this reason, it can be said that households are deciding to invest their money for education of the daughters so that they can be established in their future.

Furthermore, it can be said that jobs in the garment industry have contributed towards the women empowerment and it is noticed that those women need to do household works. In the current scenario, it has been seen that empowerment has stopped them to do household works because they now have equal opportunities to work in comparison to the men. From the data, it is recorded that out of 5-line workers of production, 4 workers are female and out of 20 supervisors, 1 worker is definitely women (Theigc.org, 2018). Therefore, from this context, it can be said that women are interested to work to a large extent in the garment factory. Many of the factory owners are women and it is a fact that majority of the talented workers are women. As it has been seen that in several villages in Bangladesh, women and girls are not allowed to work outside the home, therefore, they do not get the opportunity to work and flourish their knowledge that they have gained from their schools. Sometimes vocational training is given to women for the purpose of working in the garment factory and that are very helpful for them. In garment industry of Bangladesh, gender discrimination is not found.

2.12 Theories and Models:

2.12.1 Porter's Diamond Model

The American professor of strategy, Michael Porter has developed the economic model and this model majorly focuses on the small-sized business so that it can help them to understand the competitive position within the global market. As opined by Gearhart (2014), this theory is also known as National Advantage Theory of Porter Diamond. This name is given because all the factors are important for the business competition. According to Michael Porter, competitiveness

of the business is linked with other business performance. In addition to this, certain other factors are bonded together even if it is based on long distance, regional or local context. In addition to this, there are clusters in this model and Michael Porter always use cluster concept for groups of identical products because in this group, extreme competitive pressure exists. Businesses that have clusters compete with each other by analysing it's and competitor's strategy, market position and other relevant factors in order to increase productivity, fostering innovation and improving the business results. The companies that operate in clusters, always works as per the Diamond Model of Porter.

Furthermore, according to this model if there are several advantages, then companies can move forward towards the international market and therefore, international competition can be handled effectively.

International Advantage: Most of the organisations use Diamond Model of Porter so that national advantages can be translated into international advantages. As mentioned by Ruwanpura (2016), this model has suggested that national base of an organisation plays a major role for creating advantages in global scale. In other words, it can be said that home base offers certain basic factors which supports the organisation, and this includes government support. But even though these factors help companies build up initial market position so that they can expand beyond the domestic market, these factors are not equally applicable or present while trying to expand into foreign market. As argued by Wadud & Huda (2017), those factors can create obstructions for building advantages within the global competition. For example, a company may not develop sophisticated cost saving production technique inside the country due to subsidy they get from government which cover most of its cost. But while going to export to other countries, these subsidy factor may not exist and they may see disadvantage in terms of production cost.

There are certain determinants which have been mentioned by Michael Porter and that has been discussed here:

Factor conditions: This is considered as the situation within a country that is related to certain production factors such as infrastructure and knowledge. These factors are considered as relevant factors in order to identify the competitiveness of particular industry. According to Evans (2016), these factors are grouped into the material resources such as human resources that includes qualifications, commitment and labour costs, infrastructure and knowledge resources. However, there are also certain factors that are important and those are research quality, liquidity on the stock markets as well as natural resources that involves mineral oils and climate. Therefore, it can be said that these can be considered as reason in order to create position of international competitiveness.

Supporting and related industries: Success of the market majorly depends on presence of the suppliers. Along with this, market depends on the related industries in the region. It is seen that competitive suppliers majorly enhances internationalisation and innovation. Apart from the suppliers, related companies are highly important. If one company is successful, then that is beneficial for the supporting organisations. Supporting organisation can achieve benefits from each other and this encourages each other through production of complementary products.

Demand Condition: There are several reasons for which a market becomes successful. In this context, it can be said that there are certain interactions among economies of the scale, size of home market and transportation costs. If the producer realizes enough economies of the scale, this helps in providing enough opportunities to some companies so that servicing can be given from the single location. Demand condition can increase only when there is high innovation strategy so that customers get attracted towards the good and demand becomes huge for the home base.

Structure, Strategy and Rivalry: This factor is linked with the way through which the companies can be organised and also managed. In addition to this, corporate objectives need to be structured in an effective manner so that rivalry can be measured with the organisational culture. According to Munir et al. (2017), conditions of the country need to be focussed in order to determine in which place the company need to be established. In addition to this, cultural aspects play an important role in analysing the strategy of the company. Countries, provinces and regions can differ from one country to another country. Moreover, the factors such as working morale, management and interactions among the countries and those countries are shaped with different cultures. In this context, disadvantages and advantages of the companies can be measured and these are considered while setting up the company in some other country. According to this model, it has been noticed that domestic rivalry along with continuous research on the competitive advantage inside the nation coexist together. This helps the organisations to achieve several opportunities in regard to international scale. Besides these factors, chance events and Government forces are required to do competition among several companies.

Government: Government plays a major role to encourage the companies and industries to be more developed both at abroad and at home. Government provides support in financing and constructing the infrastructure (airports, roads). In addition to this, Government invests in the healthcare and education. Therefore, this encourages the organisations to have international trade. As commented by Billah & Manik (2017), Government encourages the organisations for using alternative energy or environmental systems that can affect the production. These are done through granting of subsidies and financial activities.

Chance Events: In most of the markets, chance plays the major role. It provides scope for the innovative companies and these companies are not at all afraid in starting up the new operations.

It is a fact that entrepreneurs majorly start their new organisations in homeland. For these economic advantages are highly required because that provides great opportunities to the new companies. Therefore, it can be said that new companies must search for relevant chances.

Criticisms of the Diamond Model of Porter: This model is popular for the rich meaning and initiatives; however, it is argued by Holtbrügge & Friedmann (2016) that this model is not perfect. Therefore, there are several criticisms of this model. This model has discussed extensively on the economic circles. There are many other authors who have criticised this model to a great extent. They have different views for this model and therefore it can be said Diamond Model of Porter has become weak. It has been criticised that this model has not highlighted decisive role of the technical innovation that are related to industrial competitiveness. Porter has mentioned about function of the technology; however, he had not mentioned about its effect on the industrial competitiveness. According to Samarasinghe, Ariadurai & Perera (2015) Porter had not included the technology as the determining factor in this model. Moreover, Porter has given the stress on providing innovative environment for the business majorly than the rivals. Industry has achieved strong competitiveness after differing the products from the products of rivals. The differences are based on features of the products, packaging, quality and other aspects.

Figure 2.14: Competitive Advantage

(Source: Created by author)

For the purpose of achieving the goals, technological innovation is considered as the radical way. Within the knowledge-based economies, technological innovation has been considered as major competitive determinant within the industry. Since 1980s, theory of economic growth has pointed out that technological innovation is considered as main factor for economic growth. There are few economists who have made accurate research on this model. For the purpose of enhancing industrial competitiveness, technological innovation plays an important role as it helps to improve the productivity, lower costs and management. As argued by Hagos, Singh & Singh (2017), Porter has not focussed on these factors minutely for which still now certain criticisms exist. Furthermore, this model has neglected industrial competitiveness in other nations. It is highly important to pay

attention towards the external sources which are required for the competitiveness of the multinational corporations. However, although there is weakness in the overall model, Diamond model are used for analysing the competitiveness of the garment industry.

2.12.2 Export-base theory

In export-base theory, main representative was Douglas C. North who has been considered as theorists for the regional development which focuses on Export of goods or products help in enhancing the economic development of a country. According to this theory, demand for the products help in producing the products locally within the same region. This theory majorly puts emphasis on development of the export sectors and this has the multiplier role and fields of other regions in the export field and along with this, activities are securities. As opined by Mastamet-Mason & Kachieng'a (2017), exporting is considered as everything that are exported beyond borders of the regional market, especially abroad. There are majorly 3 pillars. Firstly, region must be defined as that area that can have similar common-base. Secondly, development of the economy has been identified by success of the export sector. Thirdly, export base is that determining factor that affects service development and residential potential of particular area. This theory majorly determines the regional development through supporting export that has been currently broadened with the connection. As commented by Wen-ping (2018), without the export market, expansion of economy is not at all possible. This also makes the economy vulnerable to barriers of trade and volatile to international situation which often inhibit trades. Unlike big economies, the domestic market is not big enough to sustain employment and GDP in absence of export. According to this model, export development can come across several obstacles and that includes: Tariff, Exchange rate of currencies and absence of the economic policies. According to Uddin (2014), Export-based theory is majorly based on the regional growth and regional income because on these two factors,

the economic development of one country depends. Analysis of the economic base is considered as the mostly discussed theory and for regional study, this is considered as applicable technique. Export-base theory focuses on the function of the external demand within the economic life of the community. As it is a fact that exports business leads to the economic development of the country. It is majorly seen that export-base theory is based on the urban economic factor that can be improved if exporting of the products can be done in an effective manner. If some countries are having high demand of products of other countries, then export business can be done effectively. This theory has been extended for case of the regions, majorly, subnational area. This area is considered as larger than city. In this context, region is the geographical area that is developed together for the common-export base. Therefore, it can be said that external demand or exports does not consider only economic activities level within the cities. Export-base theory is the conceived framework that helps to determine the national income. However, export-base theory can be applied in the regional growth theory. According to this theory, it can be said that growth of the region depends on the exporting of products and services.

This theory highly supports the export business of the garments to several countries. It has been seen that most of the textile exports come from the countries that are having high income. The countries those are having income level as upper middle; those countries are expanding their exports. In addition to this, these countries are obtaining enough market shares. Therefore, it can be said that region is considered as high matter of concern. Textile exports that come from the countries which belong to low-income, in those countries export remains minimal. For example, Bangladesh is having lower and middle income due to this reason; export is having 95.8% in year 2015. Furthermore, garment and textile export are considered to be economically important for the low-income countries and then that of high-income countries. Hence, it can be said that it varies

from region to region. The lower-middle countries and low-income countries such as Bangladesh, Pakistan, Cambodia and Gambia, can achieve very few opportunities for exporting.

As per the Trade Theory, it has been seen that tariff is one of the popular examples of policy instruments of trade. In addition to this, tariffs are one of the major barriers for exporting and importing of goods. Traditionally, tariffs are used as the major source of the government income as it is kind of tax that are levied on the imported goods. Goods can be traded internationally and while selling those goods, are sold at domestic prices. This also varies from region to region as per the Export-base theory. As mentioned by Doyran (2015), tariff can affect both demand and supply of products. When one particular country imposes tariffs, domestic price of the garment rises accordingly and as a result of this, a tariff reduces the imports and domestic production gets increased. But even in face of tariff and other trade barrier, a country can still increase export of goods if it has competitive advantage over factors that create real product differentiation and provide more supplier power. But underdeveloped countries seem to have less technological advances and relying on low-cost labour only.

2.12.3 Post Keynesian Theory

The export business of every country contributes for the employment. In Bangladesh, it has been seen that export business of garments contributes a huge investment for the employment and therefore, employment opportunity is increasing each day in Bangladesh. In this context, Post Keynesian Theory is considered to understand the employment opportunity. As per the theory of Keynes of the employment, effective demand has signified about an amount that has been spent on consuming products and services as well as on investment. According to this theory, total expenditure is equivalent to national income and that is equal to national output. Hence, it can be

said that effective demand is equivalent to the total expenditure and national output and national income.

There were several classical economists who have given emphasis on the capitalist economy so that equilibrium can be attained in an effective manner, however, in those aspects, Keynes has criticised their theory and has emphasised on his theory of the employment. As commented by Islam, Mustafi & Islam (2016), this theory is entirely based on short run view. For the short run, Keynes has assumed certain production factors. This involves capital goods, labour supply, labour efficiency and technology and all these factors need to be remaining unchanged when employment level is determined. Therefore, it can be said that employment level is highly dependent on the national output and income. Keynes declared that if the national income increases, then that leads to increase in the employment level and vice versa. Therefore, this theory is also termed as income determination theory and employment determination theory. But this theory is grounded on the era of Great Depression, where it was essential to provide jobs for huge unemployed people. But in the long run, the question arrives whether we can really sustain economy through short run stimulus which eventually dies away and does not focus on long term productivity power. For example, BD economy can have short run export and employment growth by devaluation of money, but it will also have negative impact on the economy as a whole. The best alternative is to focus on investing in R&D, technology, better management practices which will give us more competitive advantage.

Effective Demand Principles: In order to discuss about employment theory of Keynes, effective demand principles need to be assessed. According to Shahinuzzaman, Hoque & Saha (2017), short run employment is dependent on the aggregate of effective demand for goods and services. Exporting of goods is only possible if there are high demand for goods and services. If effective

demand increases then that leads to increase of the employment level and if effective demand decreases, employment level decreases. In other words, it can be said that entire employment within the country is determined through total demand within the country. If the entire effective demand gets declined, then that leads to unemployment. As per this theory, effective demand implies an amount spent on consumption of products and services as well as on the investment.

Effective demand is expressed as:

Effective demand = National Income = National Output

Hence, it can be said that effective demand can decline if there is mismatch in the consumption and income and that leads to unemployment. If the national income increases, rate of consumption also increases. However, in the current scenario, it is identified that rate of consumption is slightly low in comparison to national income. Therefore, effective demand can decline. Gap between consumption and income can be reduced if investment opportunities can be increased to a certain level. Consequently, if effective demand increases, then it reduces the employment condition.

Determining the effective demand:

Keynes has utilised major two terms and that includes, aggregate price of supply and demand in order to determine the effective demand. Price of supply and demand contributed extensively for determining the effective demand that further helps to estimate employment level of economy for the stipulated time. As mentioned by Akter et al. (2017), within an economy, employment level is dependent on number of the workers who are employed and it aims to achieve maximum profit.

Furthermore, inflation is another factor that sometimes acts as major barrier in export business. According to this theory, private organisation plays a major role in order to determine macro-economic outcomes. Keynesian economics have advocated the participation of public sector and

that helps in making economic decision with the help of certain process. It has been argued that public sector participates in order to reduce the efficiencies and due to this, private sectors get involved for making decisions. In order to conduct the export business in an effective manner, then that requires proper making of decisions. As mentioned by Rashid & Taibb (2016), Keynesian policy is considered as best approach in order to have export business. Fiscal and monetary policies are considered as collective reflection for which this approach has become the best approach. Furthermore, there are two factors in the monetary policies and that aims to compensate all shortcomings of the monetary policies. Inflation rate can be established by aspiration gap of the actual wage and in addition to this, it can be established by the capability of bargaining for available labour and capital. For export business, right policies need to be established for the success of the export business of any country. In the export business, banks are always involved in the business and hence, there must be systematic economic system so that action plans can be determined in an effective manner.

There are certain factors for which inflation can be spread by applying the Keynesian theory. This can be considered as the main reason for the maintenance of non-full employment in economy. As commented by Rahman & Haque (2016), one of the important characteristics of Post Keynesian Theory is income distribution and economic growth as these two factors are directly related with each other. However, it is noticed that investment rate has become the major determinant and it is same against relative prices and for this neoclassical analysis has been conducted. Export business is required for the economic development of the country. With the help of proper investment, it has been seen that economy can be expanded and there are income effects due to this reason. This does not imply that Keynesian economics entirely ignore the substitution effects. Therefore, it can be said that substitution effects can be for long time periods.

Real world in the historic time is full of uncertainty. It can be said that in the export business there are full of uncertainties. This uncertainty exists because while exporting the goods to another country, it cannot be estimated whether it will be accepted more in the future or not. Element of the uncertainty has been considered as the major element and therefore it is the basic feature in field of the economics. As opined by Halder et al. (2018), economic development of the country can decline if there is huge uncertainty in the export business. However, it is a fact that it is not possible to ascertain the future because as time passed by, choices start varying and hence, due to this reason, a country that is involved with the export business, cannot enjoy the competitiveness. On the contrary to neoclassical growth theory, there is a growth theory of Keynes and that is demand-oriented. This implies that economic growth not only takes place due to supply, but also demand is required to a huge extent. If there is insufficient demand, economic growth of the country is being impeded. The reason for this insufficient demand involves insufficient need and low consumption of investment assets. As per this model, economic performance of this region majorly depends on performance of export-oriented sectors. Economic performance can be improved if proper revenues can flow into a particular region. This helps in establishing of the new industries, capital can be concentrated and in addition to this, workforce needs to be concentrated. According to this theory, growth of the economics is dependent on the growth of products to a great extent. Due to this reason, demand gets enlarged. As mentioned by Paudel & Burke (2015), economic growth can be determined by the exogenous factors. Therefore, it can be said that performance is not at all dependent on the exchange rates and that implies value ration and goods prices that is flowing to and from the region.

Settlement of the innovative export-oriented enterprises means there is direct investment and this enhances cumulative growth of the economics. As this is the scenario, it can be said that demand

can grow due to regional or local deliveries of Export Company. As the consequence, demand for new workforce has occurred and due to this reason commuter's ratio has increased to a great extent. Therefore, it has been noticed that growth of the output in a region has direct relation to regional location of those companies which are engaged in the export activities. Therefore, as per this model, it can be said that export growth leads to proper economic development of a particular country.

2.12.4 Export led Model

Model of Export Led is made to determine the growth and this model is highly required for the export business. Export promotion, policymakers and economists are of high importance for the purpose of ascertaining the role which exports play as the growth strategy. As mentioned by Hansen (2016), majority of the people perceives the export as engine of the growth. The country like Bangladesh and India, are highly biased towards the export and therefore achieve fast growth on domestic market. If there is stability in the business, then that leads to rapid growth of exports. This in result helps in the economic development of the country. There are certain supporters who support outward-looking policies of the growth and they have pointed out growth performance of countries. This can be grown if strategies of the import substitution can be adopted in an effective manner. As commented by Trần (2017), the countries that are biased with the export growth, have expanded both the non-traditional and traditional exports. The export-led growth majorly considers the certain alternative or additional exports, and this is considered as the source of the effective demand. Therefore, it can be said that mostly this strategy gives stress on the export expansion. As per this model, the essence in this strategy is export expansion. As argued by Ofreneo (2017), exports can be treated as the integral part for domestic production. Hence, it has been noticed that

this strategy is entirely different from export expansion strategy. This strategy provides encouragement for the selective exports in specific measures.

Figure 2.15: Reasons for unlimited opportunities

(Source: Created by author)

Export-led growth policy is majorly dependent on assumptions made by international market for one particular commodity. An industry can grow if domestic market is of limited size. Huge international market can provide unlimited opportunities in order to have output expansion. This helps in the growth of the export business. These unlimited opportunities can arise because of 3 reasons: Unlimited demand, Technological process and efficient resource allocation. After using these opportunities, the domestic economy can be accelerated. However, for the purpose of achieving the opportunities, countries like India and Bangladesh must follow efficient and fair-trade policies. As this is the scenario, there is a demand that Government need to manage economy in such a manner that export-orientation can be supported. However, Government support cannot

be considered as internationalist type under the policy of import-substitution and here importing of certain items become restricted.

In a similar manner, it has been noticed that policy cannot be considered as one of the exportable items. Policy involves Government policies that get stimulated and it is moulded in such a manner that increases the export freely and automatically. Model of Export-led growth has been advocated majorly on 3 grounds: Firstly, through expanding demand for the products and services, stimulate the growth from demand side. This implies that limited size of domestic market in regard to industrial goods is not the constraint for industrial growth. Furthermore, export-led strategy can create the conditions for efficient use by expansion of large-scale industries.

As world market provides several products and services, domestic producers need to select right type of activities and this has promised large profits and rapid growth. According to Knutsen (2017), profitable activities need to be chosen so that labour-intensive industries can be favoured. Labour is the reason for which there can be barriers for export business. In some countries, it has been seen that there are surplus labours and hence, there becomes problems. Finally, export-led growth strategy can be carried out at little cost. Furthermore, it is seen that there is no such need for the export incentives as export effort cannot be undertaken for production of the exportable items. As there is such compulsion, therefore, government intervention is not needed. Due to this reason, administrative costs are avoided. In order to achieve success of the export-oriented strategy, exporters need to have the ready access for the imported components so that exportable items can be produced. Furthermore, costs related to the suboptimal plants establishments can be reduced as monopolies are emerging unlikely.

2.13 Three Theories Classical Trade

Apart from the above theories, there are three other theories on classical trade which are highly important for the trading of goods from one country to other country. David Ricardo and Adam Smith have propounded certain theories for the international trade. As per these theories, when one country enters in the foreign trade, benefits can be obtained from resource allocation and specialisation. Foreign trade helps in the emergence of new technologies as well as skills that helps in high productivity. Classical theories of trade are Mercantilism theory, Absolute advantage theory and Comparative Advantage theory.

Mercantilism Theory: This theory generally discourages the import and encourages the export. As mentioned by Crinis (2017), wealth of a particular country depends on that balance which comes by: Export - Import. In this context, Government needs to play an important role within economy so that export can be encouraged and import can be discouraged because export helps in the economic development of the country. Export business is considered to be good as it helps in earning money or foreign exchange, on other hand, import is considered to be bad because there is outflow of the money and that hampers the economic development of the country. This theory is believed to be selfish trade because of the one-way transactions and therefore enhancement of the world trade needs to be ignored. Therefore, mercantilism is considered as the zero-sum game and country gets benefit out of this game. This theory is impractical on the ground as global trade nowadays require trade liberalization from both parties. Though infant industry argument can be applied to particular industry and even seem to be advantageous if proper incentive and development occur as we had seen in case of Chinese Mobile phone industry, it cannot be continued for ever. At the same time, for countries with less economic resources, it is also impractical as they need to rely on import of raw material to survive.

Absolute advantage theory: Absolute advantage theory has stated that when a country needs to specialise in all those products which can be produced efficiently. According to this theory, one production factor is considered, and labour is the considerable factor. Wealth of countries majorly depends on the products and services that are available to citizens. Adam Smith has declared that if one foreign country supplies one commodity that is cheaper, then another country can buy it in order to enjoy the absolute advantage. A trade is beneficial only when one country exports a particular good that has been produced at lower cost than another country.

Comparative Advantage Theory: Comparative Advantage Theory had been propounded by David Ricardo. In this theory, he has stated trades are beneficial for the two countries only when one particular country is having absolute advantage for all products and another country does not have absolute advantage for all products. According to Mallick & Marques (2016), a nation can achieve trade after exporting of products and services and therefore, can enjoy comparative advantage for productivity of goods. This theory has assumed labour as only production factor between two countries and in addition to that, transport cost is zero and therefore, no trade barriers are there within countries.

The three theories discussed above are related and important to the growth of international trade. These are mercantilism theory, absolute advantage theory and comparative advantage theory. These are important for our garment's industry because it is very useful for the policy makers to understand the advantages and disadvantages as well as the possibilities for international trade. These can help to participate in international trade and remove relative obstacles. The mercantilism theory discourages international trade and was created in France before the industrial and French revolution. It shows the importance of the role of the government on export and how to decrease import related to foreign exchange and national reserves. It is also known as the 'zero sum game'

as there is no benefit during trade. But the main question is if it is still relevant in modern times. The idea is that if a country proposes a tariff on another country, they might also put a tariff in retaliation. However, it can benefit the infant industry in order to compete with established foreign industries. This can be done by restricting foreign imports from that industry and subsidizing the infant local industry so that it can grow and develop such as the Chinese mobile phone market. But this cannot be continued forever as the infant industry may not develop properly. This can be related to our garment's industry if we decide to restrict specific materials and invest in them, but it is not possible as there can be retaliation from other countries. From the limitations of the mercantilism theory, the absolute advantage theory was created by Adam Smith. For this theory, the main factor is the labor for production. From this theory, if a country has an absolute advantage in the production of one product at a lower cost, then it should specialize in it while others import that product from this country. However, this may not be possible in Bangladesh and this is shown with David Ricardo's comparative advantage theory. From this theory, it is said that if a country is able to specialize and have absolute advantage in the production of a number of products with its available labor, it is not beneficial. This is because dividing up labor into for different products will make the country less efficient in producing them and other countries may be able to supply them at a lower cost. Even if the technology is less developed and cost of production is slightly higher for a country, the comparative advantage will allow for higher profits in the long run. Therefore, for the garment's industry, even if Bangladesh is lagging behind in the global market its products will have benefits while exporting to other countries due to comparative advantage and can develop further. Even in the international trade, the garment's industry can avoid tariff, excessive interest rates and gain grants on quota. This can allow the industry to hold a strong position in the global market.

Figure 2.16: Classical Trade Theories

(Source: Created by author)

2.14 Literature Gap

Although research is conducted with the best efforts, still there are certain challenges because of the paucity of time and funds. Due to this reason, research has not been made justified. The literature review has been done with the help of secondary sources. As several articles cannot be accessed properly, therefore, several challenges were faced. In addition to this, there were several journals and books were available, with the help of which, the literature review has been done. In those articles, whatever was available was very old and therefore, the data was not so much updated so that present scenario can be understood. It has been seen that lots of changes have taken place recently and those changes have not been updated in an appropriate manner. As there are lots of changes that have taken place in regard to international trade and export policies, relevant

resources have not been obtained from internet. In addition to this, there are several sites that has demanded for the subscription charge and due to this reason, many websites cannot be accessed properly. Due to all these reasons, in present scenario, the new factors that have contributed positively towards the economic development of the country cannot be identified in a proper manner. It has been noticed that several factors are changing in the recent years, as Government is changing. Therefore, evaluation of the difference in the approaches and theories might complete the study if the websites can be accessed and recent data can be made available.

2.15 Summary

This chapter has emphasised on barriers of garment industry that they face while exporting goods to other countries. After the review, it has been noticed that garment industry is very important as it contributes for the economic development of the country in recent world. The research has identified different sectors and emphasised on the garment industry because this sector does the major contribution towards development of country. There are several types in the garment industry; however, the famous one is the Readymade Garment sector. Furthermore, it has been noticed that there are several reasons for which the barriers have been created and therefore export of the goods to other countries get hampered. There are historical, economic and political factors for which barriers have been created to a large extent. All these factors have affected both negative and positive impact on the export business of the country in regard to socio-economic development of the country. This literature review identified the barriers of exporting if garments to other countries through several models and underpinning theories. The theories that have been mentioned in this literature review that needs to be analysed with the help of some methodologies that are discussed in the methodology chapters. Research outline has been discussed in the next chapter based on this methodology.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.0 Introduction:

This chapter chooses and justifies the research method and methodology. The section selects the methods that will be used to assemble data and analysis. Based on the theoretical model developed in chapter 2, this methodology chapter would select and justify the data collection method in this chapter.

The research methodology is a specific procedure that is used to identify, select, process, and analyze information about a topic. The methodology section allows the reader to critically assess a study's overall weight and reliability.

This chapter is about the different research tools and techniques that have been discussed. These tools and techniques are used in order to conduct the study successfully. There are several models and concepts that have been discussed in chapter 2 which is a literature review and that needs to be analysed further in an appropriate manner through certain methodologies. This will help to conduct the study in a proper and well-maintained way. In order to conduct this research, quantitative and qualitative analysis is necessary. In this chapter, different data collection methods have been described. Different methods of data collection in respect to secondary and primary data are described here and proper justification is given for choosing the appropriate method of data collection.

3.1 Research outline:

The research outline helps to make a step-by-step process through which the researcher can plan to complete the research successfully. The researcher needs to frame the research processes in

order to organize the research work systematically. This will help the researcher to conduct the research process according to a proper plan and will decrease the chances of error. The researcher could get an overall structure of the research and this will help the researcher to maintain the flow of the research. As opined by Choy (2014), a research is generally based on specific ideas and models. Framing a proper research outline will help the researcher to find connectivity between the ideas. The researcher will also be able to find the gaps in the research work. Framing a proper outline gives an idea about the conductance procedure of the research and shows the researcher a proper way to proceed with the research. The research outline is framed in order to set goals and determining appropriate procedures to achieve the goals in time. The research framework helps the researcher to make the research in a prospective manner so that it can be completed successfully and diversified results can be obtained. The participants of the research need to complete each section of the research in order to achieve the research aims and objectives. As mentioned by Imel, Budge & Owen (2017), it is necessary for the participants to frame the research outline first in order to complete this research successfully and achieve all the objectives. Therefore, this research outline consists of the research philosophy that is Positivism, a research design that has a descriptive design, and a research approach that is deductive in nature. This helps in the entire research of identifying the barriers in the garment industry.

3.2 Research onion:

Research onion is another vital part of the methodology. This framework helps the researchers by guiding them in a proper way. As stated by Saunder *et al.* (2009), research onion is designed in a layered way. Each stage of the research could be described with the help of research onion in a

proper way. All the approaches could be briefed in a constructive manner with the help of the research onion. Research philosophy is the first layer that is described in the research onion.

Figure 3.1: Research onion

(Source: Saunder *et al.* 2009)

In order to conduct this research, a positivism philosophy has been chosen. The research approach is the second layer in the research onion. In this research, an inductive research approach has been selected. The third step of the research onion consists of research strategy. The participants in research need to frame an appropriate research strategy in order to conduct the research work. Different strategies of research include surveys, interviews, secondary analysis, etc.

Research onion is considered as a layered approach, which consists of three strata. Axiology is a level that is concerned with the study of several values of ideas. As stated by O'Brien *et al.* (2014),

ontology is another layer of research onion that is concerned with finding the reality of the subject matter. The reality of the subject matter of topic could be known with the help of several ways. Epistemology is another layer of the research onion. As discussed, the first layer of the research onion consists of research philosophy. In order to conduct the research, the participants have chosen positivism philosophy. Positivism philosophy deals with those research values that could be tested. The research approach is the second layer and the researcher has chosen the inductive approach in order to accomplish the research objectives. The inductive approach has been chosen because it helps the researcher to create new theories and values from the existing data. As opined by Mackey & Gass (2015), the inductive research approach helps the participants of the research to widen the scope of the research with the help of questions of the research. Inductive approach is most appropriate when there is a lack of prior research in the existing literature. As I find that there is already a research gap regarding knowledge gap about export barriers, I could not take a deductive approach and conduct quantitative analysis based on axioms taken from already developed assumptions.

3.3 Research paradigm:

The research paradigm majorly consists of research philosophy, research approach, and research design that helps the researcher to accomplish the tasks in an appropriate manner as described in the research outline. The researcher generally adopts several assumptions during the proceedings of the research work. The research paradigm also deals with these assumptions and the participants of the research adopt that. As mentioned by Flick (2014), a research paradigm could be defined as a set of beliefs or assumptions of the participants of the research. Research Paradigm is an approach of the model that could be used by the researcher in order to make the research successful.

Interpretivism and positivist approaches are most important, which generally diverge to other approaches. As opined by Booth, Sutton & Papaioannou (2016), mixed-method research paradigm is another approach that has emerged from the other two approaches and this approach is widely accepted. The meaning of the word paradigm is a pattern and it is a Greek word.

3.3.1 Research philosophy:

It is vital to grasp the paradigm of the research for knowing the guidance of research philosophy. Research philosophy describes the hypotheses that underline any particular research approach; it actually explains the theory of research. These underlying hypotheses can be summarized as the two components of research philosophy; ontology and epistemology. Ontology means ‘what is out there to know?’ and epistemology means ‘what and how can we know about it?’ (Maylor, Blackmon and Huemann, 2017)

Research philosophy guides the participants in doing the research in a proper way, which helps them to complete the research by availing of each possible option. Research philosophy helps the researcher to identify and analyze the limitations of the research that could create a barrier. The researcher gets a proper idea about the limitations with the help of research philosophy. Generally, research is conducted in order to achieve the targeted/desired research outcomes about the subject matter. Selecting appropriate research philosophy helps a researcher to achieve those research outcomes. As stated by Tuck & McKenzie (2014), research philosophy is an important part of research in order to get a clear idea about the barriers in the research process. There are four types of philosophies. In this study positivism, philosophy has been chosen. All four types of philosophies differ on the basis of values that guide the participants of research in different ways. Choosing an appropriate philosophy is essential for a researcher in order to make the research

successful. With the help of research philosophy, the researcher gets a clear idea about the methods that will be used in order to conduct the research. In addition, the researcher also achieves specific knowledge about the subject matter.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Tuck & McKenzie, 2014. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 3.2: Research philosophy.

(Source: Tuck & McKenzie, 2014)

Justification for choosing pragmatism research philosophy:

In order to organize the research work, the participants need to obtain specific knowledge about the topic, which could be done by close observation. This requires the researcher to be able to

incorporate research conducting decisions based on what is more important and what would work best to find an answer to the research questions. Hence, the researcher has chosen pragmatism philosophy as this philosophy offers flexibility to the researcher to conduct the research in an innovative and dynamic way to solve research problems. Specific knowledge could be acquired by collecting data about the barriers in the export of garments of Bangladesh and closely observing them. This will help the participants to get a clear picture of the subject matter. The researcher has chosen pragmatism philosophy because it helps the researcher to conduct the study freely without any restrictions imposed by the other commonly used research philosophies such as positivism and interpretivism.

The researcher did not find other research philosophies to be relevant for this work. As the researcher aimed that research should be designed to help practitioner to get a comprehensive view of the overall barriers for the garment industry based on real life data and observations, pragmatism will not bear any fruit. Realism actually looks over existing reality that is independent of our experience. But this maybe the way to develop a highly philosophical view about probable cause for barriers for garment industry for a person who had tremendous experience about the industry. But this research aims to know what is happening and how they are influencing the current industry. Interpretivism research would also focus mostly on qualitative aspect. But this research though conducted detail qualitative secondary survey was at the end would try to understand what problems are the most influential in the eyes of practitioner. Therefore, pragmatic research philosophy would be the appropriate research philosophy for to conduct this research.

3.3.2 Research approach

The research approach is important for the completion of the research on the selected topic successfully. Proper use of the research approach helps the researchers to take theories and concepts in order to strengthen the research in the future. There are two types of research approaches; such as deductive and inductive, that can be used to convey the research in an optimized manner (Barnham, 2015). Research approaches are helpful to understand the research topic in a detailed manner. The inductive approach starts from a definite point and then provides a generalized conclusion on the topic, whereas the deductive research approach begins from the generalized description of the topic and then concludes at a specific point. The inductive approach is the opposite of the deductive approach. The inductive approach makes broad generalization from specific observations. Basically, there is data, and conclusions are drawn from that data. Deductive reasoning starts with a general theory, statement, or hypothesis and then works its way down to a conclusion based on the evidence. The inductive approach starts with a small observation or question and works its way to a theory by examining the related issues.

So, the research approach is a plan or procedure that consists of the steps of broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection, analysis, and interpretations. It is, therefore, based on the nature of the research problem being addressed.

Figure 3.3: Research approach

(Source: influenced by Youssef & Youssef, 2016)

Justification for using mixed-method research approach:

Here the researcher has chosen the mixed-method research approach for the completion of the research. The mixed-method research approach has enabled the researcher to use the most appropriate method to each individual concept to generate new theories and ideas, ensuring that on the most effective approach has been used for different aspect of the research. This is more flexible than fixing on either inductive or deductive research approach because researchers did not need to follow any specific predetermined research path. This research approach is mainly based on the theories and it complete with the analysis of the collected data analysis. The researchers had followed the study of other researchers on the same topic on the RMG garment industry of Bangladesh. The researcher has chosen this approach because here the researcher wants to create

certain new theories on the barriers of the garment industry that can be identified while conducting the research properly. The researcher wants to develop a theoretical framework to address the existing knowledge gap about export barriers. Based on this theory, the researcher hopes that in future other researchers will conduct further research to test different assumptions based on this research. As researcher did not find any comprehensive previous work on the barriers of garments industry, the researcher found that there is a need for an overall view of the industry barriers based on mixed-method approach (Saunders et al., 2009).

3.3.3 Research Design

Research design is an important part of the methodology of research to reduce inaccuracy. In order to present an outline of the study on the research topic, the Research design is three types such as descriptive, experimental, and exploratory. As commented by Youssef & Youssef, (2016) by the research design the researchers can integrate various components of the research in a logical way. In experimental research design, some random experiments are done on the existing assignment of the related topic. Descriptive research design includes research based on surveys and observation. Lastly in the exploratory research method, the research variables are taken in account in order to found the potential relation. In this research on the garment industry, the descriptive research design has been chosen because there are huge amounts of data, which need to be analyzed.

Figure 3.4: Research Design

(Source: influenced by Taylor et al., 2015)

Justification for taking descriptive research design:

The existing data on this topic of RMG garment industry in Bangladesh can be properly analyzed by the descriptive design method. The researchers had used the descriptive design method in order to gather information from depth by the proper data collection method. This design method actually assisted the researchers to find detailed information on the research topic. The descriptive research design will help the researcher to meet the research aim and objective. As the research was related to the survey method so researchers had chosen this design method. Normally the data collected by survey methods are descriptive type. This research design method helped the researchers to collect the data from the unbiased condition. Moreover, researcher find that there is good amount of information, ideas and observation about the topic, but they are not analyzed and

ordered in a systematic way. Descriptive design will help us to build up a proper perception and knowledge-based framework toward understanding the knowledge-based framework that the research wants to develop. An explanatory research cannot be conducted unless there is a broad overview of the barrier and then a more focused study could have been done to explain some particular phenomena. Researcher found that there have been quite exploratory findings about garments industry barrier but these issues and findings needed to be compiled and described in a comprehensive way. For that reason, descriptive research has been chosen.

3.4 Sampling method

In any experiential study, one of the key features of the data collection process is a sampling. A sample is a sub-group of the population from which a researcher draws a conclusion on- what is known as the target population. The selected sample will be the representation of the targeted population which will allow the researcher's findings to be generalized to the wider group. The sampling method is very important and the process of sampling is critical to the validity of the findings. (Ang, 2014)

The sampling method can influence the research outcomes. In order to generate a trustworthy research outcome, the researcher needs to choose an appropriate sampling method. As opined by Etikan et al., (2016), an accurate sampling method can help researchers to collect reliable data for research. The sampling method can be categorized into two different types, such as probability sampling and non-probability sampling. These two kinds of sampling methods have different kinds of features and they can be analyzed on the basis of these features. Probability sampling has different advantages and these advantages help researchers to generate accurate research outcomes. As mentioned by Roberge et al., (2017), this sampling technique can be considered a

convenient one for this research. In some cases, random sampling cannot be done due to certain constraints regarding time and cost. In those cases, non-probability sampling can be considered. The researcher has used both probability and non-probability sampling in order to collect authentic data for this research.

Figure 3.5: Sampling method

(Influenced by Etikan et al., 2016)

Justification: Non Probability sampling has been selected due to its advantageous features. This sampling technique is closely associated with random sampling, bias decision can be avoided by this technique and this technique will help to gain error-free results. In this technique opportunities for choosing respondents are known as well as fixed. For this reason, this objective type of sampling technique has been chosen. As stated by Etikan et al., (2016) non-probability sampling has been used by researchers in order to choose respondents for interviews. Because of its subjective nature, the researcher has used this sampling technique. This technique has helped the researcher to collect authentic data within a short time period. For this research, the researcher has

selected 30 proprietors from the RMG industry and four managers from the same industry in order to conduct survey and interview respectively. As industry experts cannot be reached via random method and need to be selected based on their profile so that we can gain enough insight for them for the purpose of research, this method was appropriate here.

3.5 Research Strategy

In order to generate a reliable research outcome application of the right research, the strategy is very essential. As mentioned by Bohl et al. (2014), the researcher has evaluated the purpose of this research and after getting proper knowledge about the research purpose, the researcher has selected an appropriate research strategy for this research. The researcher has conducted a survey as primary quantitative research and has taken interviews as primary qualitative research. This research strategy will help the researcher to collect in-depth information about the research topic. Secondary data will be gathered as well in order to acquire clear insight about previous researches and discussion on this same topic. Secondary research will help the researcher to gain detailed information about the research topic and the researcher will be able to generate accurate research outcomes. Traditionally, quantitative and qualitative research strategies have been viewed as separate and competing. Nonetheless, in recent years, there have been many calls for researchers to be open-minded to the exercise of both methods, as the potency of one is often the weaknesses of the other. Therefore, quantitative and qualitative research strategies should be observed as harmonizing rather than competing strategies. Researchers as a result offer the use of both methods within a single research project, known as mixed methods. Qualitative research helps researcher to find out the relevant variable applicable to particular research topic. Without knowing what to

quantify by an appropriate qualitative study first, the researcher will move further from research objective through doing wrong quantitative analysis based on wrong factors. (Ang, 2014)

Justification for choosing research strategy: Interview has been selected in order to collect in-depth information based on real life experience. As opined by Lushey & Munro (2015), researcher got opportunity to analyse facial expression and physical posture of respondents during interview process. During this interview, respondents have explained their point of views regarding current research topic. As people have explained their answer, it has helped researcher to evaluate their perceptions and researcher has gathered information based on real life experience about research topic. As survey is time and cost-efficient method, it has been adapted by the researcher. Researcher has collected wide range of data by conducting survey. Questionnaire has been prepared on the basis of basic requirements of this research. Researcher has collected convenient data from this technique. As survey is a scientific process from where highly reliable data can be obtained, thus, researcher has adapted this technique. Researcher has ensured statistical significance of data by conducting survey. As effort as well as expense can be saved by secondary data collection method, researcher has used this method to collect secondary data regarding research topic. As opined by Palinkas et al. (2015), secondary data collection has helped researcher to obtain clear insight about problems related to research topic. Researcher has reviewed previous research papers in order to gather authentic resources regarding research topic. Researcher has eliminated biases from this research in order to generate error free research outcome.

3.6 Data collection methods

Data collection is a process of research where the researchers collect various types of data in different ways. Mainly the data collection method is two types such as primary and secondary. In

the primary data collection method, the researchers collect the data from the surveys and questionnaire. They will collect data for the people randomly on the readymade garment (RMG) industry of Bangladesh. However, in the secondary data collection method, the researchers will collect the data from the previous research articles and journals on the garment industry of Bangladesh, for their comparative study on the research topic (Taylor, 2015). The secondary data collection is necessary in order to get a better comparative results as the researchers can compare their collected data with the previously published data on the RMG garment industry of Bangladesh. By comparison, the researchers can correlate their collected data from interviews and surveys with the secondary data (Kock et al. 2017). This comparison is required for an effective study in order to understand the change of concept on the topic.

Figure 3.6: Data Collection methods

(Influenced by Lewis, 2015)

Primary and secondary both are very useful and necessary data for a fruitful research (Palinkas et al. 2015). There are two types of primary data collection methods such as quantitative and qualitative. For the quantitative data collection method, the surveys of the common people can be done, because they are the primary consumers of the country. The questionnaire can be done on the basis of previous research and literature review on the topic. This questionnaire session will help the researchers to understand the real status of the Bangladesh garment industry. The relevant questionnaire will be based upon variables and factors that are found to be important regarding garment industry of Bangladesh. The qualitative data collection can be done by arranging the interviews of the people who are closely related to the RMG garment industry. The people who know the market better from the common people in Bangladesh can provide more accurate data on the garment industry scenario of Bangladesh. The interviews of the garment company owners and leaders of the Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA) and the policy-making government agencies will be used as the primary qualitative data collection.

3.6.1 Quantitative

Quantitative research is used when researchers need to set up a general relationship between two or more constructs given a large number of observations. Multiple observations allow researchers more certainty and a great degree of accuracy when trying to narrate one construct to another. (Ang, 2014)

Conducting surveys are the methods for the collection of quantitative data for the study. For the survey procedure, 30 owners had been chosen who are closely related to the RMG garment industry in Bangladesh. In order to help the researcher to analyze the topic in a better way, data analysis methods are used. As stated by Cheong et al. (2014) the graphical analysis of the

quantitative data will help the researchers to understand the research topic. By the surveys, the researcher can understand the consumer's choice of the garment in Bangladesh. The researcher will arrange the surveys for 30 proprietors from the garment industry. This would assist in getting an overall view of the garment industry of Bangladesh. The researchers will collect the primary data from the survey.

The evaluation of the primary data will help the researchers to understand the recent scenario of the garment industry in Bangladesh. The researchers will make 40 questions for the survey. This is the researcher's duty to take care of the questions because that is required to be closely related to the topic of the RMG garment industry of Bangladesh. The questionnaire survey would aid the researchers to collect relevant data related to the topic. For the security of the collected data, the survey will be conducted through the electronic procedure. The researchers can use a cloud-based electronic survey process electronic monkey. The researchers will assure the people, who will take part in the survey and provide information, about the confidentiality of the data. The survey process will complete within three weeks from the start date. The questionnaire process is a very efficient process because of its subjective nature. Subjectivity in answering questions would assist researcher to find out broader perspective and underlying factors that mere objective data. This method is essential to identify the variables of the research topic with the existing condition. This will help to find the gap in the study on the topic related to the readymade garment industry of Bangladesh. The questionnaire-based survey will help the researchers to identify the present framework and drawbacks related to the RMG garment industry in Bangladesh.

Therefore, the current research adopts a quantitative method.

3.6.2 Qualitative

The aim of qualitative research is to gain an in-depth understanding of human and organizational behaviors and the motives that compel these behaviors and their differences. In qualitative research, this is often ended through the contextualization of the research setting, where findings are described in light of the research context and environment. (Ang, 2014) Qualitative research is the first approach to develop a research direction and framework based on which quantitative research is undertaken in the later stage. The points and assumptions based on qualitative research is validated through quantitative research and discarded if those assumptions are not supported by quantitative study. Sometimes, these are done in a single research, sometime is a series of research.

Here, qualitative methods will be done by the interviews. Interviews play an important part to understand the reality of the garment industry in Bangladesh. As commented by Kock et al. (2017) study of small numbers of samples in-depth will help the researchers to understand the scenario well. The collection of primary data from the interviews and observations are the main data collection method for the research. The interview is a type of primary qualitative data analysis method by which the researchers can understand the recent change of the situation in the garment industry. The current issues and real market situation can be understood by the researchers. The researchers will arrange the interviews of the owners of the garment industry, leaders of BGMEA, and the government policymakers for the garment industry. For the interview session, the researchers would ask the university for a letter. All the persons, who had been chosen for the interview, need to be corporate personnel's and they should not be influenced by any factors that can modify the given information. In depth interview of these people is consistent with research approach when we talk with corporate personnel during research. (Saunders, 2009) Executives are

not comfortable to talk in focus group. Their interview often requires in-depth questioning which can be done through interview process. For this reason, researcher decided to take interview of them

Qualitative research methods are more beneficial because by using this process researchers can interpret between the theories and the current situation (Lewis, 2015). The interviews will be conducted in a friendly environment. The interviews had conducted in either Bengali or in English in order to make the situation more comfortable. The researchers will assure corporate personnel about the confidentiality of the information provided by them. In order to maintain the ethics, the appropriate approval letter would be taken first and their interviews will be recorded for authenticity electronically. Ethical issues in this research would take into account in order to maintain the professionalism and honesty of the collected data. The collected data from the interviews would not misuse for any other purposes. According to the university guideline, the researchers would assure them about the information.

The main objective of any ideal research is to make it comprehensible to the reader. Hence, to accomplish that objective an efficient methodology plays a significant role. A mixed methods research is such a type of methodology for conducting effective research.

The mixed-method research essentially involves accumulating, evaluating, and incorporating quantitative part in research such as experiments, surveys. Moreover, quantitative data includes complete information such as that found to measure attitudes for rating scales. Furthermore, quantitative research also facilitates determining behaviors, and performance instruments in any specific aspect of particular research. (Saunders, 2009)

Qualitative research on the other hand primarily emphasizes focus groups and interviews. Qualitative data consists of any information which is unlimited in nature and the researcher generally assembles through interviews or conversation, focus groups, and observations. Furthermore, the analysis of the qualitative data such as words, text, and or behaviors usually pursues the direction of combining any part of that research. Additionally, qualitative data also help to segregate any information and to present that information diversely while conducting the research.

3.6.3 Secondary Data Collection

Secondary data can help researchers to obtain clear insight about problems related to the research topic. In this case, the researcher has accessed previous research papers regarding the same topic in order to evaluate areas of further research. The researcher has realized that authentic secondary resources can support the outcome of this research. Authentic journals, books, and other secondary resources have helped researchers to analyze barriers to the Bangladesh garment industry. All legislation and government policies related to the garment industry of Bangladesh have been identified from authentic databases. It has been noticed that there are many barriers in the export of garment industry. These barriers were recognized from previous research papers.

Key words	Description
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<p>Export of garments</p>	<p>Export means selling their own product of a country to different other countries in order to obtain a financial benefit (Alvesson & Sköldberg, 2017). Bangladesh produces garments and exports these goods to other countries.</p>
<p>Barriers of the garments industry</p>	<p>As mentioned by Lewis (2015), barriers refer to challenges and, in this research, the researcher has collected secondary data in order to analyze potential barriers to the Bangladesh garment industry.</p>
<p>Significance of the garments industry</p>	<p>Bangladesh garment industry is a large business area and many people are dependent on this industry in order to earn basic wages.</p>
<p>Business opportunities</p>	<p>It has been noticed that Bangladesh produces quality garments and they have several opportunities to export their garments (Robson & McCartan, 2016). The wide range of market demand for Bangladeshi garments is a good example of a business opportunity for this industry.</p>

<p>Management strategy</p>	<p>Management strategies can be developed by garment industries in order to mitigate barriers (cirt.gcu.edu, 2018). Previous researches have shown that garment industry of Bangladesh has developed several strategies to cope up with existing barriers.</p>
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Table 3.1: Keywords

(Source: Created by Author)

3.7 Accessibility issues

Many accessibility issues are there regarding data collection procedures and during this research, the researcher has faced certain accessibility issues. As opined by Mayer (2015), these issues can create limitations for this research. The researcher has faced issues while collecting primary data. Some of the respondents were reluctant to provide answers to all questions and for this reason, ample information cannot be gathered. This aspect has affected the outcome of this research. If respondents would provide realistic data to the researcher, the research outcome could be more accurate and reliable. Researcher has faced problem to reach all. After lots of processes, the researcher has succeeded to fix appointments with respondents in order to conduct interviews. It has been noticed that some of the respondents have given bias answers and this aspect can be considered as a limitation of the research. Time constraints have been faced by researchers during this research and this can be considered as one of the most difficult accessibility issues. Due to lack of sufficient time, the researcher has missed several opportunities to investigate existing barriers to the export of garments. The limited financial resources have become an issue for researchers. Due to a shortage of time and cost, the researcher was not able to conduct prolonged

research on this topic. Besides primary data collection, the researcher has collected secondary data as well. Lack of authentic secondary resources has prevented researchers to obtain more relevant data. Technological issues have been faced by researchers while accessing secondary resources. If there would be efficient technologies, researchers could generate more accurate as well as trustworthy research outcomes. The researcher has faced several issues during accessing secondary sources. There were several relevant resources that cannot be accessed for free. Authors of those resources wanted to sell their copies. As the researcher had a limited budget for this research, it was not possible to access those resources.

3.8 Ethical Consideration

Every researcher faces several issues related to ethics during the entire research process and they can consider ethical guidelines in order to avoid ethical issues. During the collection of primary data, the researcher has followed all ethical guidelines. As suggested by Antwi & Hamza (2015), maintaining anonymity can be considered as major ethics and the researcher has maintained anonymity in this research. The researcher has not forced any respondents to provide personal data. All respondents were informed about the entire process and purpose of the research. All their queries regarding data collection technique were resolved by the researcher, after getting their consent, the researcher has proceeded to collect data for this research. The researcher has maintained the confidentiality of data and collected data has been used for academic purposes. As stated by Duke (2016), collected data cannot be used in personal life and this is an important ethics of research. The researcher has not used gathered data to gain any personal benefit and the researcher has not used this data for any commercial purpose as well. All guidelines of the Data Protection Act 1998 have been complied with by the researcher. The researcher has provided

liberty to all respondents and has mentioned that they can leave the process of the survey at any time they want. This aspect has helped the researcher to avoid legal issues. The researcher has developed a questionnaire on the basis of the research topic and respondents were not asked to provide any personal information. The researcher has provided respect to emotions of all respondents and has not hurt anyone by the process of data collection. As all ethical guidelines have been maintained by the researcher, there were no legal issues regarding this aspect.

3.9 Data analysis

The selection of the right data analysis techniques plays important role in generating research outcomes. As mentioned by Burton-Jones et al., (2015), appropriate data collection methods can help researchers to provide genuine as well as enriched research outcomes. In this research, data collected from interviews and surveys have been analysed. The response of participants has been explained by numerical calculations and graphical representation in case of data analysis of survey data. After developing a graphical representation, the researcher has analysed the findings. This technique was done in a scientific manner in order to develop reliable outcomes. The perception of each respondent has explained thoroughly by the researcher. In case of analysis of interview data, the researcher has evaluated the words of respondents in order to provide clear insight into their perspectives. Secondary data has been analysed in order to elaborate a clear understanding of existing barriers of the Bangladesh garment industry. Different literature related to the research topic has been reviewed and understood by the researcher. As the researcher has collected an inductive research approach for this research, the researcher has not predicted any outcome regarding this topic. The research outcome is purely based on findings of data analysis and this outcome can be considered as a reliable one.

3.10 Summary

In this chapter, the researcher has discussed different methodologies in order to explain and justify the research methods and approaches implemented appropriately. The researcher has mentioned that positivism research philosophy has been used to conduct this research due to its well-designed structure. In order to explain the reason of choosing positivism, the researcher has mentioned other philosophies along with their different features. In the case of the research approach, the inductive research approach has been applied in order to ensure the reliability of the research outcome. As the inductive approach has been considered, the researcher has not determined outcomes before the completion of this research. This chapter has focused on appropriate research design as well. The researcher has explained the causes behind the selection of descriptive research design. The researcher has mentioned that both probability and non-probability sampling has been used in this research and this aspect has helped the researcher to avoid bias decisions regarding the selection of sampling population. The researcher has selected respondents from the Bangladesh Garment industry in order to gather information based on real life experiences. In case of the data collection method, the researcher has faced several limitations. However, all ethical guidelines have been maintained by the researcher. The researcher has availed all authentic secondary researches in order to acknowledge in-depth information about the research topic. In the entire chapter, the research methodologies have been discussed through which the analysis can be conducted on a further basis. This can help the researcher to improve his skills because before conducting the research, a proper outline has been made. Based on this methodology, data analysis has been done in the next chapter.

3.11 Conclusion

The methodology chapter has addressed the underlying research paradigms. The research supports itself with, research philosophies, research approaches, research strategies, techniques, and procedures. Although this research was carefully prepared, there are still some limitations. Overall, this section provides the right kind of data, facts, and examples such that there are enough proof of convincing and trustworthy findings. (Ang, 2014).

Chapter 4: Data analysis

4.0. Introduction

In this data analysis chapter, researcher represents, analyses all observations of data along with its results and outcomes. These outcomes and results are obtained from gathering primary data of this research investigation. Based on the literature review chapter, the analysis has been made. However, majorly, research has been conducted based on the research outline, entire data analysis has been conducted. In addition to this, for gathering data for conduction of this research investigations, research need to apply and implement certain blend of the various techniques of the collection of the data. Henceforth, following observations seems to be proper combination for both quantitative data and qualitative data in this research study. In addition to this, for secondary data analysis, data has been collected from the authentic websites and journals. However, data has been analysed as per the data collected from several sources.

4.1. Part A: Quantitative Data Representation and Interpretations

The reasoning behind the question choice.

While preparing the questionnaire, the researcher remember that the aim was to get an overall descriptive picture of the garment industry. What is the demography of the industry personnel, the range of their experience? The researcher wants to know whether they face barriers and degree of the barrier. How they tackle these barriers and what kind of legal issues they face. What is their opinion about government policies? Whether they agree with the general overview that low price of garment production is the major driver of this export industry. Whether they are satisfied with the product quality and whether they are competitive enough. What is their opinion about the energy source cost, impact of substandard labour practice and infrastructure? What is the major financial barrier and whether they are happy with the interest rate? Are they thinking that our

country is exporting at an effective label and how political turmoil effect distinct industry? What kind of customs issue creates barrier for their business? Their view about major threats, constrains, documentation system. The researcher wanted to know about their opinion about the current export condition and what their view is about the drivers of diversification. What kind of opportunity they will be able to exploit through focusing on certain factors? Their experience about after Brexit, labour condition, workforce skill development, view about competitors, and whether they are taking steps to improve product quality. Their opinion about particular foreign policy and how their opinion about risk for the industry due to lack of resources. The researcher wished to know about their view of the quota system, cultural barrier, macroeconomic volatility and impact of inflation, exchange rate. The researcher wished to know about economic policy impact of double taxation, GDP. And finally, whether they want to increase export from the current level. The questionnaire tries to collect these data by preparing relevant question and the data is intended to develop a descriptive research.

We have interviewed 30 garments factory owners and the information from the questions asked provided relative results of frequency and analysis. We have obtained a lot of information for our research, such as, the question of their age provides information that middle aged people make up most of the interviewees and are the ones who are the owners with appropriate experience with less creativity options and that owning the business itself is a grueling task. This also shows that it is not a place for young people to be owners as it takes a lot of time to be successful and people who are a lot older usually retire. Another example can be regarding the barriers of export for local garments factories. From this question we have received information that most of the owners do see a lot of barriers while exporting to other countries and they need to be careful on their business procedures as these may affect it negatively in the long run. The following question regarding how

owners tackle the barriers provides information that they prefer collective security with allies within The North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO). This indicates that maintaining positive overseas relations can prove to be beneficial for their business. The question with legal barriers and commitments faced by the owners shows us that legal issues with foreign companies as well as humanitarian laws are equally important. Questions regarding government policies shows us that most owners have to be agreeable to the foreign terms for better business prospects in the future. A question related to price shows us that even though Bangladeshi garments products are competitively low in the global market but are still high compared to some countries which may give us problems in the long run. A majority of the owners agree that the quality of the garments is great but this question can be even more engaging in the questionnaire if it included their perspective on the foreign buyers in order to remove bias. The question related to local competition shows that owners agree of high competitiveness in the industry. Energy is crucial for any business and the owners agree that garments factories consume a lot and the country itself is running out of natural resources when asked about the question related to it. The price of electricity may also rise in the long run as supply of natural gas and available reserves are falling. The question regarding labor safety shows the concern of owners as the framework is still very weak in the country. The development of the framework for infrastructure, safety standards and green factories are important especially due to past disasters such as the Rana Plaza incident. Most owners also believe that high bank interests effect their business but this information from the question may be distorted due to the actual time of when they took out a loan. The country has a new fixed 9 percent interest on loans and 6 percent interest on deposits in place by the request of these owners to the government from 2019. This has a positive aspect on new owners taking out loans feel more comfortable with the fixed rate but this may create some instability for owners with loans on

previous interests. The interest rate is very important for the garments industry and the government must oversee the banking sector to avoid destabilization and extreme fluctuations. Related to information on finance for the garments industry, some owners do not worry about the rising cost which may create problems for them that shows financial literacy is important for them. It is evident from a question regarding supply chain that owners must increase their supply to meet the increasing demand locally and overseas. Political turmoil can also affect the production levels, especially for export. Issues related to customs include, value added tax, excise duty, customs duty, supplementary duty and each requires to be given equal importance as different garments factories face these individual problems while exporting to various foreign countries. Exporting also requires additional documentation such as valid membership from registered trade association, proof regarding renewal fees, export policy documents and clearance permission which most cannot be avoided. The owners also face local constraints such as lack of access to skilled manpower, price competitiveness, quality aspect and lack of research and development in the industry. The industry faces problems with diversification of export due to establishment of supremacy, exploitation of incentives and acquisition of transport facilities.

There are instances where some owners have taken part in exploitation in development but this amount is very low. Most owners do not expect the benefits of a quota in foreign markets for garments and extreme competition may reduce the chances of cooperation with other countries but internal power is present and needs to be developed such as training of labor and providing them education to avoid barriers. For instance, the changes of international policies following Brexit in Europe and may cause problems with separately supplying to UK and the EU. Therefore, this may increase competition and development has to be done to be still viable in the foreign market. Most owners agree that quality needs to be raised for Bangladesh' garments but there is still some doubt

on this issue. There is also the issue of humanitarian violation against child labor which is still apparent in Bangladesh and in the garments industry. However, this exclusion of child labor is a slow process and needs to be taken in steps. Moreover, there is a risk in wastage of resources and needs development. The owners must also have negotiations with foreign buyers for a quota system so that supply does not get wasted. A standard repository needs to be made for Bangladeshi garments owners to have the knowledge of this industry for business negotiations for future growth. The efficiency of the garments industry depends on the level of skill of labors and if it is developed by the owners, there can be an increase in quality of products, profit and supply. Most owners believe that inflation of different countries increase the price of the product and hampers competition against foreign companies and the lowers selling power in export market. Price volatility decreases the value of money with falling exchange rate which can affect the price of raw materials and the industry itself. Devaluation of a currency is normally done to make the exports cheaper but imports more expensive. This is usually done by policy makers and is seen as unnatural as it may affect other factors in the economy which should be avoided and increase focus on technology. Another economic problem could be taxation as it increases price which could lead to administration problems and needs to be negotiated with governments. Owners also believe that obtaining an export license is difficult due to slow and complex administration problems. For the RMG sector, it is only mostly able to provide massively to the GDP of the country when it receives an equal amount of investment and development. Expert owners and specialists are required to further grow the garments sector and increase the GDP and benefit the country as well. However, they must stay vigil to avoid disasters while focusing on progress so as to set back the sector.

4.1.1. Conduction of the survey questionnaires to get responses of the owners of RMG garment industries (Surveying 30 garment owners of the RMG industries)

Q1. What is your age?

From the survey data in table 4.1 and Figure 4.1, it can be observed that almost all ranges of the age groups are involved in the business of garments in Bangladesh. It can be seen that about 10% of owners of garments are varying in the age group of 25 to 35 years, while, about 17% of owners of garments are varying in the age group of 55 to 65 years. On other hand, maximum quantity of owners of garments is within the age group of middle-aged businessmen. Thus, it can be said that about 30% of owners of garments are varying in the age group of 45 to 55 years, while about 43% of owners of garments are varying in the age group of 35 to 45 years. Henceforth, it can be analysed that maximum number of the owners of garments are varying in the age group of 35 to 45 years.

Age Group	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
25 to 35 years	10%	3	30
35 to 45 years	43%	13	30
45 to 55 years	30%	9	30
55 to 65 years	17%	5	30

Table 4.1: Percentage of the Age Group

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.1: Percentage of the Age Group

(Source: Created by author)

Q2. How long are you working in RMG industry in Dhaka?

An analysis of table 4.2 and Figure 4.2, it can be said that maximum number of businessmen of RMG garments industry are doing business in this field for several years. It is observed that about 17% of owners of RMG industries are working in this field for about less than 5 years, while, about 23% of owners of RMG industries are working in this field for about 10 years. On other hand, maximum number of owner of garments is working within the time period of more than 30 years. Thus, it is observed that about 27% of owners of RMG industries are working in this field for about 20 years, while, about 33% of owners of RMG industries are working in this field for about more than 30 years. Henceforth, it can be analysed that maximum number of the owners of RMG industries are working more than 30 years in this field.

Working Time Period	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Less than 5 years	17%	5	30

10 years	23%	7	30
20 years	27%	8	30
More than 30 years	33%	10	30

Table 4.2: Percentage of the Working Time Period

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.2: Percentage of the Working Time Period

(Source: Created by author)

Q3. As owners of RMG industries in Bangladesh, do you face any barrier in export?

From the analysis, it can be said that maximum number of garments businessmen are agreeing with this fact that there exist many barriers in exports of garments from Bangladesh. It can be seen

that about 20% of owners of RMG industries denied with this fact that there prevails any kind of barriers in the process of exporting garments from Bangladesh to other nations. On other hand, about 80% of owners of RMG industries agree with this fact that there are various kinds of constraints and barriers that affect price of exports of garments from Dhaka to other countries. Henceforth, from this above analysis, it is analysed that there exist different types of obstacles while exporting garments of RMG industries from Bangladesh.

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Yes	80%	24	30
No	20%	6	30

Table 4.3: Percentage of the Owners of RMG Industries facing any Barrier

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.3: Percentage of the Owners of RMG Industries facing any Barrier

(Source: Created by author)

Q4. Does export business carries out with many barriers while exporting garments from Bangladesh?

Many opinions exist in the RMG industries regarding facing barriers. About 3% of owners of RMG garment industries strongly disagree with this fact that export business carries out with many barriers while exporting garments from Bangladesh. About 10% of owners of RMG garment industries disagree with this fact that export business carries out with many barriers while exporting garments from Bangladesh. It is also observed that about 20% of owners of RMG garment industries are neutral with this fact that export business carries out with many barriers while exporting garments from Bangladesh. On other hand, about 23% of owners of RMG garment industries agree with this fact that export business carries out with many barriers while exporting garments from Bangladesh. About 43% of owners of RMG garment industries strongly agree with this fact that export business carries out with many barriers while exporting garments from Bangladesh. Henceforth, it can be said that there are many barriers in export business of garments from Bangladesh as the maximum number of owners of RMG industries strongly agrees with it.

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Strongly agree	43%	13	30
Agree	23%	7	30
Neutral	20%	6	30

Disagree	10%	3	30
Strongly disagree	3%	1	30

Table 4.4: Percentage of the Opinions of RMG Industries regarding facing Barriers

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.4: Percentage of the Opinions of RMG Industries regarding facing Barriers

(Source: Created by author)

Q5. What are the ways to tackle the barriers in the export of the garments from Bangladesh?

There prevail several ways to tackle export barriers for the owners of garment industries in Bangladesh. About 40% of owners of garment industries prefer in adopting the way of collective security with its allies within NATO, while about 37% of owners of garment industries prefer in the adaptation of the way of foreign policy and national security requirements. On other hand, about 17% of owners of garment industries prefer in adoption the way dealing with terrorism concerns, while, about 7% of owners of garment industries prefer in the adoption of the way dealing with internal repression. Henceforth, many ways can be used to manage all barriers in process of exporting RMG garments from Dhaka to other countries.

Ways to tackle export barriers	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Collective security with its allies within NATO	40%	12	30
Foreign policy and national security requirements	37%	11	30
Terrorism concerns	17%	5	30
Internal repression	7%	2	30

Table 4.5: Percentage of Ways to tackle export barriers

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.5: Percentage of Ways to tackle export barriers

(Source: Created by author)

Q6. What are the legal barriers that are to be faced by owners of RMG garment industries in Dhaka?

From the analysis of the data that are collected from the conduction of the survey, as provided in Table 4.6 and Fibure 4.6, it is observed that there exist several legal barriers that are faced by owners of RMG garment industries in Bangladesh. It can be seen that about 40% of owners of RMG garments prefer to adopt the international legal commitments with obligations, while, about 33% of owners of RMG garments prefer to adopt the non-proliferation policy. On other hand, about 27% of owners of RMG garments prefer to adopt the laws against violation of human rights.

Henceforth, it can be said that owners and businessmen of RMG garment industries in Bangladesh do adopt various and different ways to tackle the legal constraints in process of export of garments from Bangladesh to other nations. Government of Bangladesh does maintain controls for the process of exports to control the export of garment products carrying out with a variety of the reasons, while, in case, if items are been subjected to export controls of Bangladesh, then, there needs a licence that is needed before export of these garment products, as per licensing authority.

Legal Barriers faced by Owners of RMG Garment Industries	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
International legal commitments with obligations	40%	12	30
Non-proliferation policy	33%	10	30
Violations of human rights	27%	8	30

Table 4.6: Percentage of the Legal Barriers faced by Owners of RMG Garment Industries

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.6: Percentage of the Legal Barriers faced by Owners of RMG Garment Industries

(Source: Created by author)

Q7. Are government policies are suitable for exporting garments?

Government policies are necessary to boost the exports of the RMG industry. International trade policies, monetary policies and taxations need to be regulated to increase the percentage of the exports of garments every year. In this survey, it was found that 30% of the individuals strongly agree that the Bangladesh government has taken enough initiatives to increase the exports of the country. Approximately 26.5% of the people agree that the government of the country has framed good policies to boost the exports of readymade garments. On the other hand, 20% of the selected people disagree with the point and 13.5% of the respondents strongly disagree as they believe, the

government needs to give more attention to frame proper rules and policies to facilitate the export of garments.

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Strongly agree	9	30	30
Agree	8	26.5	30
Neither agree nor disagree	3	10	30
disagree	6	20	30
Strongly disagree	4	13.5	30

Table 4.7: Government policies are suitable for exporting garments or not.

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.7: Graphical representations of government policies are suitable for exporting garments or not

Q8: Do you think that price of the garment products acts as a driver in export?

The price of the products acts as a driving force in exporting the garments. The price of the products generally increases due to high labour costs and high cost of raw materials. The competitiveness of the exporting country decreases if the labour cost is high and the price of the raw materials fluctuates periodically. In this survey, it could be seen that 43.33% of the respondents believe that the price of the products is high due to the high price of raw materials and huge labour cost. The government needs to take appropriate action and frame proper policy in order to control the prices

of the products. This will help them increase their competitiveness while exporting the products. Although, 56.6% of the respondents believe that the price of the garments products is competitive enough to increase the exports.

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
The price is high	13	43.33%	30
The price is low and competitive enough	17	56.66%	30

Table 4.8: Opinions about the price of the garments

Figure 4.8: Graphical representations of opinions about the price of the garments.

Q9: Do you agree that the qualities of the products are satisfactory enough for exporting?

In this survey, it could be seen that near about 26.6% of the respondents strongly believe that the quality of readymade garments is satisfactory enough to export them to other countries. 33.33% of the respondents also agree with the point. The importers demand a high quality of garments and the exporters need to give attention to maintain the quality of their products. 10% of respondents did not agree with the point and they think that more improvements are needed in the quality of the garment products. 13.3% of the people strongly disagree with the point and they also believe that improvements are required in the quality of the garment products.

Figure 4.9: Graphical representations of opinions about the quality of the products

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Strongly agree	8	26.6%	30
Agree	10	33.33%	30
Neither agree nor disagree	5	16.66%	30
disagree	3	10%	30
Strongly disagree	4	13.33%	30

Table 4.9: Opinions about the quality of the products

(Source: Created by author)

Q10. In your opinion, how is the competitiveness level in the garment industry of Bangladesh?

From the table 4.10 and graphical representation in Figure 4.10, it can be implied that 33.33% of the respondents have mentioned that the competitiveness level of the garment industry in Bangladesh is high. This happens majorly because of the globalisation. It has been seen that in several countries such as Germany, United States, France and many other countries, the export

level is high. Due to this reason, the competitiveness level is increasing to a greater extent. To maintain the competitiveness, the global marketplace needs to be considered and therefore that needs to be created. However, 50% of the respondents have mentioned that in Bangladesh, competitiveness level is medium because the garment industry of Bangladesh is flourishing rapidly and therefore demand and supply is good because of this reason. 17% of the respondents have said that the competitiveness level is low because, in their opinion, there are many countries which do not want any garment exported from Bangladesh.

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
High	33.33%	10	30
Medium	50%	15	30
Low	16.67%	5	30

Table 4.10: Competitiveness level in the garment industry

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.10: Competitiveness level in the garment industry

(Source: Created by author)

Q11. What are the low-cost energy factors that help in mitigating the barriers of RMG industry?

From the above table, it has been noticed that 57% of the respondents have said that low-cost energy factors are required so that barriers in the garment industry can be mitigated. These respondents have said that Natural gas is one of the major energy factors that help in mitigating the barriers in the RMG sector of Bangladesh. However, they have mentioned that natural gas is majorly required for any heating process and even if it is required for the heating, then also the demand for this factor is increasing rapidly. In their opinion, the main reason for the usage of this gas is the low price. Costing of the natural gas is approximately 166 taka and that is equal to 1.56 euro. Therefore, it can be said that costing is low and due to this reason, this factor is used. On the

other hand, only 43% of the respondents have said about electricity as low-cost energy factors. In their opinion, Bangladesh is having lowest electricity costs. In comparison to other countries, the costing of electricity is quite low and hence, it helps in mitigating barriers of the garment industry.

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
Natural Gas	56.67%	17	30
Electricity	43.33%	13	30

Table 4.11: Low-cost energy factors

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.11: Low-cost energy factors

(Source: Created by author)

Q12. Do you think labour safety and industrial labour infrastructure can create barriers in the garment industry of Bangladesh?

Labour safety and industrial infrastructure help in creating a good garment sector as well as it creates barriers in the RMG sector of Bangladesh. From the above table, it can be said that 50% of the respondents have strongly agreed that labour safety and industrial infrastructure create barriers. In their opinion, the industrial incident of Rana Plaza had destroyed the garment factory and due to this reason, the export got hampered. Several labourers have died in this incident and due to this, labour safety needs to be considered strongly. On the other hand, 6.67% of the labourers have strongly disagreed with this matter because, in their opinion, these two factors are not at all linked with the garment sector of Bangladesh. In their opinion, the establishment of the garment sector of Bangladesh requires huge investment and if that investment can be done in a better manner, then that helps in successful exporting of products.

Figure 4.12: Labour safety and industrial infrastructure

(Source: Created by author)

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
Strongly agree	50%	15	30
Agree	33.33%	10	30
Neutral	3.33%	1	30
Disagree	6.67%	2	30
Strongly disagree	6.67%	2	30

Table 4.12: Labour safety and industrial infrastructure

(Source: Created by author)

Q13. In your opinion, how much bank interests affect the RMG sector of Bangladesh?

From Figure 4.13 and Table 4.13, it can be said that 33% of the respondents have said that bank interest is minimal and therefore, this does not create any problem in exporting the goods to other countries. In their opinion, in the year 2014, all banks in Bangladesh have increased their interest rates, however, that interest rates were medium and due to this reason, it has not created any problems while exporting the goods to other countries. In the perception of other respondents, it has been seen that 27% of the respondents have said that the bank interest is very high and due to this reason, it creates barriers for exporting the goods. However, it has been seen that interest rate

increases by approximately 7% in 5 years and hence, to some of the respondents, it is quite low which is beneficial for exporting of goods.

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
Very High	26.67%	8	30
High	23.33%	7	30
Medium	33.33%	10	30
Low	10%	3	30
Very Low	6.67%	2	30

Table 4.13: Bank Interest affecting RMG sector

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.13: Bank Interest affecting RMG sector

(Source: Created by author)

Q14. In your opinion, what are the main financial barriers that are related to costs of garment industry?

Cost is always considered as the major factor to analyse the barriers of exporting of the garment industry in Bangladesh. 67% of the respondents have said that because of the high rate of interest, the exporting becomes difficult. In their opinion, interest rates range from 9% to 18% and because of this several countries do not feel any interest to take garment products from Bangladesh. The respondents have said that to have an effective business, balance sheets, cash flow and many other things need to be audited. After conducting the audit properly, it has been seen that major costs are required for the remediation and this sometimes hamper the exporting of goods to other

countries. In addition to this, 10% of the respondents have said that owners of garment industry do not have that much will to know about the costing and therefore, there is a knowledge barrier to some extent. Furthermore, 23% of the respondents have said that due to financial literacy, exporting problems are taking place and therefore, it gets hampered.

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
High rate of interest	66.67%	20	30
Financial literacy lacking	23.33%	7	30
Unwillingness to know about costs	10%	3	30

Table 4.14: Financial barriers

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.14: Financial barriers

(Source: Created by author)

Q15. Do you think that the country-wise export level from Bangladesh is effective?

The products are exported to different countries such as the UK, France, Germany, Spain and Italy. From the above table, it has been known that 83% of the respondents have said yes in regards to the export level is effective when it is done country-wise from Bangladesh. In their opinion, market accessibility is the major consideration upon which export level is depending. 17% of the respondents have said that the export level is not effective because of several tariffs that hamper market accessibility. Non-tariffs and tariffs regulations are considered to be the most important barriers in regards to market accessibility. Therefore, it can be said that majority of the respondents have said that export level is effective from Bangladesh and country-wise level is only effective.

Therefore, it can be said that country-wise level of export can help in mitigating the barriers of exporting garments in other countries.

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
Yes	83.33%	25	30
No	16.67%	5	30

Table 4.15: Country-wise export level from Bangladesh

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.15: Country-wise export level from Bangladesh

(Source: Created by author)

Q16. Due to the political turmoil, which part of the garment sector gets affected?

It has been seen that labour issues and political turmoil affect the garment industry of Bangladesh to a huge level. From the above table, 67% of the respondents have mentioned that due to this political turmoil, exporting of goods from Bangladesh to other countries get hampered. In their opinion, because of the political disturbances, it has been seen that production, distribution and export, all these 3 functions get hampered and these three functions are interlinked with each other. Due to these political issues, the growth of the RMG sector gets hampered and therefore, due to this reason, entire functions for exporting of the products have to face certain obstacles. This has an impact on the development of the economy of Bangladesh. In addition to this, 13% of the respondents have said that political instability hampers the production and therefore, it creates barriers in exporting.

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
Production	13.33%	4	30
Distribution	20%	6	30
Export	66.67%	20	30

Table 4.16: Political turmoil affecting Bangladesh

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.16: Political turmoil affecting Bangladesh

(Source: Created by author)

Q17. What are the customs related issues faced by exporters for exporting garments of RMG industry from Bangladesh?

From Table 4.17 and Figure 4.17 above analysis, it can be assessed that there are various issues that are related with customs, duties and taxes while exporting garment products from Bangladesh to other nations. About 23% of owners of RMG garment industries select rates of customs duty as a custom related issue during process of exporting garment products especially from Dhaka. On other hand, about 20% of owners of RMG garment industries select export permit fee as a custom related issue during process of exporting garment products from Bangladesh. In addition, about 17% of owners of RMG garment industries select value added tax as a custom related issue during process of exporting garment products from Dhaka. On other hand, about 7% of owners of RMG

garment industries select export permit system as a custom related issue during process of exporting garment products from Bangladesh. It can also be analysed that about 13% of owners of RMG garment industries select supplementary duty as a custom related issue during process of exporting garment products from Dhaka. In addition, about 20% of owners of RMG garment industries select excise duty as a custom related issue during process of exporting garment products from Bangladesh. Henceforth, it can be said that there prevail various exporting barriers related to customs in process of export of garment products of RMG garment industries.

Customs Related Issues	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Rates of customs duty	23%	7	30
Export permit fee	20%	6	30
Value added tax	17%	5	30
Export permits system	7%	2	30
Supplementary duty	13%	4	30
Excise duty	20%	6	30

Table 4.17: Percentage of Customs Related Issues

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.17: Percentage of Customs Related Issues

(Source: Created by author)

Q18. What are the additional documentation processes that are hurdling the exporters of Bangladesh?

From the conducted analysis, this is concluded that process of exporting products from Bangladesh needs to go through various processes of documentations and they are hurdle for export in owner's mind. About 7% of garment owners think providing certificate for valid membership from registered trade association is an issue, while, about 13% of garment owners regarded the process of providing proof regarding payment of the renewal fees as a barrier. On other hand, about 10% of garment owners selected providing copy of TIN certificate by tax authority, while, about 17% of garment owners pointed out showing a declaration within triplet. In addition, about 10% of owners of RMG garment industries are finding the requirement to show documents for export

policy during export process cumbersome. On other hand, about 27% of RMG owners had complained about clearance permits in export process, while, about 27% of businessmen of garment industries in Bangladesh complained about getting export permit for exporting their products to other nations. Now, in lot of cases, exporters find this system as essential or inevitable, but they think that the process is overly bureaucratic.

Figure 4.18: Percentage of Additional Documentation Process

(Source: Created by author)

Additional Documentation Process	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Certificate for valid membership from registered trade association	7%	2	30
Proof regarding payment of the renewal fees	13%	4	30
Copy of TIN Certificate by tax authority	10%	3	30
A declaration within triplicate	17%	5	30
Documents for export policy	10%	3	30
Clearance permits	20%	5	30
Export permit	27%	8	30

Table 4.18: Percentage of Additional Documentation Process

(Source: Created by author)

Q19. What are the major threats in overseas that are faced by exporters of Bangladesh?

It is concluded from above data analysis is that about 30% of businessmen of RMG industries concerned with threat of emerging market in other nations, while about 23% concerned with threat of raised competition with the local garment industries. On other hand, it is also analysed that about 33% of businessmen of RMG industries concerned with threat of political unrest that affects smooth functioning in RMG garment industries. In addition, about 13% of businessmen of RMG industries are concerned about threat of lack of the electricity.

Major Threats	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Emerging market in other nations	30%	9	30
Raised competition with the local garment industries	23%	7	30
Political unrest for smooth functioning in RMG garment industries	33%	10	30
Lack of the electricity	13%	4	30

Table 4.19: Percentage of Major Threats

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.19: Percentage of Major Threats

(Source: Created by author)

Q20. What are the constraints that are suffered by owners of garment industries in Bangladesh?

About 33% of owners of garment industries face constraints of skilled manpower absence, while, about 23% of owners of garment industries face constraints of price competitiveness. On other hand, about 27% of owners of RMG garment industries face obstacles related to the aspects of quality, while, about 17% of businessmen of RMG garments industries face barriers that deals with linkage of backward activities. Henceforth, it can be said that there exist various types of constraints that are faced by RMG garment industry owners in Bangladesh.

Constraints	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Absence regarding skilled manpower	33%	10	30
Price competitiveness	23%	7	30
Quality aspects	27%	8	30
Linkage backward activities	17%	5	30

Table 4.20: Percentage of Constraints

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.20: Percentage of Constraints

(Source: Created by author)

Q21. What are the factors that affect the diversification of the exports from Bangladesh?

About 23% of factor of establishment of supremacy effects diversification of the exports, while, about 20% of factor of exploitation of incentive of subsidy effects diversification of the exports. On other hand, about 23% of factor of acquisition of transportation facilities effects diversification of the exports, while, about 20% of factor of sharing steadily and growing demands within international market effects diversification of the exports. On other hand, about 13% of factor of Strong outlook for the shrimp export effects diversification of the exports. Henceforth, it can be concluded that there exist various factors that exploits incentives of subsidy affecting diversification of the exports.

Figure 4.21: Percentage of Factors affecting Diversification of the Exports

(Source: Created by author)

Factors affecting Diversification of the Exports	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Establishment of supremacy	23%	7	30
Exploitation of incentive of subsidy	20%	6	30
Acquisition of transportation facilities	23%	7	30
Sharing steadily and growing demands within international market	20%	6	30
Strong outlook for the shrimp export	13%	4	30

Table 4.21: Percentage of Factors affecting Diversification of the Exports

(Source: Created by author)

Q22. What are the current export conditions of RMG industry owners in Dhaka?

It can be observed from above conducted analysis is that there are various current export conditions of RMG industry owners in Dhaka. About 13% of industry owners get involved within conditions of sensational development, while, about 20% of RMG industry owners get involved within conditions regarding protected market as per MFA. On other hand, about 23% of industry owners get within conditions of financial improvement, while about 213% of RMG industry owners in Bangladesh get within conditions of political issue. On other hand, about 20% of industry owners get involved within conditions of supply of apparel products. Henceforth, there prevail various conditions regarding export process for RMG industry owners in Dhaka.

Figure 4.22: Percentage of Current Export Conditions

(Source: Created by author)

Current Export Conditions	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Sensational development	13%	4	30
Protected market as per MFA	20%	6	30
Financial improvement	23%	7	30
Political issue	23%	7	30
Supply of apparel products	20%	6	30

Table 4.22: Percentage of Current Export Conditions

(Source: Created by author)

Q23. What are opportunities of Bangladesh garments, which can be realised within international market?

It can be analysed from Table 4.23 and Figure 4.23 that there are various opportunities of Bangladesh garments, which can be realised within international market. About 23% of businessmen prefer reliability as their opportunities, while about 27% of businessmen prefer quality assurance as their opportunities. On other hand, about 13% of businessmen prefer garments

quota system as their opportunities, while about 30% of businessmen prefer labour cost as their opportunities. In addition to this, about 7% of businessmen prefer sound cooperation as their opportunities. Henceforth, there are various opportunities that are adopted and preferred by garment industry owners in Dhaka. Quality assurance and reliability carried out with several kinds of interests of various foreign nations about RMG garment industries. In addition, withdrawal of quota system in garment products dies rises demand of the sector of RMG from the early 2016. On other hand, sound cooperation and labour cost always appear to be as an opportunity for the sector of RMG garment industries in Bangladesh.

Opportunities	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Reliability	23%	7	30
Quality assurance	27%	8	30
Garment's quota system	13%	4	30
Labour cost	30%	9	30
Sound cooperation	7%	2	30

Table 4.23: Percentage of Opportunities

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.23: Percentage of Opportunities

(Source: Created by author)

Q24. Are you facing more problems in exporting garments after Brexit?

It has been noticed that Brexit has affected RMG industry of Bangladesh as it has determined market limit for this industry. During survey it has been asked to owners that whether they are facing trouble in export business after Brexit or not. It has been found that about 86% respondents have agreed that, after Brexit they have faced several problems regarding export of garments. Almost 13% RMG owner has stated that they are not facing any problem after Brexit. From the above analysis, it can be said that majority of owners has admitted that they are facing problems in export of garments. It means they are having problems to export garments in countries of UK and Europe after Brexit. This aspect can be considered as an important barrier of this industry.

Options	Percentage of Response	Response frequency	Total Respondents
Yes	86%	26	30
No	13%	4	30

Table 4.24: Percentage of owners of garment industry facing problem after Brexit

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.24: Percentage of owners of garment industry facing problem after Brexit

(Source: Created by author)

Q25. Do you have enough skilled labour in this garment industry?

It has been found that RMG industry of Bangladesh is facing difficulties due to lack of skilled labour. In order to assess impact of this problem on this industry, this question was developed. Only 6 % owners of garment producing organization have told that they have sufficient number of labours at their farm. It means these farms are not facing problem regarding shortage of skilled labour. On the other hand, 93% respondents have admitted that they do not have sufficient number of labours at their farm. It means maximum number of garment organization of Dhaka is facing issues regarding lack of skilled labour. It can affect their business. These organizations will fail to fulfil market demand due to shortage of skilled labour.

Options	Percentage of Response	Response frequency	Total Respondents
Yes	6%	2	30
No	93%	28	30

Table 4.25: Problem regarding lack of skilled labour in RMG industry

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.25: Problem regarding lack of skilled labor in RMG industry

(Source: Created by author)

Q26. Do you agree that educating labour can contribute to garment industry?

This question was prepared in order to evaluate perception of owners from RMG industry regarding education of labours. Educating labours can affect business progress. About 60% of the respondents have strongly agreed that training of labours can contribute to this industry. 20% of respondents have agreed with this aspect. It shows that majority of respondents are aware of problems regarding unavailability of skilled labour and this problem is affecting their business. It means this organization can provide training to labours and this aspect will help them to improve their professional skills. There are several owners of garment producing organizations who said this aspect do not have any effect on this industry. About 6% of the respondents think that lack of

skilled labour is not an issue. 10% respondents stated that training of labours cannot make any difference in this situation. 3% response was about strong disagreement with this fact. It means various kinds of perceptions are there regarding training of labours. However, majority of respondents has realized that training of labours can contribute to this industry.

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Strongly agree	60%	18	30
Agree	20%	6	30
Neutral	6%	2	30
Disagree	10%	3	30
Strongly disagree	3%	1	30

Table 4.26: Impact of skilled labor on garment industry

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.26: Impact of skilled labor on garment industry

(Source: Created by author)

Q27. Can competitors be considered as a threat to export of garments?

Competition has become one of the major threats to RMG industry of Bangladesh. In order to assess impact of competitors on this industry, this question was developed and asked. About 83% of respondents have mentioned that this fact is true. Whereas, only 16% of total respondents think that competition has no effect on exports of garments. From the above analysis, it can be considered that, growing competition has become threats to this industry. Different countries are investing in garment production and for a result market size of RMG industry is reducing day by day. Majority of owners of this industry are aware of this fact and they have taken this fact seriously. Rest of the owners need to pay prior attention to this fact as well.

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Yes	83%	25	30
No	16%	5	30

Table 4.27: Impact of competitor on export of garments

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.27: Impact of competitor on export of garments

(Source: Created by author)

Q28. Are you taking initiatives to improve quality of garments to export?

As this RMG industry is facing several issues they need to work on improvement of their product in order to ensure business profit. In order to acquire perception of owners about this fact, this question was developed and asked. From the above analysis of gathered data, it can be noticed that 80% of total respondents has mentioned that they have undertaken initiatives regarding improvement of their product in order to attract more customers. 16% respondents have said that they are thinking about this fact. It means these owners can take initiatives in future to improve quality of their garments. This data analysis has shown that 3% respondents is not aware about existing issues of this industry and according to them, improvement of goods are not required. However, if we consider majority of respondents, organizations of this industry need to focus on improvement of their products as this will help them to earn more profit from their business.

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
We have taken initiatives	80%	24	30
We are thinking about it	16%	5	30
Improvement not required	3%	1	30

Table 4.28: Initiatives for quality improvement undertaken by owners of garment Industry

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.28: Initiatives for quality improvement undertaken by owners of garment Industry

(Source: Created by author)

Q29. Do you agree that Herkin Bill () has affected garment industry?

In order to reduce production cost, garment industry of Dhaka prefers low-cost child labors. However, they are facing issues after placing of the Herkin Bill in USA. in order to analyze effect of this bill in RMG Industry, this question was prepared and asked to owners from this industry. About 66% of people have mentioned that they are facing problem in exporting garments to countries of USA. 20% of the total respondents have agreed with this fact. Only 6% participants have said that this bill has no impact on this industry. Very few respondents have provided disagreement to this fact. It means, majority of the owners has admitted that child labour is an

important part of Bangladesh garment industry and production will increase if child labour will be banned in Bangladesh. As this bill has mentioned that USA cannot import garments from those who use child labour at their production, it has become difficult to trade with USA. In order to cope up with this condition this industry can explore their business in other areas of the World.

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Strongly agree	66%	20	30
Agree	20%	6	30
Neutral	6%	2	30
Disagree	3%	1	30
Strongly disagree	3%	1	30

Table 4.29: Impact of Herkin Bill on garment industry

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.29: Impact of Herkin Bill on garment industry

(Source: Created by author)

Q30. What is the level of risks regarding lack of resource in Garment industry?

Scarcity of raw material is an important barrier of garment industry of Dhaka and in order to evaluate effect of this fact on this sector, this question was developed and asked to owners. This data analysis has shown that 50% respondents have stated that moderate risks are there regarding scarcity of resources. Whereas, according to 265 respondents, this factor is the cause of high risk in this sector. 23% of participants think that, risk level is low regarding availability of resources for garment industry. From the above-mentioned data analysis, it has been noticed that there are issues regarding lack of labors and this is impacting on this RMG industry of Dhaka. Bangladesh’s garment industry is purely dependent on foreign countries regarding resources and export import

system of this country is very poor. These facts are creating risks for this industry and most of the owners are aware of this fact.

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
High	26%	8	30
Moderate	50%	15	30
Low	23%	7	30

Table 4.30: Level of risk regarding availability of resource in garment industry

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.30: Level of risk regarding availability of resource in garment industry

(Source: Created by author)

Q31. Do you agree that Quota system has affected RMG industry?

Quota system can be considered as a great barrier of this industry and in order to evaluate effect of this system on garment industry, this question was included in this research and was asked to all respondents. They have provided their answer in order to express their perceptions about this fact. About 66% of total respondents have strongly agreed that quota system has great impact on RMG industry. 20% of the total respondents agreed about this fact, it means they have faced problem in exporting garments after imposition of quota system. 6% respondents think that this system has no effect on this industry. In previous days, Bangladesh had opportunities to export garments unlimitedly. However, after imposition of this system, this industry can export limited products as mentioned by this quota system. This has become limitation for this industry and it is affecting economy of this sector. Very few owners provide disagreement to this fact and according to them quota system has no effect on this industry. However, response of majority will be considered and as per that response quota system is affecting RMG industry of Dhaka.

Figure 4.31: Effect of Quota system on RMG industry

(Source: Created by author)

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Strongly agree	66%	20	30
Agree	20%	6	30
Neutral	6%	2	30
Disagree	3%	1	30
Strongly disagree	3%	1	30

Table 4.31: Effect of Quota system on RMG industry

(Source: Created by author)

Q32. Are you facing problems regarding dealing with overseas customers?

Exporters need to deal with overseas customers and RMG industry of Bangladesh is facing difficulties regarding this matter. In order to analyze effect of this problem, this particular question was developed and asked to owners of garment producing organizations of Dhaka. About 83% respondents have stated that they have faced difficulties in dealing with foreign customers. It means, these people have failed to manage foreign customers. Many reasons like cultural difference, language difference, difference in time zone and other aspects are creating difficulties in this regard. Organizations need to provide respect to cultural background of all customers in

order to ensure customer satisfaction. These owners have realized that, customer satisfaction is very important aspect and it can help them to achieve their business goals. However, 16% of respondents have mentioned that they have not faced any difficulties to deal with overseas customers. From this analysis it can be understood that these 16% respondents have developed strategies to deal with foreign customers and rest of the respondents can follow this approach as well.

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Yes	83%	25	30
No	16%	5	30

Table 4.32: Problems regarding dealing with overseas customers

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.32: Problems regarding dealing with overseas customers

(Source: Created by author)

Q 33: Did the productivity of the laborers are sufficient to boost the export of RMG?

Productivity of labor is an important factor in order to increase the export rate of the RMG industry. In order to give quality work and product, the companies need to recruit talented and skilled workers with high productivity. In this survey, it could be seen that majority of the respondents think that productivity of the laborers is quite enough in order to maintain and increase the export rate. In this survey, it could be seen that 60% of the selected individuals think that productivity is sufficient. Higher productivity of the workers will facilitate the garment companies of Bangladesh to produce efficient quality materials and export them to the importing countries in time. This will increase their reputation.

In addition, it could be seen that 40% of the selected individuals think that productivity of the workers needs to be increased. This could be done by selecting efficient workers and giving them proper training. The management of the garment firms in Bangladesh needs to organize proper training programs relating with modern technologies.

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Productivity is sufficient	18	60%	30
Productivity needs to be increased	12	40%	30

Table 4.33: Productivity of labors

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.33: Graphical representation of productivity of labours

Discussion:

Q34: Do you agree that inflation is a major barrier in export of garment industry?

Inflation is global problem that is hampering trade and business all over the world in the last few years. The costs of raw materials are increasing day by day. This problem is more prominent in developing countries like Bangladesh. 20% of the respondents strongly agree with the point whereas 30% of the selected people support it. It could be seen that majority of the selected individuals believes that rising inflation rate is creating a barrier in the export of readymade garments in Bangladesh. Inflation will not only hamper the price of the raw materials but this will also force the firms to increase the daily wage of the labors. The operational cost of the firms will also increase. This will hamper in the price of the products. The importer countries generally search for good quality products at a reasonable price. Hence, they will choose those countries that are less affected due to inflation. On the other hand, countries like Bangladesh will suffer in respect

to exporting of garment materials. However, 23.33% of the selected individuals disagreed with the point as they believe that inflation has not affected export of garment materials in Bangladesh. 20% of the individuals strongly disagreed with the point and they are considering inflation as a barrier in the way of export. 6.66% of the respondents are in a neutral state regarding this point.

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Strongly agree	6	20%	30
agree	9	30%	30
Neither agree nor disagree	2	6.66%	30
disagree	7	23.33%	30
Strongly disagree	6	20%	30

Table 4.34: Opinions regarding inflation

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.34: Graphical representation of opinions regarding inflation

(Source: Created by author)

Q35: Do you think that exchange rate could affect the export of garment products in Bangladesh?

Exchange rate between countries is a major factor that impacts in the trade and business around the world. Exchange rates of different currencies are not equal. This hampers the export of materials by creating a barrier. In this survey, it could be seen that approximately 36.66% of the respondents think that fall in exchange rates will make the export cheaper. Exports to countries

will become cheaper and the companies that are exporting will be benefitted. However, the importer will be affected by the fall of exchange rates. The Bangladesh garment companies, which are buying raw materials from other countries, will get affected because they have to pay higher price in order to buy the raw materials. 30% of the selected individuals have given this statement. On the other hand, this will also hamper the price of the product, which will create problem during exporting as demand will decrease. 33.33% of the respondents have given this statement.

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Fall in exchange rate will make export cheaper	11	36.66%	30
Fall in exchange rate will hamper in raw material collection	9	30%	30
Fall in exchange rate may decrease the demand	10	33.33%	30

Table 4.35: Opinions regarding exchange rate

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.35: Graphical representation of opinions regarding exchange rate

(Source: Created by author)

Q36: Do you think that double taxation can be considered as a barrier in exporting of garment products?

Double Taxation is one of the most prominent problem or barriers in export. Double taxation could be defined as paying tax two times for the transaction of a material. Several countries have done double tax agreements in order to pay double taxes. In this survey, 56.66% of the respondents think that double taxation is a major barrier that is hampering the export of garments in Bangladesh. At the same time, during importing raw materials for garment industry from any other countries, the companies need to pay double tax to both legislations. This is hampering the business by increasing operational costs. 43.33% of the people think that double taxation is not hampering the exportation of garment materials. Double tax agreements are a safeguard, which Bangladesh could adopt in order to save the companies to pay double tax. The government of the country needs to prepare a list of countries, which import garment products from Bangladesh and needs to sign a treaty regarding double taxations. This will influence export and import and will increase the export rate of garment products in the country. Framing appropriate government policies will help to minimize this problem.

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Yes	17	56.66%	30
No	13	43.33%	30

Table 4.36: Opinions regarding double taxation barrier

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.36: Graphical representation of opinions regarding double taxation barrier

(Source: Created by author)

Q37: Are export licenses easily available in Bangladesh?

Import and export licenses are the initial requirements in order to do cross-border business. This enables a businessman to buy or sell products to countries without any intervention from the government. Generally, in order to get an export license a business owner needs to apply in the desired government portal and submit all the details. Then after verification and paying some charge, the businessman gets the export license. However, the result in this survey shows that majority of the respondents are not satisfied with the present system of allocating export license by the government. 63.33% of the selected individuals are not happy with the present system. They think that the government officials take much time for investigation process and the system

is also not transparent. The government of the country needs to maintain transparency in order to give export license to the businessmen faster. In order to do so, the concerned government department of Bangladesh needs to do the whole process of issuing export license online. This will make the process easier as the applicants could fill the form and make payments online. In addition, the investigation process needs to be done efficiently in short span of time and eliminating any bias.

Figure 4.37: Graphical representation of opinions regarding availability of export licenses in Bangladesh.

(Source: Created by author)

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Yes	11	36.66%	30
No	19	63.33%	30

Table 4.37: Opinions regarding availability of export licenses in Bangladesh

(Source: Created by author)

Q38: Do you agree that GDP of Bangladesh acts as a barrier in export of RMG?

GDP or gross domestic product is an important factor that creates an impact in the growth of export rate. An increase in GDP will increase the reputation of the country. GDP growth rate of Bangladesh is approximately 7.3% over the last decade, but GDP per capita and overall GDP is much lower than the importing countries. This can create a negative impact in the business environment of the country. 26.66% of the selected people believe that this factor strongly hampers the export of garment products. 20% of the respondents think that GDP of Bangladesh needs to be improved and the current status is creating a barrier to export garment products. GDP could be increased by increasing the revenue collection of the country. In addition, improvement in the infrastructure and creating more employment opportunities also impacts in the GDP of a country. 10% of the respondents have neither agree nor disagreed with the point. However, 23.33% of the individuals think that GDP of Bangladesh is not creating any barrier in exporting garment materials. 20% of the individuals strongly disagreed with this point of discussion.

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Strongly agree	8	26.66%	30
agree	6	20%	30
Neither agree nor disagree	3	10%	30
disagree	7	23.33%	30
Strongly disagree	6	20%	30

Table 4.38: Opinions regarding GDP of Bangladesh

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.38: Graphical representation of opinions regarding GDP of Bangladesh

(Source: Created by author)

Q39: Do you think that accidents in RMG industries are affecting export in Bangladesh?

In the last few years, the apparel industry of Bangladesh has been affected by several incidents, which has taken many lives of labors. The Tazreen fire incident and collapse of rana plaza has taken many lives. This has hampered the image of the garment industry of Bangladesh. In this survey, it could be seen that 70% of the individuals think that these incidents have created a barrier

in export of garment products. Creation of good workplace and providing safety and security to the workers are primary requirements, which the management needs to fulfil. This will increase the productivity of the workers. In a survey in Bangladesh, it was seen that maximum buildings of garment industry are prone to fire incidents. However, the number of deaths due to collapse of building is much higher than deaths due to fire. The owners need to make proper arrangements in order to fight against any odd situations. Better workplace will improve the workplace condition and will motivate the workers to perform efficiently. 30% of the employees think that accidents in garment industry did not impact in the export of the garment products.

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Yes	21	70%	30
No	9	30%	30

Table 4.39: Opinions regarding accidents in RMG industries are affecting export in Bangladesh

(Source: Created by author)

Figure 4.39: Graphical representation of opinions regarding accidents in RMG industries are affecting export in Bangladesh
 (Source: Created by author)

Q40: What do you recommend to increase the export rate of RMG?

In this survey, the respondents are asked to recommend appropriate measures that could be adopted in order to increase the export rate of the garment products, eliminating all the barriers. It could be seen that 30% of the respondents think that improving the quality of the products will help the country to increase the export rate. Improving the quality of the products will satisfy the current

importers and at the same time potential importers will be attracted. 26.66% of the selected individuals think that improvement in the government policies would be effective in order to increase the export rate. Government policies regarding export, taxation, giving export license and creating healthy and safety workplace will increase the productivity of the companies of readymade industry. In addition, double taxation agreements with other countries will facilitate the exporting companies to export their materials without paying double tax. 23.33% of the individuals think that controlling the price of the products will increase the export rate, whereas 20% of the respondents think export rate could be increased by increasing the productivity of the labors. The productivity of the workers could be increased by giving them appropriate training. This will enable the companies to supply order in time.

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Improvement in government policies	8	26.66%	30
Increase the productivity of the labors	6	20%	30
Improving the quality of the products	9	30%	30
Controlling the price	7	23.33%	30

Table 4.40: Recommendation to increase the export rate of RMG

(Source: Created by author)

Recommendation to increase the export rate of RMG

Figure 4.40: Graphical representation of recommendation to increase the export rate of RMG

(Source: Created by author)

4.2 Part B: Qualitative Data Interpretations

Q1. What kind of Barriers are you facing at present?

The First manager has mentioned that after Brexit, they are facing difficulties regarding export of garments in countries of UK. The Bangladesh-Britain trade channel was used by Bangladesh RMG industry in order to trade in various European countries. After Brexit, Bangladesh Garment industry is not eligible for quota free access in UK countries. As this country was a British colony, they had opportunities to explore their business in European market. At present they are facing difficulties in this regard. As mentioned by the second manager, lack of skilled labor has become a barrier to Garment industry of this country. Transformation as well as upgradation of this Industry has become slower due to shortage of skilled workers. However, it has been found that government of this country has taken initiative to increase manpower for apparel sector.

3rd manager has exclaimed that, this industry is facing problems in understanding overseas customers. As overseas customers have different cultural background, it is becoming complicated to understand their requirements. Different regional language can be considered as a main reason behind miscommunication between customers and RMG organizations. This industry needs to recognize potential customers and pay respect to cultural background of customers in order to ensure customer loyalty. According to the 4th manager, foreign trade policy is a difficult barrier of this industry. The new American president has mentioned to include extra taxes on trading and this can cause threat to Bangladesh's RMG industry. These managers have mentioned that they are working hard to develop strategies to mitigate these challenges.

1st Manager	2nd Manager	3rd manager	4th Manager
<p><i>“Brexit has impacted on RMG industry as export to UK market has become difficult”</i></p>	<p><i>“It is difficult to hire skilled workers and it is affecting business progress”</i></p>	<p><i>“We are facing difficulties in understanding overseas customers”</i></p>	<p><i>“In think foreign trade policy is affecting our business and we must develop strategies to cope up with this situation”</i></p>

Q2. What strategies have you developed to mitigate challenges?

1st manager has said that their company has focused on improvement of garment quality in order to attract overseas customers. This approach can help them to maintain their reputation in global market. Financial loss due to Brexit can be compensated if this strategy works. Lack of skilled labour is a major problem of Garment industry and this problem must be mitigated by RMG organizations in order to ensure business progress. 2nd manager has mentioned that their company has organized training program for their workers to increase their productivity. Trained workers will be able to perform better and quality of garment can be improved. This approach will help organizations to obtain maximum number of customers.

1st Manager	2nd Manager	3rd manager	4th Manager
<p><i>“We are trying to improve quality of our garments in order to attract more customers towards our business”</i></p>	<p><i>“Our company has organized training program to educate our workers and we are expecting that this approach will help us to increase productivity”</i></p>	<p><i>“I think we should recognize and accept foreign culture in order to serve better to overseas customers”</i></p>	<p><i>“We are trying to explore our business in all areas of world in order to enhance our revenue”</i></p>

According to 3rd manager, they need to understand foreign culture in order to develop good relationship with overseas customers. Because of cultural difference, organizations of this industry are facing problems in dealing with foreign customers. They can train their employees about foreign cultures as this will help them to communicate with foreign customers. If they will provide respect to foreign culture, it will be easier for them to avoid misunderstandings in business. 4th manager has mentioned that, they need to explore their business in all areas of world in order maximize their revenue. After Brexit this industry is facing problems to trade in UK countries. They can explore their business in other countries to gain more financial benefits from their business.

Q3. How barriers are affecting customers overseas?

Managers have agreed that there are several barriers that are affecting overseas customers. 1st manager has mentioned that different language in different countries is creating trouble in dealing with international customers. They have faced difficulties in this area and their company has decided to use a common language like English in order to communicate with international customers. 2nd manager has discussed another major barrier of this industry. He has explained that, cultural difference is a remarkable cause behind misunderstandings between clients and organizations. This industry is facing trouble to understand foreign culture and this aspect is affecting their export business. Misunderstanding and misinterpretation of words can affect relationship with their customers. These organizations are trying to recognize and understand foreign culture in order to manage overseas customers. They are providing training to their employees to about foreign culture in order to improve relation with customers. 3rd manager has mentioned that difference in time zone can be considered as difficult barriers that can affect

1st Manager	2nd Manager	3rd manager	4th Manager
<i>“As per my understanding, language barrier is the main obstacle of customer management”</i>	<i>“Due to cultural difference customers has misunderstood out intention and for this reason we have lost several customers”</i>	<i>“Different time zone is a challenge for us in dealing with international customers”</i>	<i>“Money transaction problem has affected overseas customers and our business has faced financial issues due to this problem”</i>

customers. Due to different time zone, organizations of this industry are facing difficulties to communicate with their customers. They are not being able to solve queries of their customers within short time period. Customers are not getting immediate care from these organizations due to difference in time zone, for this reason, many companies of RMG industry have lost lots of customers. As mentioned by the 4th manager. This industry is facing problem regarding money transaction and this aspect is affecting their customers as well. As there is difference of currency, customers are facing trouble to pay for their orders. Online money transaction process has helped in this aspect. However, more initiatives are required to undertake by organizations in order to obtain their payment faster. If this problem can be shorted, customers will be happy to develop business relationship with organizations of Bangladesh RMG industry.

Q4. What strategies have you developed to improve export system?

Bangladesh’s garment industry is trying to mitigate barriers in order to maximize their financial benefits. 1st manager has stated that they must select potential market in order to obtain more customers for their business. Appropriate decision regarding selection of potential market will help this industry to generate maximum revenue from their business. This approach will help them to explore their business in different countries worldwide. 2nd manager has mentioned a different perspective regarding improvement of export business. According to him, development of strategic relationship can help them to explore their business. This industry of Bangladesh needs to develop business relationship with other readymade garment maker countries. They are considering Ethiopia and Myanmar in this regard. By this approach, Bangladesh will be able to purchase

1st Manager	2nd Manager	3rd manager	4th Manager
<p><i>“I think we can select potential market in order to explore our business internationally.”</i></p>	<p><i>“Our company is focusing on development of international relationships in order to explore our export business”</i></p>	<p><i>“We have focused on increase of productivity in order to pay government taxes for export business and this approach will help us to maintain our annual financial benefit”</i></p>	<p><i>“We are improving our negotiation power in order to obtain value for our uniqueness from international market”</i></p>

required resources of readymade garment from those countries. This kind of collaborative effort can help this organization to explore their export business.

New elected American president has mentioned that he can include additional taxes for importers of America. Similarly, different country has developed different taxation policy for exporters. According to 3rd manager, they need to increase their productivity in order to enhance their earning. He has mentioned that increasing revenue will help them to pay government taxes and this approach will help them to avoid legal issues. In order to do so, they are providing training to their workers and developing innovative business strategies. It has been noticed that, Bangladesh is poor in negotiations. This point has been mentioned by the 4th manager. He has included that this industry has ensured quality garments and these garments are cost effective. In addition, Bangladesh can be considered as most strategic location. These reasons are making this industry unique. They need to negotiate to achieve maximum payment for their products. This approach will help this industry to improve their export business and they will be able to gain more profit from their business.

Q5. In your opinion what is the role of exporting garment in the economic status of Bangladesh?

Discussion:

According to the first manager, the RMG garment export has an important role in the economy of the country. As per his opinion especially Bangladesh has made a strong textile market in USA. Yearly a healthy number of foreign exchanges satisfy the economy of Bangladesh. According to him only from USA more than \$2 billion foreign currency comes in Bangladesh every year. As

per his opinion the garment export has a strong impact on the country's economic status. The opinion of second manager is almost same as the first manager. His opinion has a focus on global export market not only country-based export. As he mentioned that near about \$5 billion overseas currency comes in the country per annum. The people in US are quite satisfied with the garment of Bangladesh. This has a strong impact on the export condition. As per both of them RMG industry has strong influence in the economy of the country.

First Manager	Second Manager	Third Manager	Fourth Manager
<i>“Bangladesh has made an apparel market in US. RMG Garments worth more than \$2 billion export in USA from Bangladesh yearly.”</i>	<i>“Garments worth near about \$5 billion has been exported by Bangladesh Globally.”</i>	<i>“Garment export in Bangladesh has very strong position in global market. More than 70% of the economy in country is due to the export in international market.”</i>	<i>“As global market position of Bangladesh is continuously evolving, so it has a strong contribution in the economy of the country.”</i>

Third manager has given a positive opinion towards the export market of Bangladesh. As per his opinion more than 70% of the monetary status of the country is supported by the amount comes due to export. The fourth manager's opinion is related to the ideas on global market position of the Bangladesh in case of garment export. The interviews data has strong indication on the sustainable position of the country in the international RMG garment export market. Continual export

condition of the country has a powerful impact on the economy of the country. As per third manager's opinion the less labour cost in the country is one big reason of the export of the garment in reasonable price. This has an interrelation with the financial status of the country.

Q6. According to you what is the future of RMG garments of Bangladesh and relation with export in international market?

As per the first manager in the international market Bangladesh has a strong and bright future. The RMG garment industry in the country is using the advanced and modern new invented technologies to make the quality better. The spinning, weaving, dyeing, printing technologies are becoming advanced by using new technologies. As per the second manager's opinion the controlled cost is one of the best reasons to be popular in the global market. He also said that increased export and production will make more scope of employment in the country. This condition will make the internal social and economic condition better in the country.

As per the third manager's opinion the diversification in the export of RMG garments by using the advanced technologies in printing and new inventory ideas will help to create new marketplace. This will help to make more foreign money in future by exporting the garments in developed country. As per the fourth manager over 20 years the export market of the RMG Garments of Bangladesh is in the growing condition. By facing any challenges and difficulties they are stable in the global export market. This increasing growth will help the country to get free access in the US market in near future. As per his opinion market has demand of local traditional garments of Bangladesh. For this reason, this country is introducing new manufacture garment products in the international market to create new wide market for future.

First Manager	Second Manager	Third Manager	Fourth Manager
<p><i>“The use of modern and advanced technology in the textile is important which will create the bright future of RMG export.”</i></p>	<p><i>“The controlled cost and good quality are important to be in the competition in the global market. The increased market will create employment scope”</i></p>	<p><i>“Diversification in the RMG garments will help to get new marketplace.”</i></p>	<p><i>“Expected growth rate of the RMG garment industry will help to get free access to the US market.”</i></p>

Q7. What is the export condition in Bangladesh for RMG garments?

According to the first manager Bangladesh has a continuously growing sustainable export market globally. As a large amount of foreign currency introduced in the country per annum so the country has some rules and condition to manage that income and used that in social and economic welfare of the nation. There are many international treaty and agreements which help the nation to be competitive in the global market As per him to cope up the market permanently we are benefitted from Multi Fiber Agreement (MFA), 1974 of GATT. This helps the country to manage the high amount of foreign currency in short time and increase the GDP in minimum time span. By this many industries have already increased their GDP value dramatically. According to the second

manager in the year of 1994 Bangladesh joined in an agreement on Textile and clothing (ATC) for the welfare of the garment industry in the country. He also told that the ATC is not valid for the company's that established after January 1, 2005 because that rule becomes abolished.

According to the third manager the MFA is important for the garment industry to increase their GDP value in Very little time span. The MFA restrict the developed country as importers and exporters of textile industry. This makes the scope for the third world country to become developed and make a marketplace globally. As per the fourth manager ATC, which comes under WTO rule, has importance in exterminate of all quotas in the year of 2004 which make the equality all over the country.

First Manager	Second Manager	Third Manager	Fourth Manager
<i>“As Bangladesh has strong influence on the country’s economy for over last 20 years so for advantages Multi Fiber Agreement (MFA), 1974 which help to manage the foreign income.”</i>	<i>“There are some policies and agreements related to garment export in Bangladesh such as Agreement on Textile and clothing (ATC) 1994.”</i>	<i>“MFA has influence on international business and investment in the garment (T & G) sector which is applicable for developed country in the earth like United States, the european country etc.”</i>	<i>“ATC domain has role in managing the trade of the country by WTO rule.”</i>

Q8. What are the competitive strengths of garment industry in Bangladesh that affect global export market?

As per the first manager's opinion to become competitive is one of the main strengths to cope up a diverse export market throughout the world. In order to reach in the competitive strength, the companies need to use some effective strategy such as reduction in the product value. Bangladesh is improving their strategy in order to reach the competitive strength. According to the second manager to reach in the competitive strength the country is using a three-way plan. Their plan is upgrade the technology first followed by creating new market scope and diversification in the product. New ideas in the products will create the market scope for the RMG garment industry.

As opined by the third manager for the success the right path followed by accurate policies is important to cope up the market globally. The policies and agreement will make the garment companies of Bangladesh legally stronger in comparison to the companies in other country. According to the fourth manager the lowering the cost of the product and maximization of the quality of the garments are two main factors that is main strategy in order to create vast market globally. He also told that the competitors are important and based on their market strategy companies can standardize their strategy for better export market internationally. As per his statement the price level of the parents is important to create a global export market.

First Manager	Second Manager	Third Manager	Fourth Manager
<p><i>“Competitive strengths are important to get more diverse export market globally. Bangladesh is improving the strategy to reach in the competitive strength.”</i></p>	<p><i>“For reaching in the competitive strength the country is using three Way plan including overall and technological up gradation, search new market place and diversification of the products.</i></p>	<p><i>“The success comes through right path and accurate strategy. Other than that, the policy and agreements have also important role.”</i></p>	<p><i>“The increase in the quality and decrease of the cost are the main strategy to be competitive in the global market. The price of the RMG garment products is important factor for competitive in future.”</i></p>

4.3 Part C: Secondary Analysis:

Global trends in the garment industry

In the current world, apparel and textiles amount is approximately US\$ 130 billion and therefore, it can be said that garment industry is growing rapidly. Total amount of the trade has gone approximately US\$70 billion and that entire trade is divided into both apparel and textiles. As stated by Alam, Azim & Alias (2017), along with exceptions in Federal Republic in Germany and Italy, all the industrial economies are considered as the larger importer of the textiles. In this context, it is noticed that there are several developing countries such as Korea, China, Turkey and Hong Kong have increased the standing and those are considered as the major exporters. Due to the deficit in the textile industry, both the imports and export ratios are getting reduced, however, these are not getting eliminated. In Germany, the textile industry got restructured so that the specialisation degree in the context of garment industry can be increased. The manufacturing of garment industry in Bangladesh at the lower end is in the favour of the outward processing and therefore, it is dependent on the imports that come from some developing countries.

Demand and supply is the major factor for any product and as argued by Al-Amin & Hoque (2015), high added value as well as high quality does create competitive advantage for any country. This helps in the specialisation and restructuring and these things are observed in Japan and Italy. Therefore, it can be said that the exporting of the garment industry needs to be compared with other developing countries. Industrial economies need to be matched with the textile imports that are of low-value and due to this reason, besides becoming an exporter, it has become net importers. In comparison to Bangladesh, China is the country which is considered as the major exporters and here, it deals with those textiles which are having low to medium value additions. Due to this reason, the competitiveness factors have increased in Bangladesh and the country need to change

certain strategies so that garment industry can be developed in an appropriate manner. On the contrary, Ali et al., (2017) have mentioned that Hong Kong was not a good producer initially, however, it has been noticed that export of the garment industry and output of garments are being modernised. This leads to the improvement of weaving and spinning capacities. Therefore, as these type of competitiveness is increasing at high level, therefore, it is creating major barriers for Bangladesh to export the garments to other countries.

Finally, it can be said that there are several developing countries in the exporting of garments and that involves, Bangladesh, Mauritius, Morocco, Costa Rica, Sri Lanka and Bahamas. These countries were able to develop their garment sector due to low labour cost. Therefore, it can be said that Bangladesh is considered as having major garment industry using cheap labour and over the years, it has also developed capabilities of manufacturing high-quality textiles for the export to other countries (Ali & Moudud-Ul-Huq, 2016).

Threat from several regional organisations

Bangladesh is having remarkable presence for the garment industry and it is majorly in the EU and US markets. As this is the scenario, the opportunity profile and external threats are increasing to a great extent. External threats are the powerful competitors which create obstacles in trading environment. These threats are created in such a manner that it became major hurdles for Bangladesh for improving the competitive edge. As mentioned by Anisul et al., (2014), barriers can be of several forms and it is noticed that nowadays these are taking place majorly. The major barriers that are found are MFA phasing out and the non-tariff barriers. It seems that as RMG exports of Bangladesh is growing at a rapid pace, therefore, it is becoming threat for certain powerful competitors. As this is case, the competitors are making certain strategies so that garment industry market can be snatched away from Bangladesh.

The competitors are taking the advantages of MFA phase out. This has become the major barriers in Bangladesh and these needs to be identified clearly so that proper actions can be taken. As opined by Ansell et al., (2015), GATT (General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade) is not at all included in the apparel industries in the principles of MFN. Therefore, Uruguay Round (UR) has decided to link the textile industry with GATT system. However, it has been seen that the tariff barriers that are unjustified can be prohibited by WTO or GATT. As stated by Billah & Manik (2017), discrimination among the trading partners has become the major barriers for the export industry of Bangladesh in regards to garment industry. The trading must be done in a fair manner so that barriers can be mitigated to a certain level. It has been identified that labour cost is another major factor that creates restriction in those developing countries which are cost-disadvantaged. Due to this reason, the latter countries become injured.

Furthermore, it is realised that interests for the textile industries are much high and that has been recognised by GATT. Trend of modern world is regionalism and that is required for strengthening economy of several member countries and that can be done through the proper cooperation. As commented by Biswas et al., (2018), threats majorly come from several regional organisations and those are NAFTA, EFTA, EEC and many more. As per NAFTA, USA can invest the domestic resources so that their economy can be developed with the help of usage of approximately 65% of raw materials. Majorly, all these creates barrier for the exporting of garment from Bangladesh to other countries. Sometimes it happens that some of the developed countries do not show any interest to get products from Bangladesh. Therefore, it can be said that it has become the potential threat for Bangladeshi garment industry.

Again, the EC countries have decided to give protection for the interest of member countries and that are done with the help of cooperation. Therefore, it can be said that if these types of protections

are given, then it can be a great threat for garment industry for Bangladesh. As mentioned by Brooks (2016), this is not threat for only Bangladesh; it is a threat for other countries as well such as Britain, Belgium and many more, as they are purchasers of garments of the Bangladesh. Apart from this, there are certain other threats that are creating barriers for Bangladesh and those are Raw materials scarcity, political instability, and issue of child labour and also there are certain other business activities that become threat for Bangladesh at a huge extent.

Hopeful succession of Bangladesh while negotiating with US

US relate increase of the quota of garment export to the labour standard. Therefore, Bangladesh wants to have hopeful success in order to have negotiations in US market access. Government of Bangladesh has requested for rise of the export quota of about 30% rise for readymade garments and this request has been done to the US markets. Due to this reason, it has been seen that as export quota is rising, child labour is being eliminated. Approximately 10% will be added in the export quota of US market and this will affect the RMG export industry to a great extent. As commented by Carlson & Bitsch (2018), issues related to the labour standard are considered as a major barrier for the exporting of garments to other countries. It has been seen that Cambodians have failed in implementing the proper labour standards and because of this several labourers ignore to work properly. Therefore, that hampers the exporting of goods because that is affecting both in production and distribution. The same thing took place with Bangladesh; however, there were no such justification for this problem (Carlson & Bitsch, 2018). From the source, it has been known that Bangladesh embassy within Washington and BGMEA lobbyist has given enough effort so that their negotiations can be made successful as this led to the mitigation of the barriers. Apparel makers of the country has implemented some specific labour standards and these include better working conditions, hygienic and health standards, regular payment, safety measures and

overtime. As this has been implemented properly, therefore, the production, distribution and exporting are done in a good manner and hence that mitigates the barriers. After the negotiations, the US administration has taken up all the issues of Bangladesh Government as it has delayed to amend the law that allows the activities of trade union in Export Processing Zones. As mentioned by Choudhury & Rahman (2017), trade union is another barrier for hampering the export of garments to other countries.

There are some other issues also and that emerges while negotiating problems of adolescence workers. These workers have knowledge barriers at a huge level and therefore, it creates huge barriers for exporting business of garments. It has been seen that garment industry is the major industry for which the economic development is huge in Bangladesh because it creates a huge source of foreign exchange in the country and therefore, negotiations are highly required.

Economic growth of Bangladesh despite challenges

It is expected that economy of Bangladesh will increase up to approximately 6% in the upcoming fiscal year even if there are several challenges in regards to textile exports. As there were several challenges, there were huge loss of job and this report has been given by IMF. IMF has forecasted about the budget estimation and then it has been noticed that economy had been recovered from the devastating floods. Due to loss of the quotas, competition has opened up to a great extent and there are some large rivals that include India and China. Due to these two countries, more barriers are taking place and this is hampering the economic development of the country.

Quota system of international textile is termed as the Multifibre Arrangement and despite of this, economic development of the country is increasing accordingly. This quota has been abolished at some point of time because this is creating a major challenge for the job loss (Chowdhury, 2016).

In the month of June, 2014, it has been noticed that Bangladesh has exported goods approximately of 8 billion dollars and among these goods, 75% were textiles. However, it is a fact that Bangladesh has faced key challenges in acceleration of growth. Moreover, challenges are faced in Bangladesh while maintaining stability of macroeconomic in order to overcome the significant result of MFA phase out. For the economic development, exporting is required and for that, products of all ranges must be present in the market of higher-quality. In regards to cotton fabrics, the marketers have tendencies to focus on the export of standard products that includes, men's shirts, T-shirts, printed fabrics and many more. However, for this price is considered as the major determinant for which several barriers can be created.

In the current scenario, major changes are taking place in developed markets. There are no cheap imports as the finishing of the products are better. In addition to this, higher quality casuals are exported as per the choices of the countries. In this scenario, government is trying to overcome their problems in the RMG sector. It has been seen that Government is making their efforts so that they can overcome all the barriers faced by garment industry of Bangladesh. For this, the government has tried to make the duty free as well as quota free for the purpose of accessing of goods of Bangladesh to European and US markets. As opined by Chowdhury & Quaddus (2015), garment sector of Bangladesh is considered as the major earner of foreign currency that has earned 70% of total exports of country in last year. Bangladesh has made economic growth faster and it has projected approximately 5.5% growth in the GDP. Performance of the export has marked a steady progress with an increase of 17% in the current fiscal year. RMG are exported and in this case both the knitwear and woven has been picked up because of the increasing rate of global demand even if there are several barriers. Therefore, it has been noticed that export earnings were 70% in Bangladesh.

Current Export Condition in RMG Sector

RMG is actual trading industry within Bangladesh that experienced the sensational development within most current 20 years. Through exploration of protected market as per arrangement of MFA of the GATT, it leads to accomplishment of prominent distance of fares, industrialisation, commitment and trade income to GDP of other nations. As stated by Ali & Moudud-Ul-Huq (2016), it gets inside with some limited ability in focussing on time with amount of the assembling units that are developed from about 180 to 3600 and more in course of current years. Henceforth, RMG division assumed as additionally noteworthy part within financial improvement regarding Bangladesh. As explained by Evans (2016), fares that are created by these garments industries in Dhaka are enhancing endless quantity of time along with some exceptions of a year. Design, strike, political issue, shutdown of industries, expansion, financial issue and many more are major cause for the diminishing fare within imperative area. As opined by Dhiman & Sharma (2016), in segmentation of trade, RMD garment industries are the major part in garment industry sector in Bangladesh. Henceforth, in this course of more current 30 years, universal interests and universal exchange in worldwide articles and global materials of clothing areas are affected by MFA. In addition, these areas carry out with quantitative limitations along with some standards that are connected by major merchants of Bangladesh depending on trades from the other creating nations (Hasan, 2017).

Bangladesh seems to be winding up the huge increasing processes of forming brands and clothing retailers in worldwide basis. In addition, nation is giving reliably C&M benefit with no more concentration on cost keeping and principles of satisfactory quality. As influenced by Habib (2016), it needs to be kept within mind that end goals are to be used for open doors to make products of theirs for swift exports. In addition, there exists noticeable and mould brands that are

proposed in building sourcing from Dhaka. It deals with alternative retailers such as making circumstance as lucrative, precarious in meantime for business of garments. Henceforth, this issue regarding Bangladesh garments at current date is intended towards making diagram of attire retailers and designing brands. As criticised by Hansen (2016), these are sourced from Dhaka with purpose of the perspective about current business.

There is huge concern regarding the lead time of Bangladesh Garment industry. Due to Bangladesh failure to reduce lead time, many orders are going to Vietnam and China. At the same time, Bangladesh has still lot of issues when it comes to develop JIT (Just-in-time) manufacturing process and implement Six Sigma in production.

For past 25 years, RMG is the main foreign exchange source and major export item in Bangladesh. Garment's sector of Bangladesh is expanded in vigorous way to maintain maturity of it's by holding the second position globally. Henceforth, Bangladesh is supplying successfully all the apparel products in consistent manner to international and premier fashion markets.

Barriers faced by the Exporters of Bangladesh

Constraints that are faced by the exporters of Bangladesh act as multifarious due to lack of the finance, which is identified as major constraint as exporters of both the small sized and the medium sized industries are identified as affected more severely by this barrier. As commented by Islam, Rakib & Adnan (2016), in addition, infrastructural obstacle is perhaps most affecting and having serious bottleneck regarding expansion of the export activities along with activities of argumentative investments in Bangladesh. The government rules, regulations of Bangladesh pertain towards exporting garment products of RMG garment industries that are complicated in nature and need more paperwork. As observed by Islam & Pattak (2017), in addition, valuable time of senior management is spend over with officials of government of Bangladesh depending

on interpretations along with changes in the laws, regulations. Thus, exporters of Dhaka are needed to pay the extra amount of money to the officials of customs in order to receive their checked export consignments. In addition, payment is needed to be made towards officials of ports along with officials of telephone service, airport personnel and power personnel. As suggested by Jacobs et al., (2016), even there prevails process of bribing that are paid to the other officials of service personnel. Cost regarding doing business in Bangladesh seems to be very high, mainly due to absence of the skilled manpower in sectors such as leather, RMG, information technology, electronics and data entry.

Most of enterprises in Dhaka carry out with neither in house capacity for collecting essential information about trade nor networking facility towards access information. Issues of market access are becoming complex, diversified as increasingly. As argued by Khan & Ullah (2017), access of Bangladesh to the market of European Union is jeopardised depending on both environmental requirements and ecological needs. On other hand, environmental conditions are tied to continue for posing serious issues to exporters of Bangladesh over the time. Henceforth, in Bangladesh, base of export has remained as narrow carrying out with no such breakthrough, which appears to be visible in nature. Such breakthrough leads to expansion of export baskets with removal of the quotas along with process of the restructuring of RMG sector on global basis. As discussed by Khan & Abasyn (2017), these are expected in evolving when aspects of quality and competitiveness of price seems to be dictating predominantly depending on behaviour of market. On other hand, comprehensive strategies are required to deal along with sector of RMG in post era of MFA. Henceforth, increasing importance of the knit RMG requires to be provided with some special attention. In addition, activities of backward linkage are needed for strengthening purpose

for further operations in RMG garment industries. Thus, strong and political commitment is needed for pursuing proactive policy of export (Khan et al., 2017).

4.4. Summary

According to global trends in the garments industry, the current apparel textile industry is a \$130 million industry and is still rapidly growing. Italy and Germany are the only developed countries that export apparel while the others import. Korea, Turkey, China, Hong Kong along with Bangladesh are joining in on imports. There have been developments in Germany so that their garments industry improves. Bangladesh is on the lower end or the last stage considering manufacturing or outer processing which means many other countries are dependent on these imports. Demand and supply are the major factors for any product. High quality value and value creation gives a country competitive advantage globally and specialization restructuring helps here which can be seen in Japan and Italy. Bangladesh is able to provide products with low-labor cost but its competitors are more advanced with quality. China is a major exporter and is able to supply with low to medium level products. Hong Kong initially was not a good producer, but has gradually improved specially developing with weaving and spinning. Bangladesh needs more technological development for its products even if it has improved with quality over the years.

Bangladesh has a few threats from regional organizations such as from the European Union (EU) and the United States market. One of these threats include the expiration of the Multi Fibre Arrangement which is creating non-tariff barriers. On the other hand, competitors are able to take advantage from this expiration. Bangladesh needs to work on these barriers. Free trade and tariff free processes are not applicable in many places of these agreements. Even if World Trade Organization (WTO) and General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) are able to remove these non-tariff barriers, there is discrimination present for some countries. Interest rate in the

apparel industry is very high which is recognized by GATT which leads to regionalism. This allows the creation of zones by many countries such as North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) which allows benefits for its members only. As Bangladesh is not part of such zones, it is facing barriers from these competitors. Most developed nations are not interested to take products from Bangladesh. The EU countries also provide protection among members. Bangladesh has also faced political issues of child labor and lack of access to raw materials in the past.

The United States has instilled quotas on garments industry based on labor standards. So, Bangladesh needs to develop its labor standards to gain greater access to the US market. We are forced to eliminate more labor as the restrictions keep increasing but at the moment, we are not able to export freely without barriers. This is because most of the factors are related to labor and we may face problems and lose markets similar to Cambodia as they did not follow proper labor standards. However, Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA) lobbyists and Bangladesh embassy officials in the US has given enough effort so as to mitigate such barriers for now. Bangladesh is also trying to improve better labor working conditions, hygienic and health condition, regular payment, safety measures and overtime which is being noticed by foreign countries and are providing support with interests. However, there is still room for improvement even if the situation is getting better. Trade unions can also be another problem due to trade unions and regulations can put pressure. Knowledge barriers and negotiations can also become a recurring problem as the local owners does not have enough information yet.

Bangladesh is still able to improve its economy regardless of these problems according to data from IMF and the world bank. There are several challenges such as loss of quota advantage and increase in competition which is creating job loss. Price is a huge determinant with cotton products which can fluctuate due to inflation and cause problems with buyers. We are also forced to import

capital and raw materials for finished products for export. Government is supporting this initiative with better access. Globally, knitwear and woven products have high demand from Bangladesh and has high export earnings with future possible growth. This shows the importance of RMG sector on the GDP but lacks diversification. The RMG sector has provided Bangladesh prominent industrialization, trade income benefits and commitment from foreign investment. However, the congestion and increase in fare has decreased revenue for the companies and the government with taxation. Strikes, labor movements, design problems, lack of funding and political instability have decreased revenue and growth in certain areas. We can only hope that the country's garments sector grows and we may have more benefits in the long run (possibly in 30 years). Bangladesh is trying to work with numerous brands but it is difficult to say how successful it has become as there are many alternatives available. Most countries are focusing on improving quality. The country has a problem with increasing lead time compared to Vietnam and China which is decreasing orders. This is why Bangladesh needs more modern innovation in its supply chain such as Just In Time (JIT) and implementation of six sigma production. Therefore, we need to focus on the industry which has given us benefits in the last 25 years.

Bangladesh has faced financial, infrastructure barriers and obstacles of government rule regulation which is causing bottle necks. The country also has a lot of politics and bribing which increases costs and lacks skilled labor and data management. There are in-house problems as well such as in information collecting, networking facilities with not special organizations. Bangladesh faces issues in entering European markets due to lack of ideas in environmental requirements and ecological need. We need a comprehensive strategy to tackle the export basket. We also need to strengthen backward linkages in the industry along with political commitment. Therefore, we have a good hold on the current customers but we still have many problems.

Through this analysis, interpretations, findings, current state regarding RMG garment industries are understood well. In this analysis, research has identified that RMG garment industries carries out with good hold on customers. Moreover, their revenues are falling depending on virtue of various barriers during process of exports of garment products. In addition, in primary analysis, quantitative analysis along with its findings show the diversified results and outcomes that concludes the personal perceptions of the owners of RMG garment industries that seems to be varying in nature. On other hand, qualitative analysis along with its findings represents the diversified results and outcomes that conclude many expressions and feelings of the managers of RMG garment industries that appear to be varying in nature. In addition, in secondary analysis, there are detailed discussions about various themes that are related to the title of this research study. The research has been conducted with the help of several responses from the garment owners and also through several journals, articles and textbooks. However, close attentions have been made so that customers preferences for the garments can be understood in an effective manner. Hence, data analysis has been made so that proper barriers can be identified and that can be mitigated with possible solutions that have been given in the next and last chapter.

Chapter 5: Conclusion and Recommendations

5.0 Conclusion

It can be concluded that the research paper has focused on export barriers in the business of the garment industry in Bangladesh. The research has also focused on several challenges such as competitive market, globalization and so on faced by this industry. It also focuses on which manner the exports in the garment industry can enhance GDP (Gross Domestic Product) of Bangladesh and increased number of employments.

In the last two decades it has been observed that the garment industry of Bangladesh managed a prosperous standing in the export of garments goods all over the world. This is a result of the fact that Bangladesh readymade garment export (RMG export) concentrates on enhancement of social and economic development which mainly impact on the female workers in Bangladesh. It has also been observed that Bangladesh garment industry has been facing several challenges such as competitive market, globalization and so on. However, even in the face of all these challenges, the Bangladesh garment export industry has become the most dominating sector in modern economy of Bangladesh regarding generations of employment, secondary import and export earnings. On the other hand, the research has helped substantiate the impact of RMG as source of income, expenditure and revenue of Bangladesh. Hence it also concludes that Bangladesh export earnings are the main earnings in terms of its demand and supply of readymade garments in all over the world. This business stream facilitates Bangladesh to maintain an elevated position in the global economic world. Due to this, it can be concluded that the garment industry in Bangladesh has recognized as 100% export oriented. In respect to this, the sustainability of the export of Bangladesh garment industry is most beneficial for the development of the country. It has been

observed that the linkage among the transport and banking system in Bangladesh is highly important for the enhancement and development of export in Bangladesh. Therefore, it can be concluded that the good linkages between the roads of Dhaka and Chittagong may enhance the exports of readymade garments industry in Bangladesh. The research also focuses on the supply chain logistics for shipping of the finished products such as readymade garments; and raw materials required for manufacturing. The export in the garments industry in Bangladesh is hugely dependent on trucks and air transportation for the transportation of the finished products and raw materials all over the world. However, often, due to natural calamities such as flooding, the transportation of the raw materials and finished products are sometimes disrupted. Therefore, it can be concluded that the transportation system in Bangladesh may create hindrance for the exports of garment in and out of Bangladesh. The link among the transport system in Bangladesh has been acting as the major threat for garment exporters in Bangladesh.

The garment export industry has been creating the optimal expectations for better economic developments of Bangladesh. The trade liberalization can impact on both risks and opportunities in the RMG sector of Bangladesh in respect to certain trade policies such as tariffs, quotas and subsidies. These trade policies can hamper the garment businesses of Bangladesh which can have a knock-on effect on the export of garments all over the world. Hence it can be concluded that the export of the garment industry in Bangladesh is most vital in terms of its development within the country and making its mark all over the world. As mentioned previously, it is also observed that there are several disturbances due to which the export industry gets hampered such as strike, sudden shutdown of company, layout and several economic and political propagandas. From the survey of thirty individuals and four managers, it has been found that the export garment industry in Bangladesh may face different types of challenges such as competitive market, globalization

and so on in respect to time paucity and funds in the garment industry in Bangladesh. As from the overview of the secondary sources it has been found that the research has been focusing on the mitigations of the challenges faced by the exports garment industry of Bangladesh. On the other hand, it can be concluded that change of government also impacts on the exports of the garment industry in Bangladesh in terms of rules and regulations in export. Though the current interest rate is not prohibitive for the growth of RMG sector, the overall cost of financing is a major issue for the garment industry. The government must carefully analyze whether they will restrict the interest rate cap and constraint market dynamics to support industries and take the risk of economic turmoil and inefficiency due to government intervention.

The garment industry needs to concentrate on several types of problems that may impact on the financial conditions of the garment industry. Therefore, for the mitigation of these types of problems, the garment industry needs to concentrate on the several recommendations such as a greater number of employments, segmentation of the transport system for the exports of the garments in all over the world and so on; and action these plans in respect to the problem.

The export target of Bangladesh is approximately \$50 billion by 2020. Export of knitted and woven garments has helped the country to gain near about \$30.6 billion in 2016-17. The garment sector of the country contributes a large portion in the revenue collection of the country. In order to increase the competitiveness of the RMG industry, the government and management of the garment companies need to take adequate measures. Workplace safety is one of the main measures that need to be taken in order to improve the reputation of the industry. In the recent past, several incidents have happened, which have taken many lives. Majority of the deaths have occurred due to fire in buildings and building collapse. This has hampered the business to a greater extent. In

order to revive the image of the industry, the management needs to give their attention in maintaining the work environment in a better way.

Trade and export also contribute to the development of the country. Increase in export rate will help the companies to expand, creating more job opportunities. The government of the country needs to frame adequate (sufficient) policies considering the global outlook of the economy. It is the duty of the government to facilitate the companies to export their garment materials. Policies need to be framed regarding export duties and export license. The system of the government related to these functions needs to be transparent. As export of garment products contributes a major percentage in the overall earnings of the country, hence, the government needs to give special attention to the growth and development of this sector. Barriers also caused due to cultural differences and productivity of labors. Cultural and language barriers cause many problems in dealing with the overseas client. In order to satisfy the customers, the management needs to hire proper employees, who can efficiently interact with the clients. Customer satisfaction could also be gained by supplying the materials in time. This could be done by increasing the productivity and performance of the laborers. Proper training and adaptation of modern equipment will help the garment companies in Bangladesh to achieve their export targets. Modern machineries including advanced sewing machines, pressing equipment and knitting machines need to be adopted. This will help the firms to increase the productivity of the laborers.

In this era, the rise of ecommerce has simplified the operation of business and export. The garment industry of Bangladesh could also use the facilities provided by e-commerce for their growth and expansion. A large community will be opened in front of the garment manufacturers by the adoption of ecommerce. They will also get a better platform to advertise and promote their

products. The garment industry of Bangladesh has bloomed a lot in recent times, although many barriers are still there, which are hampering its expansion. The managers of the industry need to work in collaboration with the concerned ministry of the government in order to overcome those barriers efficiently. This will help the industry to grow further in future and contribute in the development of the country.

5.1 Linking Objectives with Findings

To examine present scenario to export garments in Bangladesh

The garment industry in Bangladesh has been focused on the social and economic development of Bangladesh by expanding export all over the world. On the other hand, the Bangladesh government has been focused on the products that have been produced by that country. It has been found that Bangladesh's readymade garment sector is reputed and branded in terms of its exports of garments all over the world. In the last two decades it has been found that the garment industry of Bangladesh got a successful result from the export of the garments all over the world. Bangladesh readymade garment export (RMG export) concentrates on enhancement of social and economic development in Bangladesh that mainly impacts on female workers. In respect to the present scenario, it has been found that Bangladesh garment industry has employed more than 4 million people of Bangladesh among which 40% of people are employed in the manufacturing department of garment industry. It may help to enhance the financial development in terms of export of garment industry in Bangladesh. The exports of the garment industry have focused on the employment of people all over the world. It has also been observed that the garment industry has employed more than 10 million people directly and indirectly. Bangladesh has considered this export business for the maker of golden eggs from the last 4 years. Therefore, the sustainability of the export of

Bangladesh garment industry is most beneficial for the development of the country. Hence, linkage among the transport and banking system in Bangladesh is highly important for the enhancement and development of export in Bangladesh.

To critically determine economic effects of the garment industry in Bangladesh and those effects are related to GDP, total exports and national income

Bangladesh export earnings have been recognized as the most important earnings in terms of its demand and supply of readymade garments in all over the world. In respect to these it helps Bangladesh to get a high position in the economic world. According to the export of Bangladesh garment industry the garment industry in Bangladesh has been recognized as 100% export oriented all over the world. In respect to this, the sustainability of the export of Bangladesh garment industry is most beneficial for the economic development of the country. It has observed that linkage among the transport and banking system in Bangladesh is highly important for the enhancement and development of GDP (Gross Domestic Product) in Bangladesh. These two sectors are highly depended on garment sector for its revenue. Thus, garment sector is having spillover effect of development by earning revenue for other sectors. On the other hand, it has been found that good linkages between the roads of Dhaka and Chittagong may enhance the GDP of the country in terms of exports of readymade garments industry in Bangladesh. According to its GDP and export it has been observed that Bangladesh has been recognized as the second largest clothing exporter in all over the world. The export of this sector has contributed more than 80% of the revenue of the country that may help to enhance the financial development of the country. The exports of the garment industry of Bangladesh have accounted for more than 23% of GDP of the total country in terms of its revenue and expenditure. Due to the exports of the garment the poverty rate of

Bangladesh has reduced at the rate of 25% per annum compared to 2016. In respect to these it has been observed that the garment export industry has been creating the optimal expectations for better economic development of Bangladesh. In respect to this it has been observed that trade liberalization can impact on both risks and opportunities in the RMG sector of Bangladesh in respect to certain trade policies such as tariffs, quotas and subsidies. In respect to these trade policies, it has observed that the readymade garment sector of Bangladesh can be hampered that may impact on the export of the garments all over the world. On the other hand, it also observed that there are several causes due to which the export industry gets hampered in respect to strike, sudden shutdown of company and layout and several economic and political problems. Due to this reason the country's GDP has fallen and that may impact the revenue of the country.

To recommend certain knowledge framework so that it can be used for decreasing exporting barriers and hence, an export structure can be improved

The garment industry needs to concentrate on several types of problems such as competitive market, globalization and so on that may impact on the financial conditions of the garment industry. In respect to this it has been observed that for the mitigation of these types of problems, garment industry needs to concentrate on the several recommendations such as a greater number of employments, segmentation of the transport system for the exports of the garments in all over the world and so on and actions plans in respect to the problem. The garment industry needs to concentrate on the demand-supply structure of the export of garments from Bangladesh. In respect, Bangladesh needs to concentrate on the several regulatory frameworks for the enhancement of the export of garments all over the world. Bangladesh garment industry needs to concentrate on the direct linkage between the transports systems in all over the world. On the other hand, the country

needs to concentrate on retailer distributors' profit in terms of export of garments all over the world. However, the Bangladesh government needs to focus on the rules and regulations that have been followed by the garment industry exporters that may impact on revenue of the country. One of the major detriments of higher profit is less productivity. This can not be achieved without capital investment in R&D sector. Government funding and policy can bring new era of progress in this respect. Government must provide fund and design supportive policy in this respect.

To critically identify the knowledge barriers while exporting the textiles and RMG products for the producers of Bangladesh

From this research analysis, there are various indications regarding all resources that are needed by RMG garment industries of Bangladesh in order to get competitive position in international markets. In addition, most essential and difficult things to obtain deals with information, knowledge about the target market, which provide RMG garment industries with the competitive advantage. Garment industries in Dhaka carry out with accurate quantities of knowledge that faces less uncertainty rather than the other industries with few degrees of the knowledge. On other hand, there prevails internalization regarding accumulation of the incremental knowledge. It deals with incremental steps and interval capabilities that are taken by RMG garment industries. In addition, it provides network view along with concentration on the external environment regarding internationalization of garment industries in Bangladesh.

Exporting with accurate and relevant quantities of knowledge about all the information about markets of other nations, helps exporters of garment industries of Bangladesh to export their garment products. This information works as the primary need to get an entry into the foreign markets with success with help of RMG garment industries that are constrained by resources. On

other hand, internationalization acts as processes of gradual development, which takes place within stages along with accumulation of knowledge, information at each stage. In addition, in initial stages, RMG garment industries develop in the domestic market with no venturing out due to lack of the knowledge regarding foreign operations and foreign markets. With growth in knowledge of RMG garment industries in Bangladesh; there exists internationalization within incremental steps. There exist four stages regarding internationalization such as no regular activities of export, export through representativeness in foreign markets, production and manufacturing in foreign market and sales subsidiary within foreign market.

In the first stage, RMG garment industries carry out with no knowledge about foreign markets with no presence within foreign markets. On the other hand, in the second stage, selling through a sales representative, RMG garment industries does not make any relevant commitment of resources, while, in the third stage, a flow of controlled information appears. On the other hand, in the fourth stage, creation of resource commitment is made. These stages reached when RMG garment industries accumulated significant quantities of knowledge regarding foreign markets. There is emphasis that knowledge about markets of other nations leads to the commitment of resources during the process of decision making by using results depending on commitment done under market.

There are different stages that are involved in innovation of RMG garment industries with determination on the export towards sales ratio. On other hand, when garment industries carry out with enough knowledge, then, it can be converted towards actionable knowledge, which makes garment industries reach the stage of internationalization. In addition, at such juncture, RMG garment industries can start the process of internationalization.

To assess competitive positions regarding the garment industry of Bangladesh and evaluate the competing countries for exporting the garments of apparel industry of Bangladesh to other countries

By 2005, as per WTO (world trade org) policy, there were various facilities such as Quota, GSP and many more in the sector of RMG garment industries in Bangladesh. On other hand, Bangladesh is not an exception as the exports of RMG are the highest sources of earning currency of foreign countries. In addition, to abate poverty within Bangladesh, the rate of unemployment is needed to be decreased by making more opportunities for employment in the sector of non-agriculture. In addition, for the development of the economy, foreign trade with the help of garment industries that are labour intensive allows unemployed people to participate within formal activities in the economy that can carry out the significant role within the process of poverty alleviation. RMG garment industries are keeping a momentous part within such context as entrepreneurs of RMG garment industries are recognized only as producers in foreign markets. On other hand, with immediate influence of the withdrawal of the preferential treatments, there occurs acceptance of challenges regarding global and international marketing within the situation of free market competitiveness as the international marketers. In addition, they need to face 2 levels of the uncertainty that are increasing from several of internal uncontrollable and domestic uncontrollable factors. On other hand, these challenges for the future marketers focus on accommodating such uncertainties to uncontrollable variables to create the market opportunities. In addition, attempts to assess these challenges, weaknesses need to be initiated by the international marketers regarding RMG garment industries. This occurs in a governed and free economy of trade as per WTO in framework of certain possibilities, strengths within consideration towards significant contribution in RMG garment industries towards domestic economy.

One of most vital aspect of the competing in such intensive and competitive world focus in minimizing cost of products and maximizing quality. In addition, textile industries of Bangladesh lack both these aspects. On other hand, BTMA (bd textile mill association) claims about the low cost of manufacturing regarding spinning mills within Bangladesh. It is done as because the cost of production of garments in Bangladesh is quite cheaper than several Asian countries. It includes Pakistan, India, Korea, Thailand, Japan and Indonesia.

5.2. Recommendation

Bangladesh is facing any problems regarding the RMG garment export in the international market. In order to reduce those problems, the country can use some possible way out and that will improve their market competition.

We have found barriers from our research and to prevent these we need to give some recommendations. Each recommendation will be with a particular problem and will be a (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and within a Time Frame) SMART one which is a measurement of effectiveness. A recommendation must be Specific, such as improving the skills of new labor in this industry with 4 months of training; how it will be conducted and what to do with no vague statements. Output has to be Measurable, such as with the change in productivity after training. Certain goals must be Attainable and not something illogical. Goals must also be Relevant to the industry which benefits the stakeholders involved and must be within a particular Time Frame. One of the important recommendations that we have seen is to improve the policies to export RNG to the international market. For example, the Agreement on Textile and Clothing (ATC) act of 1994 was terminated by the government in 2005 which has excluded Bangladesh from the world quota.

Recommendation to improve the policies to export RMG garment in international market

The country needs to improve their policies and regulation which are essential for the exporting purpose. There was an agreement on Textile and clothing (1994) (ATC) that had been terminated by the government from January 1 of the year 2005. This act was helpful to exclude quotas and that was also to maintain equality in the world trade field.

SMART recommendation	Extent to which it is SMART
S- Specific	It is specific because in the primary qualitative data analysis it has shown that the acts are not favorable for the country's economy, although they are introducing a healthy amount of foreign exchange, but they are required to provide huge taxes for accessing international trade markets.
M- Measurable	The recommendation is measurable because the authority needs to conduct a survey in order to analyze the proper condition of the acts that are already available.
A- Attainable	This could be attained by proper act and regulation to maintain equality in all over the international market.
R- Relevant	This recommendation is relevant because to improve the economy the country needs to start new policies to be equal with all other developed countries in the world trade organization. Accurate agreements will help the country to pay less tax to access the international market for business.
T- Time specific	This is time specific because creation of an agreement between the government and world trade organization will require a minimum time.

Table 5.2.1: SMART recommendation for making and using policies

(Source: Created by author)

Action plan:

Activities	Time span
Survey of the existing policies as the exporting condition in Bangladesh	First week - second week
Analyse the report of the survey	Third week - fourth week
Categorizing the list of the requirements	Fifth week
Making plan for the requirement list as per the priority level	Sixth week - eight week
Meeting between the government of Bangladesh and World Trade Organization to fulfil the requirement	Ninth week - tenth week

Table 5.2.2: Action plan for making and using the policies in favour of export of RMG garments

(Source: Created by author)

Improve transportation for the exporting purpose

The government can take further steps to start new airlines in future only for exporting purpose. For this the country needs to first make roads which will connect the international airport in the country with the trade hub. The country can make new airports only for the export purpose in Chittagong, Savar, Ashulia etc which are RMG hubs. The airways of the flight special for the export purpose of the RMG garments need to be direct from Bangladesh to the international target country. This will help to reduce the time of the export and solve the transport problems. The steps will increase the growth rate of the economy of the country.

SMART recommendation	Extent to which it is SMART
S- Specific	This is very specific because the country has less air connection with few international market hubs. In order to access the market of European country and America Bangladesh can start some more flights in direct way. This will reduce the time of export and make more connection with developed country.
M- Measurable	This is measurable because the present numbers of flights will help to decide the future number of flights from the country to developed country. Before starting air flight, the country needs to measure the present status of the aviation in the country.
A- Attainable	This could be attained by government and different aviation companies. The country can start special direct flight only for the export purpose.
R- Relevant	This is relevant recommendation because transport is interrelated factor of the export and to trade the garments in the international market.
T- Time specific	This is time specific because the advent of new flights and new airways need planning and implication of accurate strategy.

Table 5.2.3: SMART recommendation for improving transportation for the exporting purpose

(Source: Created by author)

Action plan:

Activities	Time span
Survey of the existing international direct flights and their ways in Bangladesh by government and aviation companies.	First week - second week
Analyse the result of survey critically	Third week - fourth week

Categorizing the list of the requirements as per the present condition	Fifth week
Making plan for the requirement list as per the priority level	Sixth week - tenth week
Implication of the plan by government of the country and other airline companies	Eleventh week - nineteenth week

Table 5.2.4: Action plan for improving transportation for the exporting purpose

(Source: Created by author)

Mitigating the exporting barriers such as language, management and currency

This program will help the people related to the export business to manage the trade efficiently and the foreign country will show more interest. The agencies may provide training to reduce the currency related barriers. This kind of programs will help to reduce the export barriers and make the business more effective. Mitigation of the language related problem: the country can transmit their messages to the foreign country in a relevant way and even they can understand the consumer's requirements. All these steps will assist the country to increase the international business. The introduction of foreign exchange will increase more due to mitigation of export barriers.

SMART recommendation	Extent to which it is SMART
S- Specific	This is specific because the country is facing the problem in order to conduct the business internationally. They are facing the language related problems and management problems due to huge cultural barriers.
M- Measurable	This is measurable because the percentages of the people related with the international trade and export of RMG garments can be measured based on which the country can understand the importance of the issue.
A- Attainable	This is attainable because the country's government will make a strategy to improve the management status in order to do business with the developed country internationally.
R- Relevant	This recommendation is relevant because the management system needs to be strong in order to maintain the business properly and accurately. By solving the problem, the country can increase the income rate.
T- Time specific	This is time specific because the government or any private organization will make plans to help the local people in order to be more flexible with foreign language, culture and international market conditions.

Table 5.2.5: SMART recommendation for mitigating the exporting barriers such as language, management and currency

(Source: Created by author)

Action plan:

Activities	Time span
Survey of the existing issues related to management and language barriers in the international trade	First week - second week
Analyse the result of survey critically	Third week - fourth week
Categorizing the list of the requirements as per the present condition	Fifth week
Making plan for the requirement list as per the priority level to mitigate the issues related to export barriers	Sixth week - tenth week
Implication of the plan by government and non-government organizations of the country which will help local people to become accustomed with the foreign cultures	Eleventh week - fifteen week

Table 5.2.6: action plan for mitigating the exporting barriers such as language, management and currency

(Source: Created by author)

Improving the quality of the product

In order to increase the export rate of readymade garments in Bangladesh, the companies of garments need to increase their quality of product. This will help them to attract new importers and at the same time, the current customers will be satisfied. Improved quality of the garments will also increase the competitiveness of the industry in respect to others.

SMART recommendations	Extent to which it is smart
S-specific	This recommendation is specific as quality of product is a basic need in order to export. In the quantitative data analysis, it could be seen that a large portion of the garment's managers are not satisfied with the present quality of the products. The quality of the apparels will help the RMG industry to eliminate the barriers and increase the rate of exports.
M-Measurable	In order to increase the quality of the apparels, the managers need to measure the present quality and take appropriate steps for making improvement. Hence, this recommendation is measurable. The management of the garment companies need to detect specific gaps in the quality management, analyse its effect in the quality of the products and then adequate measures need to be taken to rectify the gaps.
A-Attainable	This recommendation could be achieved by regular monitoring of the present system of quality management, observing skills and performance of the labourers, organizing training programs to increase their skills etc. Regular monitoring will help the management to find the gaps in quality management and invest funds in organizing training programs for the workers.
R-Relevant	It is a relevant recommendation because good quality products will help the industry to flourish and expand and at the same time export rate will be increased. Product quality will affect the revenue collection of the industry as the number of importers will increase if the quality of the products is improved. On the other hand, current importers will also get motivated to import more apparel from Bangladesh.
T-Time specific	This recommendation is time-specific. The managers of the garments industry will have to monitor closely and find the gaps in quality management. Then only they will be able to take specific measures to improve quality. At the same time, they will have to organize training programs to increase the efficiency of their staff. These processes are time-specific.

Table 5.2.7: SMART recommendation to increase the quality of the products

(Source: Created by author)

Action plan:

Actions	Time span
Organizing meeting, making commitments in order to increase the quality.	1st week
Monitoring the present system of quality management	2nd to 4th week
Identification and analysis of the gaps	5th to 6th week
Framing steps to fill the gaps	7th to 9th week
Organizing training programs to improve the skills of labors.	10th to 12th week

Table 5.2.8: Action plan for improving the quality of the products

(Source: Created by author)

Recommendation for increasing the workplace safety:

A safe and secure workplace will motivate the workers that will impact their productivity. This will increase the reputation of the industry and will affect the export rate. If the number of accidents in the garment industry is reduced, then this will facilitate the companies to supply orders accurately without any interruption. The workers will be able to work in a healthy and safer environment. The accidents that caused the garment industry of Bangladesh have hampered the reputation of the industry by creating a negative impact in the minds of the importers. In addition, these incidents also affected the performance of the workers by decreasing their motivation. At the same time, Bangladesh RMG sector was continuously monitored by Accord and Alliance, two foreign buyer group to ensure workplace safety. Ensuring overall workplace safety will end such extreme monitoring, renewed GSP benefits, and less regulatory costs.

SMART recommendations	Extent to which it is smart
S-specific	The recommendation of increasing workplace safety is specific as in data analysis, it could be seen that the majority of the garment managers think that accidents in the garment industry of Bangladesh is hampering trade and exports of garment products.
M-Measurable	This Recommendation is measurable as the managers of the garment industry need to access the areas of risk factors and measure the threats. According to the risk appropriate measures need to be taken in order to mitigate the risks. This Could be done by building infrastructure and adopting proper security steps like emergency alarms, fire exit, fire exhausting devices etc. In addition, the condition of the old buildings needs to be accessed.
A-Attainable	Recommendation of improving the safety of the workplace in the garment industry is achievable. The companies of the garment industry need to adopt modern safety technologies and improve the condition of the buildings. This will eliminate the risk of accidents and a safer and healthier workplace will motivate the workers to perform more efficiently.
R-Relevant	This is a relevant recommendation because in recent years several incidents have happened in the garment industry of Bangladesh, which has deteriorated the image of the industry to their importers. Those incidents have created a deep impact in trade and export of garments. Moreover, these accidents have taken several lives of workers. Hence, to improve the image of the industry and increase the export rate, maintaining the workplace safety is inevitable.
T-Time specific	This recommendation of adopting safety measures is time specific. The risk factors need to be detected and proper planning is essential in order to mitigate the risk factors. On the other hand, the organizations of garment industry need to organize training programs for the workers in order to aware them regarding use of safety devices. The whole process is time consuming and a budget needs to be allocated to achieve this recommendation.

Table 5.2.9: SMART recommendation for increasing the workplace safety

(Source: Created by author)

Action plan:

Actions	Time span
Analysing the risk factors	1st to 2nd week
Proper planning to mitigate the risk factors	2nd to 4th week
Budget planning for adopting safety measures	5th week
Organizing training programs to aware the workers about reacting during emergency situations.	6th to 10th week
Installing modern safety devices	11th to 13th week

Table 5.2.10: Action plan for increasing the workplace safety

(Source: Created by author)

Recommendation to increase the productivity of the labors in garment industry:

Labour productivity is another factor that impacts the export of garment products. Skilled and efficient workers will be able to deliver good quality products in the given time. This will create a good impression among the importers. Although the garment industry of Bangladesh has flourished in recent years, training and incentives will motivate the workers to perform more efficiently and their productivity will be increased.

SMART recommendations	Extent to which it is smart
S-specific	The recommendation of increasing the productivity of the labours is specific as this will impact on the export rate. The companies will be able to deliver good quality materials in quick time by increasing the productivity of the staff. In quantitative data analysis, it could be seen that several garment merchants are not satisfied with the productivity of the laborers. The increase in productivity of the laborers will impact the performance of the industry.
M-Measurable	This recommendation is measurable as the management of the garment companies need to access the present performance of the workers and plan accordingly for increasing the productivity. The present performance of the workers could be measured by judging their skill and efficiency.
A-Attainable	The productivity of the workers could be increased by recognition and rewarding. The managers could recognize their effort and award them incentives. This will motivate them to perform better and in turn their productivity will be increased. The recommendation could also be achieved by organizing specific training programs for the workers. Training programs will help the workers to increase their skills and efficiency. Modernization of the garment firms is another way, which can also increase the productivity of the workers.
R-Relevant	It is a relevant recommendation because increase in productivity of the workers will enable them to deliver good quality products. The garment firms will be able export the materials in time. Fine quality products will also attract many new importers.
T-Time specific	The whole process of increasing the productivity of the workers is time specific. The management of the garment firms will access the performance of the workers and then planning will be done accordingly. Organization of training programs to increase the efficiency of the workers is also time bound.

Table 5.2.11: SMART recommendation to increase the productivity of the labors in garment industry

(Source: Created by author)
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Action plan:

Actions	Time span
Analysing the performance of the workers	1st to 3rd week
Offering incentives to the performers	4th week
Giving adequate feedback	5th week
Organizing training programs to increase the efficiency of the workers	6th to 8th week
Training of workers	9th to 11th week
Allocating budget for adopting modern equipment	12th week
Installation of modern equipment	13th to 16th week
Reassessing the performance and productivity of the workers	After 6 months of taking necessary measures of increasing productivity of the workers.

Table 5.2.12: Action plan to increase the productivity of the labors in garment industry

(Source: Created by author)

Market Diversification: RMG products of Bangladesh are majorly exported to EU and US. At some point of time, it has been seen that Bangladesh was the 5th and 7th largest sector to EU and USA respectively. Therefore, for this reason, it is highly required to make the market diversification more. It is a fact that the garment industry has become successful in order to explore the business opportunities in some markets that are away from the US and EU. If the market diversification can be made in a proper manner, then that helps in turnaround and that can be

observed in the exports be made in other countries. It has been noticed that in the financial year 2013, there was negative growth to some extent and that had helped the market to grow rapidly. The overall export growth was approximately 23.1% within the RMG sector. It has been anticipated that the trend of market diversification should be continued and that will help in maintaining growth.

SMART Recommendations	Extent to which it is SMART
S-Specific	This recommendation is specific because market diversification helps in the growth of the garment industry. This in result helps in the exporting of goods to other countries.
M-Measurable	It is measurable because growth of the garment industry can be measured.
A-Attainable	This is attainable by maintaining the growth of the momentum of export earnings.
R-Relevant	This is relevant because exporting of the goods depends on the market growth of the industry. Therefore, it is highly relevant to diversify the market.
T-Time specific	It will be completed within 4 weeks.

Table 5.2.13: Market Diversification

(Source: Created by author)

Action Plan

Activities	Time Span
Making plan for market diversification	1st week
Strategies for market diversification	2nd to 3rd week
Analysis of the growth of market	4th week

Table 5.2.14: Action Plan for Market Diversification

(Source: Created by author)

Training and research: This have been noticed that Bangladesh is not having proper research institutes in relation to the apparel sector and therefore, the marketers or employees are not having any proper knowledge about the garment industry of other countries. It is a fact that the RMG sector is a continuously evolving market and therefore, market research is highly necessary in order to make the business successful. In the current scenario, the design works which are carried out are done mostly with foreign experts and workers. Therefore, BGMEA should establish an institute that provides knowledge about the market as well as provide the training. This initiative should be taken so that employees and laborers can be encouraged.

SMART Recommendations	Extent to which it is SMART
S-Specific	This is specific because if the marketers and labourers do not have any relevant knowledge about the market, then, it damages the exporting of goods to other countries. Therefore, market growth becomes affected.
M-Measurable	The knowledge of the labour can be measured if proper monitoring on their activities of marketing can be done.
A-Attainable	It can be said that this is attainable as it is possible to take the initiative of building a research institute so that the employees can get knowledge about the market.
R-Relevant	It can be considered as relevant because if proper knowledge is not gained, then preference of the customers of other countries cannot be known and furthermore market growth cannot be obtained.
T-Time specific	This can be completed within 7 weeks

Table 5.2.15: Training and research

(Source: Created by author)

Action Plan

Activities	Time Span
Planning for creating research institute	1st to 2nd weeks
Designing the institute	3rd to 5th weeks
Monitoring the progress of designing institute	6th to 7th weeks

Table 5.2.16: Action Plan of Training and research

(Source: Created by author)

Development of the Backward Linkage in Textile Sector:

Appropriate and proper policies and procedures that should be implemented applied and adopted for ensuring development of the backward linkage. The sector of RMG garment industries remains dependent on the export of woven materials, dying materials and knit materials. Henceforth, it needs further improvement to make and source all the minimum items from Bangladesh to other nations.

SMART Recommendation	Extent to which it is SMART
S- Specific	This recommendation is specific because backward linkages are needed to be used by an industry of the manufactured inputs from other industry.
M- Measurable	This recommendation is measurable because it provides success to RMG garment industries on basis of effectiveness of linkages. These sectors should operate both in backward as well as forward linkages of RMG garment industries.
A- Attainable	This recommendation is attainable because it needs to give effective control on supply of the raw materials, ancillary services and components. These are required to produce the final product with flow of production that is needed to be prevented from getting interrupted.
R- Relevant	This recommendation is relevant because improvement of the backward linkages is required to develop effective strategies for marketing services.
T- Time Specific	This recommendation is time specific because it needs to be completed within 7 weeks.

Table 5.2.17: SMART Recommendation for Development of the Backward Linkage in Textile Sector

(Source: Created by author)

Action Plan:

Activities	Time Span
Use of manufactured inputs from the other nations	First week

Analyse the effectiveness of the linkages of sectors in RMG garment industries	Second week to Third week
To increase effectiveness on supply control from Bangladesh to other nations	Fourth week to Fifth week
Implementation of strategies of marketing services	Fifth week to Sixth week
Analysing outcomes in development of the backward linkages and move forward for further improvements	Sixth week to Seventh week

Table 5.2.18: Action plan for Development of the Backward Linkage in Textile Sector

(Source: Created by author)

Ensuring Uninterrupted Supply of Electricity for the RMG units:

Interruption in the supply of electricity should be developed and improved immediately in RMG garment industries of Bangladesh. With help of the government, certain measures are taken for identification of issues regarding supply of the power in these garment industries in Dhaka. These issues include economizing of its use, setting up of generation plants of power of small scale, fixing up of some sequential holidays regarding factories and industries of garments and textiles in various commercial zones and different industrial areas and many more. On other hand, the government should take certain initiative to the source of usage of the solar system. In addition, there needs to be usage of the latest alternatives of technology for production of electricity.

Henceforth, operations of the ecosystem along with promotion of green production should play an effective role. Thus, clearing the power from all kinds of wastes of textile industries are required to be carried out with an approach that should be friendly in nature. It should be assisting uninterrupted supply of the power to RMG garment industries. One of the major problems of power sector in Bangladesh is transmission. Garment industries are spread all over the country and it is imperative that transmission channel is improved in order to supply power uninterrupted in garment sector.

SMART Recommendation	Extent to which it is SMART
S- Specific	This recommendation is specific because supply of electricity is required to boost up the business of garment industries.
M- Measurable	This recommendation is measurable because it should be operated along with the policies of long term to support and remain competitive within global market.
A- Attainable	This recommendation is attainable because it needs to improve the current condition along with possible steps for development of efficiency functioning regarding ports of Bangladesh.
R- Relevant	This recommendation is relevant because supply of electricity directly effect on predictability of price for some period in a textile business.
T- Time Specific	This recommendation is time specific because it needs to be completed within 4 weeks.

Table 5.2.19: SMART Recommendation for Ensuring Uninterrupted Supply of Electricity for the RMG units

(Source: Created by author)

Action Plan:

Activities	Time Span
Analysing and implementing policies of long term	First week
Taking possible steps for development of efficiency functioning	First week to Second week
Analysing predictability of price	Second week to Third week
Implementing private captive of power projects	Third week to Fourth week
Installation of latest technology to increase use of power efficiently	Fourth week

Table 5.2.20: Action plan for Ensuring Uninterrupted Supply of Electricity for the RMG units

(Source: Created by author)

Delivery Time within Shipment need to be cut down for RMG Industries:

Government of Bangladesh should reconsider their decisions in order to set up bonded warehouses centrally. In addition to this, the World Bank recommended the development of bonded warehouses as centrally for textile and RMG garment industries.

SMART Recommendation	Extent to which it is SMART
S- Specific	This recommendation is specific because delivery time of exported garment products needs to be depending on contribution in process of business along with outcomes of this business.
M- Measurable	This recommendation is measurable because it can measure all the dramatic changes that focus on landscape of the composition of exports of RMG garment industries from Bangladesh.
A- Attainable	This recommendation is attainable because it should be directly related to supply chain rather than the management of process within minimisation of lead time.
R- Relevant	This recommendation is relevant because delivery time carries out with ability to get deliver the products quickly within provided time period. It can directly affect sales, exports and revenues.
T- Time Specific	This recommendation is time specific because it needs to be completed within 5 weeks.

Table 5.2.21: SMART Recommendation for Delivery Time within Shipment need to be cut down for RMG Industries

(Source: Created by author)

Action Plan:

Activities	Time Span
Analysing management of lead time	First week
Focussing on landscape of the composition of exports of RMG garment industries	Second week
Analysing and improving supply chain management	Third week
Focussing on improvement of sales, exports and revenues	Fourth week
Implementing and managing time of delivery	Fifth week

Table 5.2.22: Action plan for Delivery Time within Shipment need to be cut down for RMG Industries

(Source: Created by author)

Recommendation to eradicate number of child labor

Bangladesh use Child labor in garment industry in order to maintain low production cost. This is affecting exports of garment at present. Tom Herkin, a congressman has placed a bill called Herkin Bill in order to restrict import of garments in countries of the US. According to this bill, USA will not be able to import garments from those countries that use child labor in garment production. This bill has created barriers for export of garments to USA. Bangladesh can hire more adult workers in order to eliminate child labor from their system.

SMART recommendations	Extent to which it is smart
S-specific	This recommendation is specific as it will help RMG industry to export their garments to USA in order to earn more financial benefits.
M-Measurable	This industry can measure their revenue after eradicating child labor from their business. They will be able to monitor improvement of their earnings.
A-Attainable	RMG industry can replace child labor with efficient adult workers and they will help them to enhance their productivity.
R-Relevant	This recommendation is relevant as this will help this industry to trade in USA and they will be able to maximize their financial benefit.
T-Time specific	In order to follow this recommendation, garment industry needs to provide time in their recruitment process and they will need to hire adult workers on the basis of their professional skills.

Table 5.2.23: SMART recommendation to reduce number of child labour

(Source: Created by author)

Actions	Time span
Estimate financial loss for losing USA market	1st week
Proper planning to eradicate child labor	2nd to 4th week
Budget planning for new recruitment process	5th week
Planning for media exposure regarding this approach	6th week
Conducting recruitment process	7th to 12th week

Table 5.2.24: Action plan to reduce number of child labour

(Source: Created by author)

Improving relationship with other garment exporter countries

Bangladesh needs to develop and maintain strategic relationships with other garment exporter countries like China, Ethiopia and Myanmar in order to obtain more advantages in their business. They can obtain raw materials for garment production from China as China is termed as the house of raw materials. On the other hand, Ethiopia and Myanmar are important parts of the garment export industry and they need input materials like packaging, fabrics, accessories and so on. Bangladesh can supply these supply materials in order to build and maintain good strategic relationships with these countries. By this approach this industry of Dhaka can earn more financial benefits from their business.

SMART recommendations	Extent to which it is smart
S-specific	This recommendation is specific as this will guide this industry to focus on developing strategic relationships with their competitors. They will be able to figure out possible solutions for their existing barriers by discussing with other exporter countries.
M-Measurable	RMG industry can estimate their earnings after following this practice and that will help them to understand financial benefit.
A-Attainable	This recommendation is attainable as the garment industry of Dhaka can take initiative to communicate with other exporters and can develop business relationships with them.
R-Relevant	The RMG industry is dependent on other countries for raw materials. For example, if they can build a strategic relationship with China, they will be able to obtain raw material from this country.
T-Time specific	This recommendation is time specific as this will help this industry to gain raw material for garment production easily. They will be able to deliver orders within time.

Table 5.2.25: SMART recommendation to improve relationship with other garment exporter countries

(Source: Created by author)

Actions	Time span

Recognizing benefit of strategic relationship	1st and 2nd week
Meeting of garment export organization in this regard	3rd week
Communicating with other garment export countries	4th to 5th week
Discussion about deals	6th to 7th week
Budget planning for deals	8th to 12th week

Table 5.2.26: Action plan to improve relationship with other garment exporter countries

(Source: Created by author)

Recommendation to ensure affordable price of garments to avoid competition

The RMG industry of Bangladesh will require setting affordable prices in order to improve their export business. Affordable prices can attract more customers towards this industry. Competitors are introducing innovative approaches to set affordable prices for their customers and this aspect can be considered as potential threats for the garment industry of Dhaka. Over the last few years, competitors have introduced innovative price-cutting policy for export of garments. On the other hand, it has been noticed that Bangladesh has not taken any initiative to develop this kind of pricing policies. Reportedly, China has dropped their export price remarkably in US countries. They can occupy maximum market area by this approach. Bangladesh needs to work on this matter seriously

in order to maintain their business position. This kind of policy can be developed with the help of experts and the government. This approach will help them to set an affordable price for their garments.

SMART recommendations	Extent to which it is smart
S-specific	This recommendation is specific as setting affordable price will help this industry to attract more customers and this will help this industry to explore their business in international market.
M-Measurable	This industry can measure their annual revenue after setting affordable price for their garments. After developing price cutting policy, revenue of this industry will be increased.
A-Attainable	RMG industry can take advice from experts and government in this regard and can attain this recommendation.
R-Relevant	This recommendation is relevant as this aspect will help to improve export of garments to new markets.
T-Time specific	This industry needs to provide prior time to develop plan for new price cutting policy.

Table 5.2.27: SMART recommendation to ensure affordable price of garments to avoid competition

(Source: Created by author)

Actions	Timespan
Identification of needs of affordable price of garments	1st week
Planning for policy development	2nd to 3rd week
Acquiring advice from experts	4th week
Budget planning	5th to 6th week
Developing a price-cutting policy	7th to 10th week

Table 5.2.28: Action plan to ensure the affordable price of garments to avoid competition

(Source: Created by author)

Recommendation of including e-commerce while exporting garments:

E-commerce is a modern and efficient channel, which could be adopted by the garment manufacturers and exporters of Bangladesh to expand into international markets. The inclusion of the internet and networking in business has simplified the system of trade and export. This has also helped the firms to promote their products efficiently. The inclusion of eCommerce could also help the garment industry of Bangladesh by removing the barrier of communication with the customers. The managers could easily communicate with the clients by using email and the internet. The e-commerce strategy will help the country to reach many potential customers in a short period. Ultimately, this will affect trading by increasing the export rate and will also help the industry to get modernized.

SMART recommendation	The extent to which it is SMART
S- Specific	The inclusion of eCommerce in the trading process is specific as it will help the garment firms to communicate with the clients in a better way and it will also enable them to reach a large number of clients around the globe. This recommendation will also help the firms to exclude cultural barriers.
M- Measurable	The managers of the garment industry need to measure the extent upon which they can adopt eCommerce. The problems and barriers need to be identified and proper measures need to be taken to mitigate the problems with the help of the internet and networking.
A- Attainable	Adaptation of e-commerce could be achieved by changing the traditional setting by adopting eCommerce. Promotion and marketing need to be done with the help of social media platforms, websites and other online trading applications. Better communication with clients could be done with the help of emails.
R- Relevant	This recommendation of adopting e-commerce is relevant as it can help the RMG industry to expand further in the international market by creating many chances. It will also simplify the process of exporting and will also help the management of the industry by eliminating many barriers like communication problems, cultural barriers etc.
T- Time-specific	E-commerce is modern technology. The inclusion process of this technology is time-bound. The management of the garment companies will analyse the present situation and then they will adopt e-commerce strategy. Installation of the system and training the employees about the system also involves time. The whole process of analysis, installation involves nearly one month.

Table 5.2.29: SMART recommendation of including e-commerce while exporting garments

(Source: Created by author)

Action plan:

Activities	Timespan
Analysis of the present situation and identifying the problems	1st to 3rd week
Proper planning about the inclusion of internet and networking in the export process	4th week
Budget allocation for installing modern e-commerce technology	5th week
Installation of networking devices	6th to 10th week
Training of the employees about the usage and advantage of e-commerce	11th to 13th week

Table 5.2.30: Action plan of including e-commerce while exporting garments

(Source: Created by author)

Summary of the SMART recommendation

Even though ATC act is providing a healthy amount of foreign exchange into the economy, we still need to give a lot of tax and it is not providing any favorable Specifics to the industry. The authority can find it Measurable that this act can be refined and work in a way to improve the economy. A proper regulation can be Attainable which can make it Relevant for greater access to the international market with less tax to pay. There also needs to be an agreement with the government in a Time frame as to how much there is progress every day with proper action plans. Another recommendation is improving transportation for the exporting purpose. We need to create a new airline for the transportation which will only be for exporting and build better trade hubs

(Chittagong, Ashulia RMG) that will lower the time required. The SMART recommendation for this is: We are providing a Specific solution of a flight plan for this problem as we are unable to access some of the European markets due to less flights. It can be Measurable as we can judge the exporting amount of previous and future trades regarding profits. It is Attainable as this can be worked with different aviation companies and it is Relevant as it will increase exports. It is within a Time frame as planning all of this will require a time table. The 3rd recommendation is mitigating the export barriers such as language, management and currency. For our export business, we can see the problem of no proper idea being implemented with the outside culture. For this, we need a proper training program so that these problems can be reduced. With language problems, we need to keep foreign language courses. This is Specific as we are holding language and management policy as a cultural barrier and we are creating a training program. It is Measurable as we can find how beneficial this program will be and is Attainable. It is Relevant as it is a problem for our industry and government organizations can help to make it possible within a Time frame. The 4th recommendation is improving the quality of the product so that customers will purchase even more. It is Specific as quality can notify us of the export rate. It is Measurable with new instruments, providing new training to workers or new management styles which might improve the quality for a certain goal. This is Relevant as it is essential to improve the quality in the industry and it will be required to be in a Time frame. The 5th recommendation is increasing the workplace safety and it is an important issue because it is having harmed the exporting of products (Rana Plaza incident) for our country and we are being monitored for it internationally. This will also increase worker's productivity as they can work in a better environment. It is Specific as we have seen with data analysis that this safety issue exists in the industry. It is Measurable as building infrastructure is important (fire alarms, fire exits). It is Attainable as new infrastructure being

developed with investment will improve workplace safety. It is Relevant as it is confirming safety and increasing goodwill internationally. It is also required to be done within a Time frame and will need some time for this industry with regulations. The final recommendation is to increase the productivity of labor in garment industry as it is essential to decrease lead time and provide fast deliver which can improve impressions on importers. For this we need to provide training and incentives that can increase efficiency. It is Specific as it will increase export rates and Measurable with the training being provided to the workers. It is Attainable to increase productivity with training and Relevant to increase exports. This has to be done within a Time frame with an action plan.

Market Diversification - Bangladesh usually exports to American and the European Union. If we want more secure form of trade, we need to diversify with countries or products. This way we can specifically grow the garments industry, lower barriers, measure it with types of products to certain countries, it is attainable and relevant as it can provide more opportunity. It is also time specific within a frame to obtain these goals. In Bangladesh, there are no proper research institutions for apparel and the RMG sector is constantly evolving which requires a lot of training for more export. Specifically, there needs to be proper knowledge for workers, measurable by monitoring benefits from training, attainable and relevant with the industry, and within a time frame with the action plan. Development of the backward linkage in the textile industry can help with improving the current policies. This way, we can attain the proper materials needed for production. It is specific to develop for the industry, measurable for the effectiveness of the development, attainable with effective control for final product, relevant and time specific as well. Ensuring supply of electricity for the RMG can help the production process and not slow it down. This needs to be used efficiently to not waste energy, provide sequential holidays to maintain balanced demand, utilize

solar energy with appropriate technology, transmit the supply of energy to the exact demand. This is specific to boost the industry, measurable of the production levels with the energy, attainable, relevant and time specific with the action plans. Delivery time of shipment needs to be cut down in the industry with bonded warehouse. This is specific for the bonded warehouse, measurable of the improvement from this facility, attainable, relevant and specific with the action plan. Eradicating number of child labor is essential to maintain export levels. It is specific to lower child labor and increase export, measurable to see if this issue is lowered, attainable to remove this problem from the industry, relevant as it goes with foreign policies and time specific with the action plan. Improving the relationship with other garments export countries (China, Ethiopia, Myanmar) as we are dependent raw materials from some of them and input materials (packaging). This strategy can provide Bangladesh with financial benefits by developing relationships. It is specific to focus on the relationship, measurable to lower trade restrictions, attainable with diplomacy, relevant for strategic alliances and time specific with the plan. Ensure affordable prices of garments to avoid competition (China) with innovation to increase exports. It is specific as price-cutting is a solution towards the barriers, measurable for the annual revenue, attainable, relevant and time specific as well. Including e-commerce for exporting garments to efficiently promote products across the globe with different clients. It is specific to include e-commerce with the industry, measurable for the growth with effective advertising, attainable with promotions, relevant with the industry and within a time frame.

5.3 Limitations of the research

While carrying out a research project, the researcher faced several challenges. The researcher had to deal with unseemly interactions with government institutions and businesses. In addition to this,

researchers had to face issues with data filtering and irrelevance of the data. The researcher did not find proper data because several websites cannot be accessed properly. It has been found that researchers were unable to interact properly with the managers and garment owners due to their time-pressured and busy schedule. Few garment owners did not have enough time to participate in the survey and hence, relevant data could not be obtained properly. Interaction programs need to be between researchers and establishments. As these were not done properly, therefore, data related to the topic cannot be obtained. Apart from this, there were time constraints. To conduct research of such depth, much time is needed, and, in this research, researchers did not get enough time and therefore, collection of proper data was difficult to be received. In addition to this, researchers had financial obstructions and therefore execution became difficult. For conducting the primary investigation, financial constraints were present as well. At the same time, the collected data may have some issues regarding response bias. For example, garments owner may say that they had taken step to improve quality of product in order to give a positive view about the industry while in reality they didn't. It is difficult to find out without industry access and quality assessment which is beyond the scope of researcher.

There are a few challenges that we have faced. The first is the problems with communication with the government bodies, problems of data filtering, improper data with websites not being accessible, not enough time with owners and managers. Interaction program is also required for researchers to obtain information for the topic and more time is needed to conduct detailed research. There is also a financial obligation which caused limitations and there were biases with quality through managers possibly.

5.4 Future Scope of research

In this research study, the desired spectrum of quantitative and qualitative data was not possible to be obtained due to time and financial constraints. Therefore, future researchers have ample scope to elaborate and properly expand this research. This dissertation can serve as the secondary source for future researchers. The future researchers can take help from this dissertation and extend their findings as suits their focus topic. In addition, researchers in the future can propose additional business strategies so that barriers in the exporting of the garments to other countries can be mitigated as soon as possible. The recommendations, which are not given in the current study, can be given by the future researchers so that more theories can be formulated, and strategies obtained. Furthermore, researchers can make a comparison between the exports of garments of different countries so that positioning and conditions of Bangladesh RMG sector can be identified and compared. Researchers also have the scope to provide innovative strategies so that it becomes easy for the garment industry to strategize for sustainability and competitive advantage.

Original Contribution of the research:

The main contribution of this research was that it presents a comprehensive view of the overall barriers of the garment industry in a research framework. The detail secondary analysis found out multiple issues regarding the export barriers and present them coherently in a structured manner. The survey was critical to found out the current state about export barriers from the industry personnel. It also gave us a general outlook of the industry. The researcher found that the demography of managerial people in the industry is basically middle-aged people with in general 10-30 years of working experience. They are currently facing high business risk. They found that careful foreign policy like alliance with NATO is essential to mitigate evolving business risks. They are facing various source of problems like legal, non-proliferation. The government policy

seems to be ineffective to cope up against the new rising dynamic problem though they find that policy of the past was effective to resolve past issues. The research showed that industry competitiveness is based on low price of the product. The low cost of natural gas is major cost benefit and it indicate industry turmoil in future as gas reserve is being depleted. The researcher found some seemingly contradictory findings. The market is worried about the labour standard issues, foreign policy about strict labour law. At the same time, it is complaining about low productivity of the industry and finding that labour skill set is a big problem. This is quite inevitable for an industry which is highly dependent on low labour cost benefit with very low R&D investment. The middle aged, high experience nature of the managers also indicate that there is less opportunity for innovation and higher growth in career for professionals. Not surprisingly, such industry is not attractive for dynamic innovative people and entrepreneurs who vie for rapid growth. They are therefore facing quality assurance issue and though they are taking steps to raise quality, they are constrained by the skill set of the workforce. The researcher found that present business world is extremely dynamic and issues like Brexit, inflation rate which creates market volatility is creating huge problem to cop up with as the industry lack vital workforce with dynamic mindset. Not surprisingly, the industry is still rife with infrastructural problem like backward linkage issue and having difficulty with diversification. There are issues with individual aspects like permit and their relative magnitude has been discovered. There is cultural, language, environmental, and business knowledge barrier and no comprehensive framework to address these issues. The industry with its backdated mindset, over reliance on labour, and lack of new initiative is fraught with major infrastructural, work, cultural, and knowledge issues. The researcher also found out multitude of ideas from different managers about their idea about effective policy, transport, language, quality, safety, labour productivity, market diversification and various steps

they have taken. Then the researcher analysed the problems found in the survey with further secondary literature analysis and build a comprehensive research framework and bound them into a coherent framework. Finally, the research not only showed the broad picture, it also focuses on developing an action plan with SMART objective for the policymakers, industry personnel to work with. The researcher provided detail plan regarding this. Therefore, the research gave an immediate action plan alongside providing initial workplan to address problems of high importance.

The descriptive research framework is useful to give a detailed picture of the current scenario so that policymakers, industry personnel can have a comprehensive idea about the situation. Then they can draw the detailed long-term plan for situation improvement. Such comprehensive plan initiates with immediate plan, but judge success and failure on the basis of progress toward the long-term goal. Therefore, any improvement from one project won't create over-satisfaction as involved personnel know that success should be measure based on overall progress. At the same time, they won't be frustrated at the failure of any steps or project as success may be correlated with other or any stall in progress would disappear if certain other conditions are overcome. This actually instil a sense of purpose. But to do these, there should be detailed framework present with immediate action plan. The current research provides this framework and action plan which is its major contribution. At the same time, it had worked in various aspects of the barrier issues about the RMG export industry from which other researcher can gain useful insight.

We could not undertake extended qualitative and quantitative research on this topic as there was a time constraint. Future researchers have an elaborate scope based on this research to expand on it. The findings from this research can be used with analysis to mitigate the barriers through strategies. The recommendations given can be used to create further strategies and compare research of garments industry from different countries to understand the position of Bangladesh

on a global scale with innovate strategy and developments. Original contribution of the research provides a comprehensive view for the garments industry but lacks knowledge-based review and smart based recommendation. Secondary analysis has a provided a general outlook which showed us that the demography of managers is middle aged with experience and wants to mitigate the current problems. The industry is also shown to face legal barriers and does not have effective government policies. The only competitive advantage is the low-priced products which is a cause of natural gas in the country but this will also deplete There are also some contradictory findings such as the market labor standard issue (training, skill) according to foreign policies and exporting. This is due to lack of capital investment and research. The cost will be high to develop these in the industry to increase production. Technological development is required to tackle this and young entrepreneurs need to come forward. Quality issues are also present as the current business world is dynamic which cause market volatility problems (inflation, Brexit). The proper mindset and vitality are lacking to handle these issues. Infrastructure has problems with backward linkages and diversification. Cultural knowledge is low which requires a comprehensive framework to update the mindset. The various steps required to find solutions for these problems are coming from different mangers in the garments industry which can be made into a plan. The benefit of this research is the overall compressive framework created for the policy makers. The plan has to be long-term which will need constant updates to be adaptable. Therefore, as the research is based on actual practitioners in the industry, the solutions can be made detailed and effective for a proper action plan.

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Appendices:

Appendix 1:

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at the website below. Please contact the author for further information.

(Source: <https://www.textiletoday.com.bd/a-midyear-review-of-rmg-textiles-export/>)

Appendix 2:

(Source: https://www.google.co.in/search?biw=1242&bih=602&tbm=isch&sa=1&ei=-EYNW9eiCIX3vgTxoKuACA&q=Export+barriers+of+garment+industry+Bangladesh&oq=Export+barriers+of+garment+industry+Bangladesh&gs_l=img.3...3220.5529.0.5765.11.11.0.0.0.0.247.1055.0j5j1.6.0....0...1c.1.64.img..5.0.0....0.xeK2LTMnVL4#imgrc=WBWOgJjW6v2lvM:)

Appendix 3:

(Source:

[https://www.google.co.in/search?biw=1242&bih=602&tbm=isch&sa=1&ei=_0YNW57WKcr_vASvko-YAQ&q=export+base+theory&oq=Export+base+&gs_l=img.1.0.0i24k118.154940.155536.0.156974.4.4.0.0.0.0.235.568.0j2j1.3.0....0...1c.1.64.img..1.3.567...0j0i67k1.0.Y02Hffc kWYg#imgrc=g3h5z-ekrtCywM:\)](https://www.google.co.in/search?biw=1242&bih=602&tbm=isch&sa=1&ei=_0YNW57WKcr_vASvko-YAQ&q=export+base+theory&oq=Export+base+&gs_l=img.1.0.0i24k118.154940.155536.0.156974.4.4.0.0.0.0.235.568.0j2j1.3.0....0...1c.1.64.img..1.3.567...0j0i67k1.0.Y02Hffc kWYg#imgrc=g3h5z-ekrtCywM:))

Appendix 4: Questionnaire

Q1. What is your age?

Age Group	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
25 to 35 years			
35 to 45 years			
45 to 55 years			
55 to 65 years			

Q2. How long are you working in the RMG industry in Dhaka?

Working time	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Less than 5 years			
10 years			
20 years			
More than 30 years			

Q3. As owners of RMG industries in Bangladesh, do you face any barrier in export?

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Yes			
No			

Q4. Does export business carry out with many barriers while exporting garments from Bangladesh?

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Strongly agree			
Agree			
Neutral			
Disagree			
Strongly disagree			

Q5. What are the ways to tackle the barriers in the export of the garments from Bangladesh?

Ways to tackle export barriers	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Collective security with its allies within NATO			
Foreign policy and national security requirements			
Terrorism concerns			
Internal repression			

Q6. What are the legal barriers that are to be faced by owners of RMG garment industries in Dhaka?

Legal Barriers faced by Owners of RMG Garment Industries	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
International legal commitments with obligations			
Non-proliferation policy			
Violations of human rights			

Q7. Are government policies are suitable for exporting garments?

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Strongly agree			
Agree			
Neither agree nor disagree			
Disagree			
Strongly disagree			

Q8: Do you think that price of the garment products acts as a driver in export?

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
The price is high			
The price is low and competitive enough			

Q9: Do you agree that the qualities of the products are satisfactory enough for exporting?

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Strongly agree			
Agree			
Neither agree nor disagree			
disagree			
Strongly disagree			

Q10. In your opinion, how is the competitiveness level in the garment industry of Bangladesh?

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
High			
Medium			
Low			

Q11. What are the low-cost energy factors that help in mitigating the barriers of RMG industry?

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
Natural Gas			
Electricity			

Q12. Do you think labour safety and industrial labour infrastructure can create barriers in the garment industry of Bangladesh?

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
Strongly agree			
Agree			
Neutral			
Disagree			
Strongly disagree			

Q13. In your opinion, how much bank interests affect the RMG sector of Bangladesh?

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
Very High			
High			
Medium			
Low			
Very Low			

Q14. In your opinion, what are the main financial barriers that are related to costs of garment industry?

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
High rate of interest			
Financial literacy lacking			
Unwillingness to know about costs			

Q15. Do you think that country-wise export level from Bangladesh is effective?

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
Yes			
No			

Q16. Due to the political turmoil, which part of the garment sector gets affected?

Options	Response percentages	Response Frequency	Total respondents
Production			
Distribution			
Export			

Q17. What are the customs related issues faced by exporters for exporting garments of RMG industry from Bangladesh?

Customs Related Issues	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Rates of customs duty			
Export permit fee			
Value-added tax			
Export permits system			
Supplementary duty			
Excise duty			

Q18. What are the additional documentation processes that are hurdling the exporters of Bangladesh?

Additional Documentation Process	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Certificate for valid membership from registered trade association			
Proof regarding payment of the renewal fees			
Copy of TIN Certificate by the tax authority			
A declaration within triplicate			
Documents for export policy			
Clearance permits			
Export permit			

Q19. What are the major threats in overseas that are faced by exporters of Bangladesh?

Major Threats	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Emerging market in other nations			
Raised competition with the local garment industries			
Political unrest for smooth functioning in RMG garment industries			
Lack of electricity			

Q20. What are the constraints that are suffered by owners of garment industries in Bangladesh?

Constraints	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Absence regarding skilled manpower			
Price competitiveness			
Quality aspects			
Linkage backward activities			

Q21. What are the factors that affect the diversification of exports from Bangladesh?

Factors affecting the Diversification of Export	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Establishment of supremacy			
The exploitation of incentive of subsidy			
Acquisition of transportation facilities			
Sharing steadily and growing demands within the international market			
Strong outlook for the shrimp export			

Q22. What are the current export conditions of RMG industry owners in Dhaka?

Current Export Conditions	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Sensational development			
The protected market as per MFA			
Financial improvement			
Political issue			
Supply of apparel products			

Q23. What are opportunities of Bangladesh garments, which can be realised within the international market?

Opportunities	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Reliability			
Quality assurance			
Garments quota system			
Labour cost			
Sound cooperation			

Q24. Are you facing more problems in exporting garments after Brexit?

Options	Percentage of Response	Response frequency	Total Respondents
Yes			
No			

Q25. Do you have enough skilled labour in this garment industry?

Options	Percentage of Response	Response frequency	Total Respondents
Yes			
No			

Q26. Do you agree that educating labour can contribute to garment industry?

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Strongly agree			
Agree			
Neutral			
Disagree			
Strongly disagree			

Q27. Can competitors be considered as a threat to the export of garments?

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Yes			
No			

Q28. Are you taking initiatives to improve the quality of garments to export?

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
We have taken initiatives			
We are thinking about it			
Improvement not required			

Q29. Do you agree that Herkin Bill has affected garment industry?

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Strongly agree			
Agree			
Neutral			
Disagree			
Strongly disagree			

Q30. What is the level of risks regarding lack of resource in the Garment industry?

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
High			
Moderate			
Low			

Q31. Do you agree that the Quota system has affected the RMG industry?

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Strongly agree			
Agree			
Neutral			
Disagree			
Strongly disagree			

Q32. Are you facing problems regarding dealing with overseas customers?

Options	Percentage of the Response	Response Frequency	Total Respondents
Yes			
No			

Q 33: Did the productivity of the labourers are sufficient to boost the export of RMG?

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Productivity is sufficient			
Productivity needs to be increased			

Q34: Do you agree that inflation is a major barrier in the export of garment industry?

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Strongly agree			
agree			
Neither agree nor disagree			
disagree			
Strongly disagree			

Q35: Do you think that the exchange rate could affect the export of garment products in Bangladesh?

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Fall in the exchange rate will make export cheaper			
Fall in the exchange rate will hamper in raw material collection			
Fall in the exchange rate may decrease the demand			

Q36: Do you think that double taxation can be considered as a barrier in exporting of garment products?

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Yes			
No			

Q37: Are export licenses easily available in Bangladesh?

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Yes			
No			

Q38: Do you agree that the GDP of Bangladesh acts as a barrier in the export of RMG?

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Strongly agree			
agree			
Neither agree nor disagree			
disagree			
Strongly disagree			

Q39: Do you think that accidents in RMG industries are affecting export in Bangladesh?

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Yes			
No			

Q40: What do you recommend to increase the export rate of RMG?

Opinions	Respondents	Percentage	Total number of respondents
Improvement in government policies			
Increase the productivity of the labours			
Improving the quality of the products			
Controlling the price			

Appendix 5: Qualitative Data Interpretations

Q1. What kind of Barriers are you facing at present?

1st Manager	2nd Manager	3rd manager	4th Manager

Q2. What strategies have you developed to mitigate challenges?

1st Manager	2nd Manager	3rd manager	4th Manager

Q3. How barriers are affecting customers overseas?

1st Manager	2nd Manager	3rd manager	4th Manager

Q4. What strategies have you developed to improve the export system?

1st Manager	2nd Manager	3rd manager	4th Manager